

A guideline-based framework for building and maintaining secure and cost-effective smart contracts

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Abstract

There is an explosion of interest in Blockchain technology. To date, Blockchain is widely used in sectors such as financial transactions, supply chain, health, and other sectors including asset management. This technology offers users the ability to interact through a peer-to-peer network system without trusting each other and without any intermediary. Blockchain technology presents interesting characteristics including machine-based decentralized governance, transparency, and immutability. These characteristics allow the Blockchain to ensure fast peer-to-peer transactions in which data are recorded, publicly available, and impossible to be altered by anyone. The development of features such as smart contract- a software program running on top of the Blockchain has allowed the Blockchain to extend its application beyond financial transactions.

However, the implementation of smart contracts on top of the Blockchain does not guarantee that smart contracts are secure and free from defects. Many smart contracts have been the target of attacks resulting in huge loss of data and assets. Smart contract vulnerabilities, therefore, limit the impact of the Blockchain on businesses and practitioners. The existing research to tackle smart contract vulnerabilities is mainly focused on vulnerability classification and static analysis tools. Although these solutions may help to deal with smart contract security, they do not prevent smart contract developers from introducing errors in their code. Furthermore, considering the immutability of Blockchain which prevents smart contract code from being altered, these solutions are not effective enough to deal with smart contract security.

In this thesis, we aim to provide a comprehensive solution to support secure smart contract development. To achieve our goal, we explore other existing security solutions including security programming practices and patterns, software metrics from non-blockchain software, and maintainability approaches from smart contracts to propose a comprehensive guideline-based framework.

Firstly, we investigate the security programming practices and patterns of the non-Blockchain software in smart contracts by evaluating their applicability as well as their implementation cost. Security programming practices and patterns which are widely used in the non-Blockchain software development process have been contributing to improving the security of the non-Blockchain software. In this research, we investigate the applicability of a list of security programming practices and their cost through a case study involving smart contracts. By using systematic judgment and statistical methods, the result of our study shows that security programming practices and patterns from non-Blockchain software can be applied to smart contracts, and their implementation cost is not significant enough to deter practitioners from implementing them.

Secondly, we look at security metrics by investigating their applicability to smart contracts. Looking at security metrics to complement the previous investigation to measure the security level of smart contracts during development. Given the immutability of Blockchain, we intend to provide developers with tools to decide if their smart contracts are ready to be deployed. Therefore, we empirically evaluate the applicability of the identified security metrics from three measurement properties (construct, measurement, and reliability) by using a case study involving a list of smart contracts. The result of this research shows that most of the security metrics from non-blockchain software can also be implemented in smart contracts and some help to measure smart contract security.

Furthermore, this thesis also investigates the cost and the evolution of smart contracts implementing upgradability standard methods provided by the Ethereum community. We look at this direction as it may help to improve the smart contract security by updating the security level during the maintenance if the practitioner can afford the cost. We, therefore, statistically evaluate the cost, size, complexity, and quality of the smart contract over a period through a case study involving a list of 18 smart contract projects. The research results

show that, among the upgradability methods, the EIP-2535 implies less cost for smart contract maintenance, and that the smart contract evolutionary behaviour with regard to size, complexity, and quality follows Lehman's laws.

Finally, a guideline-based framework is developed for the development of secure- and cost-effective smart contracts with the insights identified from our investigations. The proposed framework is based on foundations that have been elaborated with the elements that we identified and considered as the factors of the security, and cost improvement of the smart contract development. This proposed framework includes both the development and maintenance phases of smart contracts. An example of an abstract implementation of this framework is provided in this thesis.

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Chapter 1. Introduction

In 2008, Satoshi Nakamoto, an anonymous person proposed a new kind of financial system called Bitcoin[1] which, unlike the traditional financial system, did not require any trusted third party such as a financial bank, or even the government. Bitcoin with its underlying technology 'Blockchain', is described as a fully decentralized cash system, allowing anyone to transact financial digital assets so-called cryptocurrency without any third-party intervention. Bitcoin was not the first cryptocurrency to be proposed but was the first one to solve the double spending issue efficiently. Since the apparition of Bitcoin, people and companies start getting interested in cryptocurrency and its underlying technology Blockchain in particular.

Blockchain has changed the way people can interact and transact assets. The technology allows untrusted peer-to-peer transactions through a decentralized ecosystem [2]. It offers the possibility to parties to achieve transactions without any third party. To support this trustworthy interaction, Blockchain refers to interesting features including decentralization protocol, security, transparency, pseudo-anonymity, immutability, and accountability. Through these features, transactions are recorded in blocks and publicly published. Every block, except the first block, is linked to its previous block using cryptography. The transaction records form a chain of blocks that are maintained and remain unaltered through a decentralized peer-to-peer network of untrusted computers (nodes) which dictates the next appending block by following predefined consensus protocols.

Since the advent of the Blockchain with the implementation of the Bitcoin, several Blockchain implementations have emerged, all following the same purpose which is decentralized control over assets. Unlike Bitcoin, most of the emerged Blockchain, beyond providing a decentralized finance system provides a decentralized computer as a whole. This idea was proposed and implemented by Buterin later after the bitcoin release. Buterin [3] proposed Ethereum-the first second generation of Blockchain that allows execution of smart contracts on the top blockchain network. Smart contracts are software programs embedding business logic to enforce the agreement between parties without the need for a third party [4]. They are executed and deployed in the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) which is a stack-based virtual machine that supports a large set of instructions and enables the execution of Turing-complete programs. Smart contracts have revolutionized digital asset transactions as it promotes the execution of any type of digital asset-based agreement while benefiting from the blockchain advantages. For example, research [5]–[7] shows that the smart contract can help to solve the traceability issue in the supply chain sector. Many other sectors such as health, IOT[8], [9] have been implementing the Blockchain smart contract to handle agreements and transactions. Ethereum to date has run over 8 million smart contracts handling significant financial assets estimated to be around US\$ 912,767,235 in the first quartile of 2022[10].

Ethereum smart contracts are usually developed with high-level programming languages. Solidity is the most popular programming language for smart contract development in Ethereum. Yet, Solidity as a language is not so different to the well know programming languages (i.e.-JAVA, C++) as it provides some similar features such as object-oriented constructs which developers are already familiar with. However, while Solidity's similarity with other languages may help developers to easily develop the Ethereum smart contract, the Solidity smart contracts are running in Blockchain which environment is different to that of the traditional software. Therefore, may lead developers to inadvertently introduce mistakes into smart contracts. Furthermore, in contrast to the traditional software, a deployed smart contract source code remains immutable in the Blockchain. Therefore, any smart contract program mistakes, once deployed become irreversible which may result in crucial consequences.

This concern happened with the DAO-the first Decentralized Autonomous Organization leading to the loss of USD 60 million[11]. DAO was proposed by the Ethereum community to function in a similar way to a venture capital fund. The idea was to allow anyone to pitch their project to the community and potentially obtain funding directly from The DAO's smart contract. Anyone owning DAO tokens could then vote on projects and obtain rewards if the projects turned profitable. The DAO had a creation period during which 12.7M ether(ETH) (worth around 150M USD at the time) have been gathered. However, later on, in the creation period of the DAO smart contract, the attacker used one vulnerability from the DAO system called reentrancy vulnerability to drain the DAO contract account during transaction executions. A re-entrancy occurs when external contracts are allowed to call back the calling contract before the initial execution is completed. Ironically, before the DAO attack, the developers of the DAO have been notified about the potential existence of such a recursive call bug within their smart contract, but the developers simply reassured the community that their smart contract would not be vulnerable. **As shown in this attack case, it is clear that Ethereum smart contract developers are misunderstanding smart contract development as they are likely not aware of vulnerabilities they may be added to the smart contracts.** And this can be observed through several other attacks [12] that have been implemented through other discovered vulnerabilities after that the DAO attacks. Among these attacks, the POLY NETWORK HACK[13], a recent attack that happened in August 2021, is considered the biggest crypto heist, leading to the loss of USD 600 million.

1.1 Research question

The aforementioned raises concern about smart contract security development. Although businesses benefit from Blockchain features using the smart contract, the problem is this does not guarantee businesses to be secure because, unlike the Blockchain which is secure by design, the smart contracts are not free from vulnerabilities [11]. The vulnerability of the Blockchain smart contracts as shown above was famously evidenced through the DAO attack and several other attacks and recently by POLY NETWORK hack. Such a situation related to the security issue of the smart contract can be catastrophic for businesses if a cyber-criminal organization could launch attacks through the smart contract vulnerabilities to steal millions of dollars and other valuable data from Blockchain platforms. This is a critical situation that needs attention and solutions.

Research suggests that identifying smart contract vulnerabilities is a possible solution to this problem[14], [15]. The main direction of research to tackle the security aspect has focused on vulnerability analysis tools. Although vulnerability analysis tools could help to support smart contract security by detecting vulnerabilities, they are not effective enough for smart contract development. The vulnerability analysis tools present false positives and false negatives that impact the tools' results and therefore can leak some vulnerabilities in deployed smart contracts. Given the Blockchain immutability, this is not an effective solution for businesses. If a vulnerability is not detected earlier, after the deployment it may be hard to remove it.

Therefore, the core research questions this thesis aims to address are:

- There is growing evidence [16][17] of alternative security solutions, in particular security programming practices and patterns for supporting the software security development life cycle by preventing developers to introduce vulnerabilities into the software. However, little interest has been given to these alternative solutions in the smart contract context. As security programming practices and patterns support non-Blockchain software security development, **can these solutions from non-blockchain software apply to the smart contract, and how does it cost to implement them? (RQ1).**

- Although security programming practices and patterns can support software security development, there is a need to measure how secure a smart contract is (*security level*). Thus, in an environment like Blockchain in which contracts are immutable, knowing the *security level* of the smart contract is a must. There is growing evidence[17], [18] showing Security metrics support software security development by measuring the security level of software. In the smart contract context, little interest has been given to this solution. As Security metrics help to measure the software security level, **can security metrics from non-Blockchain software apply to smart contracts? (RQ2)**.
- Despite the security solution applied to the software, it is not free of bugs. Therefore, maintenance should be carried out in order to improve software security. The Ethereum community to tackle the smart contract immutability is proposing upgradability solutions to upgrade the smart contract. To the best of our knowledge, there are currently four solutions including EIP-897[19], EIP-1822[20], EIP-1967[21], and EIP-2535[22] that are used as standards to upgrade the Ethereum smart contracts. These solutions obviously may help to maintain the security of smart contracts as they allow the smart contracts to be modified. However, as updating non-Blockchain software evolves according to Lehman[23], considering this new computing environment (Blockchain) may impact differently the smart contract maintenance and furthermore the smart contract evolution compared to the non-Blockchain software, and given no interest has been given to this aspect, **what is the impact of the implementation of these upgradability standards on the smart contract evolution? (RQ3)**.

1.2 Research methods

This research aims to answer the research questions and, contribute to closing the research gap through the case study method [24]. A case study is a multi-dimensional activity used for seeing something in its completeness and looking at it from many angles. Using this method allowed us to study this concerning phenomenon (applicability and impact) in its completeness to avoid missing variables or biased introductions that may affect the investigation insight.

The data collection was supported through the document analysis method, Static and Dynamic Analysis of a smart contract source code and some code metrics such as code size, complexity, and security vulnerabilities evaluation.

For effective data analysis, we support our analysis using statical methods. Each research investigation result involving quantitative values is evaluated through suitable and effective statical methods.

Figure 1 provides an overview of our research process for achieving our research goal.

Figure 1 Overview of thesis research process

1.3 Thesis contribution

We carried out an empirical evidence-based *investigation of the applicability and cost characterization of the non-blockchain security programming practices and patterns in smart contracts*. Through a case study involving smart contracts, we investigate the applicability of a list of security programming practices and their cost. By using systematic judgment and statistical methods, the result of our study shows that security programming practices from non-blockchain can be applied to the smart contract, and their cost is not significant enough to deter practitioners from implementing them. This investigation result has been published in N'Da et al. [25]

We carried out an empirical evidence-based *investigation of the applicability of security metrics from non-Blockchain to smart contracts*. By using a case study involving a list of smart contracts we evaluate three measurement properties (construct, measurement, and reliability) for the applicability of the security metrics identified from a literature review. The result of this research shows that most of the security metrics from non-blockchain software can also be implemented in smart contracts and can help to measure smart contract security. A part of this investigation result has been published in N'Da et al.[26]

We provided *the characterization of the implementation of the Ethereum upgradability standards into the smart contract concerning the implementation cost, and software evolution*. Through statistical methods and a case study involving a list of 18 smart contract projects, we evaluate the cost, size, complexity, and quality of the smart contracts over a period. The research results show that, among the upgradability methods, the EIP-2535 is currently the one implying less cost for smart contract maintenance and that the smart contract evolutionary behaviour with regard to size, complexity, and quality follows Lehman's laws.

We proposed a comprehensive Secure cost-effective smart contract development life cycle framework (SCESMDF) for supporting practitioners in building and maintenance of secure and cost-effective smart contracts. This framework represents a conceptual model using security programming practices and patterns (Chapter 5), security metrics (Chapter 6), and Ethereum upgradability standards Chapter 7 . These components of the framework are used to support, the security-cost trade-off, the maintenance, and to measure the security level of the smart contract. An example of the implementation of this framework has been provided in this thesis.

1.4 Thesis structure

Chapter 1 This chapter includes the thesis motivation, the research questions that are answered to this thesis, and the research contribution.

Chapter 2 Provide a background on the Blockchain technology and some mathematical concepts used in the smart contract development field.

Chapter 3 covers the Background of the Ethereum smart contract, security programming practices and patterns, and security metrics. It also reviews the research works related to the smart contract security issue.

Chapter 4 covers the background on the research philosophy, research methods, and justification of the research method selections for this thesis.

Chapter 5 reports the investigation on the applicability of the security programming practices and patterns to a smart contract. It discusses the research process and results of the investigation.

Chapter 6 reports the investigation of the applicability of the security metrics to a smart contract. It discusses the research process and results of the investigation

Chapter 7 discusses the impact of the Ethereum upgradability standards on smart contracts. This discussion is related to the cost of the standard implementation, and the software evolution of Lehman's laws.

Chapter 8 includes our proposed framework built to support the smart contract development life cycle. This chapter provides a description of the foundations representing the underlying basis of the framework, a description of the framework conceptual model, and detail of the framework implementation process.

Chapter 9 concludes the overall research carried out in this thesis and summarises the contributions made to the body of knowledge. Some of the potential future research directions are also extended in this thesis.

Chapter 2. Background

This chapter provides the background that is necessary for understanding the technology and concepts used in this thesis. We briefly highlight information on Blockchain, and the running mechanism of the Blockchain to allow the reader to understand the execution process of the Ethereum smart contract program in a Blockchain environment. We also provide a brief understanding of some mathematical concepts used in the smart contract domain.

2.1 Blockchain technology

There is an explosion of interest in Blockchain technology. To date, this technology is implemented in many sectors. Blockchain is a tamper-evident, and tamper-resistant digital ledger implemented in a distributed network and usually without a central authority[2]. This technology provides a decentralized peer-to-peer ecosystem in which transactions are managed and recorded without the intervention of any third party. It can also be assimilated into a database, however, unlike the traditional database; Blockchain provides interesting features that fundamentally ensure for leveraging of trustless activities. These main features are described below:

Immutability: Unlike the traditional database, blockchain technology uses an append-only ledger to provide a full transaction history that cannot be overridden.

Decentralization: The Blockchain transactions of users are governed by the decentralized network of computers following what is known as a **Blockchain consensus** for preventing anyone(authority) to get the advantages of the transaction operation.

Security: The security of the Blockchain is enhanced by cryptography, which added to the decentralized nature of the Blockchain provides a security layer. The cryptography implementation in the Blockchain prevents the data within that ledger to be altered.

Transparency: Unlike the traditional database, the data within the Blockchain ledger (transaction information) are public and available for all participants to audit.

Pseudo-anonymously: The Blockchain also allows a user to participate in a Blockchain network while keeping the user's identity unknown.

Unlike traditional transaction activities, these Blockchain capabilities allow each one to proceed safely, directly to any transaction(activity) commitment without the need to know each other and without a central authority, which enables a transaction to proceed faster.

The first Blockchain implementation was limited to the financial transaction with Bitcoin [1]. Since then the Blockchain transaction has been democratized through computing protocols known as smart contracts. Smart contracts are logic encoded on the top of the Blockchain to implement programmable transactions. Ethereum is the first Blockchain-based platform proposing this feature on top of the Blockchain[27]. Since the advent of smart contracts, many Blockchain platforms proposing different features with different approaches to Blockchain performance, scalability, and security have been implemented. Businesses and practitioners can therefore work with any specific Blockchain platform and features based on their system requirements (i.e.

Smart contract programming language, system cost, system performance). These Blockchain platforms are generally grouped into permissionless and permissioned blockchains which both present advantages and disadvantages[28]. In the following section, we introduce the Blockchain's main components.

2.1.1 Blockchain components

In this section, we introduce the Blockchain components responsible for the Blockchain running. These components include cryptography, ledger, consensus protocol, Blockchain transaction, and smart contracts as presented in the following sections.

Blockchain cryptography

Cryptography is about developing techniques and protocols that prevent third parties from accessing information from private messages during communication [29], [30]. Cryptography is used to secure data in transit or stored. Cryptography is generally classified into the following three types of cryptographic schemes: symmetric cryptography, asymmetric cryptography, and hash function. Blockchain implementations mainly make use of asymmetric cryptography and hash functions. These cryptography algorithms are used in Blockchain for multiple purposes such as wallet, transaction, security, and privacy-preserving protocols[31].

Asymmetric cryptography is a form of cryptography that uses a key pair to encrypt and decrypt data [26]. It is usually used in an environment where information is shared between different communication parties. A key in cryptography represents almost anything, ranging from a number to a word to a random string of characters, which when processed into cryptographic algorithms can encrypt or decrypt cryptographic data. With asymmetric cryptography,

- Each user has two keys: a public key and a private key.
- Both keys are mathematically related
- The public key is made available to anyone. The private key is kept secret.
- Both keys are required to perform an action. For example, over-communication data encrypted with the public key should be unencrypted with the private key.
- Digital signatures can be implemented. A Digital signature is a cryptographic primitive that provides integrity[32]. With asymmetric cryptography, a digital signature is created through the encryption of data with the private key. This ensures the data come from the right person. As qualities, digital signatures are non-repudiable, incorruptible and easily verifiable. For example, as shown in Figure 2, if Bob wants to send a message to Alice, but Alice wants to ensure Bob has sent the message. Assuming that Bob has a key pair, Bob uses his private key to sign the message, Alice then can verify the message integrity (and right sender) using only Bob's public key generated by the private key. This also ensures that the message has not been altered by anyone else.

Figure 2 Private and public key usage example (Reproduced with permission from the copyright owner)

Figure 3 Ethereum address creation (Reproduced with permission from the copyright owner)

In Blockchain, Asymmetric cryptography and digital signature are used in several places to ensure the integrity of transaction data. In platforms such as Ethereum, Asymmetric cryptography is used to create the public-private key pair. The public key is derived from the private key (64 hexadecimal characters as shown in Figure 3) using the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) which is a digital signature algorithm specifically made for signing and verifying data and recovering public keys from a signature. Together, the private-public key pair represents an Ethereum account by providing, respectively, a publicly accessible account handle (account address) and private control over access to any ether in the account and over any authentication the account needs when using smart contracts. The private key controls access by being the unique piece of information needed to create digital signatures, which are required to sign transactions to spend any funds in the Ethereum account, while the public key is used to access the transaction by verifying the signed transaction. Therefore, unlike the public key which can publicly be shared over the Ethereum network, the private key should not be public at the risk to allow anyone to access the account of the owner of the private key[33].

The hash functions are algorithms that enables taking an arbitrary input (plaintext) of any size and converted into a unique fixed length bit string output called hash value or message digest. In Blockchain, the hash functions form an integral part of transactions. They have a major role in linking Blockchain blocks and maintaining the integrity of data in each Block. Indeed, the hash functions are used for the creation of digests of the Blocks in the ledger, which blocks are tightly dependent on each other by having the digest of their previous Block. Thus, any alteration in the block data can lead to inconsistency, making it INVALID unless the previous blocks are also altered during the current block validation by the Blockchain network[34]. Besides securing the Blockchain ledger, the cryptographic hash functions are used to derive the Blockchain addresses, creating unique identifiers used in the Blockchain[35]. In Ethereum, the addresses are derived from the public key or contract using the Keccak-256 one-way hash function. As shown in Figure 3, for a given public key derived from a private key using ECDSA, an Ethereum address will correspond to the last 20 bytes of a hash of the public key calculated using the Keccak-256 hash function.

Blockchain transactions

Transactions in the Blockchain are cryptographic data packages sent over the Blockchain network for verification before being recorded in the ledger. While limited to the transfer of financial assets in Bitcoin, the transactions may include any event occurring on data other than financial assets in other Blockchain platforms [3]. In Blockchain, the transactions are triggered by an external owner (corresponding to a human i.e buyer), then processed by the Blockchain network for verification and validation, and finally recorded to the Blockchain ledger as shown in Figure 4.

In most of the Blockchain platforms, the user initializes a transaction by passing its identifier (i.e., address), its public key, a digital signature derives from its private key, the transaction input -which represents the digital asset to be transferred, transaction output -which represents the accounts of the recipient along with digital asset he is supposed to receive.

To process the transaction by the network, the user must pay fees corresponding to the transaction cost which mechanism varies from Blockchain implementations. This transaction cost represents the cost of computing the transaction. The transaction cost varies and may reach a high-cost value depending on many factors such as Blockchain network congestion, the transaction confirmation execution (affected by the liquidity providers), and transaction size[36].

Combining into a Block, transactions are verified by the network to ensure their authenticity and validity. The validity of a transaction ensures that the transaction meets the protocol requirements and any formalized data formats or smart contract requirements specific to the blockchain implementation. The authenticity of a transaction determines that the transaction sender had access to the transaction data. This verification process in the Blockchain is performed by following a specific computing protocol known as Blockchain consensus which varies for different Blockchain implementations.

Figure 4 Blockchain transaction process

Blockchain consensus algorithms

The Blockchain consensus algorithm is one of the core elements of the Blockchain. It is a built-in protocol in the Blockchain defining the way transactions are validated [3]. This protocol is responsible for the decentralized nature of the Blockchain as it is based on a process in which the transaction validation is the result of the agreement of nodes (computers responsible for the transaction validation and record) on the network. There exist various consensus algorithms varying from computation power, performance, scalability, and tolerating disruptive behaviours. However, in general, the consensus models require that transactions be combined every certain amount of time into a block with a proof serving as a key to the miner (the computer which intends to accept and execute a transaction) to get the block accepted by the Blockchain network (to update the ledger by adding the block as a new Block to the ledger).

When joining the Blockchain network, the nodes are agreeing to the initial state of the system which is recorded in the origin block (known as the genesis block) from which new blocks will be chronologically attached. Regardless, of the consensus model, each block should be valid and thus can be independently validated by some Blockchain nodes. By combining the initial state and the ability to verify each block, the nodes can independently agree on the current state of the Blockchain. In case there were ever multiple valid chains presented to a node, following a default mechanism (i.e. GHOST protocol [37]) in the Blockchain, the longer chain viewed as valid will be adopted by the nodes.

From their recent survey study, Nguyen and Kim [38] have classified the Blockchain consensus protocols into two categories including proof-based and voting-based. The proof-based method involves that among many nodes freely joining the network, the node providing sufficient proof gains the right to add a new block to the Blockchain ledger followed by a cryptocurrency rewarded by the Blockchain system. Unlike the proof-based method, the selection of the Block publisher is voted by nodes. That is multiple nodes vote for every Block that should be attached to the ledger. This type of consensus also defines a threshold of votes representing the

minimum number of votes requiring validating a block. Table 1 shows the list of current Blockchain consensus showing their advantage and disadvantages.

Blockchain Ledger

The Ledger in Blockchain technology is a record system for the validated transaction. Every node in a blockchain network owns a copy of the Ledger [3]. That is every participant joining the Blockchain network reaches out to get a copy of the ledger and participates in ledger maintenance, making loss or destruction of the ledger difficult. By design, the ledger structure consists of a set of Blocks cryptographically and historically linked as shown the Figure 5([39], Figure 2). The Blocks are linked together through each block containing the block identifier (the Block hash) of the previous block, allowing thus the ledger to be harder to alter as all the previous blocks of a given altered block should be altered, which is practically impossible considering the Blockchain consensus as explained in the above section.

A ledger's block captures(records) the Blockchain system state at a given time which is translated by recorded transactions performed in the Blockchain system at a given time (depending on the Blockchain implementation the block creation time varies). The entire transaction data are not stored in the block, instead, their hash values using cryptographic hash functions are recorded, making the blocks use less memory size in the nodes(computers) when adding to the ledger.

By design, for most of the Blockchain implementations, a **Block** as shown the Figure 5([39], Figure 2) consists of the Block data and Block header. The Block data consists of a number of validated transactions represented by their hash values as mentioned above. The Block data itself is also represented by a hash value which can be obtained from different methods (using Merkle tree¹ or using a hash of all the combined block data) depending on the Blockchain implementation. The Block header includes the block identifier (represented by a hash value), the identifier of the previous block, the block timestamp, and the size of the Block. For most Blockchain implementations, the Block hash value results from the Block data hash and previous block hash, and a cryptographic hash function. In the Blockchain implementation using PoW consensus, a nonce value is included for generating the Block hash by solving a hard mathematical puzzle[34].ss

¹ A data structure where the data is hashed and combined until there is a singular root hash that represents the entire structure

Table 1 List of consensus algorithms used in Blockchain networks

Consensus Name	Description	Advantage	Disadvantage
PoW	a node publishes the next block by being the first to solve a computationally intensive puzzle. The solution to this puzzle is the “proof” they have performed work.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to perform denial of service by flooding the network with bad blocks. • Open to anyone with hardware to solve the puzzle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computationally intensive (by design), power consumption, hardware arms race. • Potential for 51 % attack by obtaining enough computational power.
PoS	Here, the amount of stake held by a node is used as a determining factor for publishing new blocks. The stake. Stake corresponds often to an amount of cryptocurrency that the blockchain network user has invested into the system. the more stake the nodes have invested into the system, the more likely they will want the system to succeed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlike PoW, here less computationally intensive is used. • Open to anyone who wishes to stake cryptocurrencies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System control is held by the stakeholder. • Possibility to create a pool of stakeholders for centralized power. • Potential for 51 % attacks by obtaining enough stakes.
Delegate PoS	Here, nodes(known as delegates) responsible for the block validation are voted on and elected. The votes are performed by pooling tokens into a staking pool and linking those to a particular delegate.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elected delegates are economically incentivized to remain honest. • Less computationally intensive than PoW 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less node diversity than PoW or pure PoS consensus implementations. • High-security risks for node compromise due to a constrained set of operating nodes. • Since all delegates are "known", block producers can be tricked into colluding and accepting bribes, thereby compromising the security of the system.
Round Robin	Here, the block validation is based on the turn of the node. may include a time limit to enable available nodes to publish blocks so that unavailable nodes will not cause a halt in block publication.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low computational power. • Straightforward to understand 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires a large amount of trust amongst publishing nodes.
Proof of identity/authority	Here, publishing nodes must have their identities proven and verifiable within the blockchain network. Blockchain network users directly affect a publishing node’s reputation based on the publishing node’s behaviour.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fast confirmation time • Allows for dynamic block production rates • Can be used in sidechains to blockchain networks which utilize another consensus mode 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relies on the assumption that the current validating node has not been compromised • Leads to centralized points of failure. • The reputation of a given node is subject to the potential for high tail-risk as it could be compromised at any time
Proof of Elapsed Time (PoET)	Here, each publishing node requests a wait time from a secure hardware time source within their computer system for creating and publishing a new Block.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less computationally expensive than PoW 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hardware requirement to obtain time. • Assumes the hardware clock used to derive time is not compromised • Given speed-of-late latency limits, true time synchronicity is essentially impossible in distributed systems

Figure 5 Blockchain ledger (taken from [39])

2.1.2 Smart contracts

Smart contracts are software programs running on top of the Blockchain. Smart contracts automate the enforcement of contract terms while minimizing the need for trusted intermediaries[4]. The smart contract is one of the powerful features of Blockchain technology. It provides the ability to the Blockchain to satisfy common contractual conditions (such as terms, confidentiality, liens, and even enforcement) in multiple domains such as supply chain[7], [40], [41], IoT[9], [42]. It provides the ability to the Blockchain to satisfy common contractual conditions (such as terms, confidentiality, liens, and even enforcement) in multiple domains such as supply chain[7], [40], [41], IoT[9], [42].

Various Turing-complete programming languages are used for smart contract development. General programming languages such as C++, JAVA, and NodeJS are used by Blockchain implementations such as *NeO*, *Tendermint*, and *Hyperledger fabric*. On the other hand, programming languages that specifically include blockchain constructs have been developed. Among them, *Solidity*-the most used programming language for smart contracts, *Vyper*, and *Sway* are used by Blockchain platforms such as *Ethereum*, and *Libra* as shown the Table 2. The list of programming languages given in the Table 2 is not exhaustive.

Table 2 List of programming languages used for smart contract (✓ is equivalent to 'belong to'- table adapted from [43])

Programming languages	Blockchain implementation		
	General	Contract-design	
JAVA	✓		NeO, Tendermint, Hyperledger fabric
C++	✓		Eos, Tendermint, Hyperledger fabric
Python	✓		Tendermint,
Go	✓		Tendermint
Node.js	✓		Hyperledger fabric
JAVAScript	✓		Hyperledger fabric
Solidity, Vyper, Flint, Baboo, Sway		✓	Ethereum
Move		✓	Libra
Fi		✓	Tezos
DAML		✓	Digital asset
Sophia		✓	Æternity
Fift		✓	TON

Figure 6 Ethereum EVM and account types (taken from [44] - Reproduced with permission from the copyright owner)

The execution of smart contracts is triggered through transactions issued by users. Smart contract transaction consists of smart contract deployment, and smart contract method call [3]. The contract method call may include one or multiple transactions depending on the number of methods defined under the smart contract. For most Blockchain implementations such as Ethereum, smart contract transaction execution is supported by a cost, used generally in the permissionless Blockchain to reward the block node publisher and to prevent any malicious users from deploying and then accessing smart contracts that will perform a denial of service by using all the resources.

The scope of this thesis is on improving the quality of Ethereum smart contract development, as a result in the following sections we provide details about the smart contract execution mechanism in the Ethereum Blockchain

Ethereum Smart contract deployment and execution

As mentioned above, a smart contract is a program running at the top of the Blockchain. They represent the application layer of the Blockchain. In order to run a smart contract on the Ethereum Blockchain, the user (any practitioner: developer, or business) should initially deploy the smart contract. The Ethereum contract deployment consists of sending a transaction containing the smart contract code (a low level of code after compilation) as transaction data without specifying any recipient. Once the transaction is validated by nodes, a unique account is created for the deployed contract [3]. To date, there are two categories of accounts in Ethereum including an Externally Ownership Account (EAO) and a Smart contract account. Both accounts contain a unique address as an identifier and account balance as shown the Figure 6([44], Figure 5). However, unlike EAO, the smart contract account contains the smart contract code represented by the hash of the code stored in the Blockchain ledger as shown Figure 6 ([44], Figure 5). the smart contract code stored in the Blockchain, remains immutable just like any other recorded transaction data.

Figure 7 EVM Machine structure (taken from [44] Reproduced with permission from the copyright owner)

Therefore, any intent of altering the smart contract source code is not possible. While contract code is stored in the ledger, the contract states are stored (in the order that variables were declared) in memory slots of a virtual machine named EVM (EVM-a distributed Turing completeness machine in Ethereum nodes) as shown in Figure 7([44], Figure 5). While contract code is stored in the ledger, the contract states are stored (in the order that variables were declared) in memory slots of a virtual machine named EVM (EVM-a distributed Turing completeness machine in Ethereum nodes) as shown in Figure 7([44], Figure 5). EVM is a state machine responsible for keeping the Ethereum Blockchain state while executing the Ethereum transactions on top of Blockchain. Therefore, unlike the smart contract source code, smart contract states can be updated through smart contract executions.

A smart contract execution (method call) consists of sending a transaction from the smart contract function to be executed. By design, the smart contract structure consists of the set of functions and state variables used to enforce condition terms. Then, a deployed contract on the Blockchain network is executed through transactions requesting the execution of one or multiple functions (as defined in a smart contract) either by an external owner or another smart contract. The data required for the transaction include the address of the smart contract from which the function should be executed, and the function payload (the function selector and arguments represent by hash value[45]) that should be executed. The data required for the transaction include the address of the smart contract from which the function should be executed, and the function payload (the function selector and arguments represent by hash value[45]) that should be executed. Once compiling, the smart contract code is transformed into EVM bytecode-a low-level, stacked-based bytecode used by EVM for the smart contract execution. This bytecode consists of a series of bytes² where each byte represents an operation. Then, a formal transaction involving smart contract execution consists of the execution of a set of bytecode operations in the EVM. The EVM bytecode operations have access to both Blockchain data (Block header data, sender, and data of incoming message) and EVM storage. As shown in Figure 7([44], Figure 5) the EVM storages consist of:

*Two non-persistent storages **Stack, Memory**: from which data can be read and written, but it is reset after each invocation.*

² List of all bytecodes of EVM

```

pragma solidity >=0.7.0 <0.9.0;

contract SimpleStorage {
    uint storedData;

    function set(uint x) public {
        storedData=x;
    }

    function get() public view returns (uint) {
        return storedData;
    }
}

```

Figure 8 Example of Solidity contract(taken from Figure 8[46])

One persistent storage Storage: from which data (precisely contract state) can be read written and persists for the long term for keeping Blockchain state.

Ethereum smart contract transaction cost

The transactions in Ethereum have a cost. This cost is applied for simple transactions (ether transfer) as well as for transactions that involve smart contracts. The Ethereum transaction cost depends on the resources used by the EVM of Ethereum nodes for computing the transaction. These resources in Ethereum are expressed in GAS (a defined unit) [47]. The transaction cost ($TxCost$) in Ethereum is straightforwardly determined by the equation below.

The **Gas Cost** represents the spent amount of resources for the transaction execution. For the smart contract, the GAS Cost can be grouped into the GAS Cost for the contract deployment, and the GAS Cost for the smart contract execution (one or multiple function execution). In Ethereum, the GAS cost for contract creation is significantly higher than the gas cost of resources used for contract execution³. The resources for the smart contract execution correspond to the gas cost of the operation codes (EVM bytecodes) used for executing a smart contract function.

The **GAS Price** represents the price for which he will be able to pay a unit of resource (GAS). Therefore, in general, the transaction cost of the smart contract deployment may be higher than that of the smart contract execution[48]. In order to perform a transaction by the network, a user should also provide a **GAS limit** representing the limit of resources used by the nodes to compute the transaction. When this limit is not totally spent after the transaction execution, the remaining is sent back to the user.

$$TxCost = GasLimit * GasPrice \quad (Equation 2.1)$$

³ Gas Costs from Yellow Paper -- EIP-150 Revision (1e18248 - 2017-04-12) - Google Sheets

Ethereum smart contract programming language -Solidity

Solidity is a Turing-programming language provided by Ethereum to support smart contract development[45]. Although there are several programming languages including mainly Vyper[49]and Yul[50] supporting smart contract development, Solidity is currently the most used programming language for Ethereum smart contracts. Based on the Object-oriented programming paradigm, the code of smart contracts written in Solidity is structured into contracts as shown the Figure 8[46]. It supports some Object-oriented features such as inheritance, coupling, and aggregation. Designed for the EVM Machine, Solidity also offers features allowing performing most of the Ethereum Blockchain operations (ether transfer, Blockchain data management, EVM read and write storage).

Through these features, Solidity offers concepts common to that of the modern programming languages allowing thus developers familiar with the modern programming language to get easily adapt to Solidity [49][50]

2.2 Mathematical concepts

Confusion matrix-A confusion matrix is a mathematical tool used in statical classification problems and machine learning to measure the performance of an algorithm or model (in ML). The confusion matrix can be applied in binary classification as well as multi-class classification problems. It is also widely used in the security analysis tool for evaluating the performance of static tools. As shown in the Figure below, the confusion matrix consists of the following elements which can also be used individually to evaluate the performance of a model:

True Positive(TP) value: a result that correctly indicates the presence of a condition

True Negative(TN) value: a result that correctly indicates the absence of a condition

False Positive(FP) value: a result that wrongly indicates the absence of a condition that exists

False Negative(FN) value: a result which wrongly indicates that a particular condition does not exist.

In the context of the security analysis method, the false positive and negative are widely used to evaluate the analysis; tool performance. For example, a static vulnerability analysis tool presenting a higher rate of false positive value, may not be advised to be used as this means the tool mostly wrongly indicates that vulnerabilities in a program code do not exist. Furthermore, metrics including accuracy(ACC), precision(P) and sensitivity(Sn) derived from the performance measures (True Positive, True Negative, False Positive, False Negative) aforementioned can be used to evaluate the program (or model) performance. These metrics are most frequently used in the machine learning field and can obtain through the following equation:

$$ACC = (TP + TN) \div (TP + TN + FP + FN)$$

$$P = TP \div (TP + FP)$$

$$S_n = TP \div (TP + FN)$$

2.3 Chapter summary

In this chapter, we presented the Blockchain background and the Blockchain features. We also provided information on basic mathematical concepts used in Blockchain and smart contracts. In summary, Blockchain is a new technology that intent to revolutionise the interaction between the party. The Blockchain provides features including a peer-to-peer decentralised network, security, transparency and immutability allowing making exchanges without any intermediaries all maintains by cryptographic-based consensus protocol. On top of the Blockchain, protocols such as smart contracts-Turing completed programs can be developed and deployed by anyone to extend the blockchain application which was prior limited to financial transactions with Bitcoin. Ethereum has been the first platform to implement smart contracts on top of the Blockchain and since hosting the smart contract of several activity fields.

Chapter 3. Literature Review

This chapter reviews the research studies in the area of secure smart contract development. We initially reviewed the smart contract history and Ethereum Blockchain. We then provide the state of the smart contract vulnerabilities and review the related security-based research contributing to smart contract security. We also review the topic of security development approaches from non-blockchain software.

3.1 Smart contract history

3.1.1 From the idea to the implementation attempts

Smart contracts were first introduced by Nick Szaboo[51]. Szabo argues that “contractual clauses can be embedded in the hardware and software to make a breach of contract expensive. According to Nick Szabo’s conception, smart contracts are digital protocols for information transfer that use mathematical algorithms to automate the execution of a transaction once the established conditions are met and fully control the process.” A vendor machine could be used to illustrate this in Szabo’s idea as it is a machine (consisting of hardware and software) that receives cash and dispenses assets and changes according to the listed price. However, although this machine is automated it does not meet that full control process as the vendor machine administrator has privileged access to the money and asset in the machine. The idea of smart contract conception raised in 1996 could not be implemented at that time as the necessary technologies (mainly based on full control process protocols) did not exist.

This smart contract idea remained dormant until the Bitcoin appearance in 2008. Bitcoin enabled trustless digital contracts. Indeed, a user can only spend cryptocurrencies by providing the required arguments to their respective output scripts. Moreover, not only do Bitcoin scripts execute as programmed, but every user can verify this. Therefore, the users do not need to trust the administrators of the contract used. This key property of Bitcoin has led to the first attempts at encoding complex contracts such as Counterparty [52], and Mastercoin

However, the restricted capabilities of the programming aspect of Bitcoin do not promote the development of several types of contracts. The Bitcoin script is not Turing-complete, and the Bitcoin contracts cannot interact with other contracts as Bitcoin transactions are executed in isolation.

3.1.2 Smart contract in Ethereum

Buterin and his team [3] have developed Ethereum- a Blockchain platform that aims to address Bitcoin’s limitation regarding programmability. Ethereum differs from Bitcoin in three major ways. Firstly, Ethereum offers a richer programming environment for developing and running any contract type. Smart contracts in Ethereum are written in Turing-complete programming languages and executed by a large capability virtual machine (EVM). The Ethereum smart contract source code is stored at a unique address representing the smart contract’s unique identifier. Ethereum contracts can therefore be executed by the user and even by other contracts by referring to the contract address. Secondly, Ethereum smart contracts can also benefit from updatable and addressable storage for keeping and updating their state. They have also the possibility to permanently store arbitrary data in the Blockchain ledger. Thirdly, Ethereum implements an account-based model, as opposed to Bitcoin’s UTXO (Unspent Transaction Output)-based model. In UTXO, a user’s wallet keeps track of a list of unspent transactions associated with all addresses owned by the user, and the balance of the wallet is calculated as the sum of those unspent transactions. While the Account base model keeps track of the

balance of each account as a global state. The balance of an account is checked to make sure it is greater than or equal to the spending transaction amount. Therefore, modelling an account simplifies smart contract logic, unlike UTXO which involves checking the whole history.

3.2 Ethereum architecture

3.2.1 Accounts

Ethereum nodes communicate through a peer-to-peer network and maintain a shared view of the global state, which consists of accounts with their respective states. Each account has its own address. In the address space, there are two types of accounts: one is External owned account (EOA) controlled by a public/private key. This account is held by people to save ETH; the other one is a contract account controlled by code. Both types of accounts can send and receive ethers, however, EOA can initiate transactions. Each account consists of a unique address, balance and a nonce. The balance corresponds to the amount of the native cryptocurrency ether controlled by this account. The nonce is a counter that keeps track of the number of transactions issued from the account, preventing replay attacks. In addition to balance and nonce, contract accounts have code and storage. Contract code is a piece of bytecode used by the Ethereum virtual machine (EVM) for contract execution. This code controls the changes to the balance and storage of the account.

3.2.2 Transactions

A transaction is a data package sent from one account to another account. We could transfer ETH between accounts by sending transactions to an EOA. If the target account is a contract account, sending a transaction will trigger its code execution. A transaction includes the following fields:

- nonce – the number of transactions sent by the sender;
- gasPrice – the number of Wei per gas unit that the sender is paying;
- gasLimit – the maximum amount of gas to be spent during execution;
- to – the destination address
- value – the number of wei transferred along with the transaction;
- v, r, s – digital signature data.

An Ethereum transaction is classified into two categories including message call transaction, and contract creation transaction. A message call transaction is a transaction executing a function of a deployed contract or transfers ether. It contains the arguments for the function call in an optional data field. A contract creation transaction is a transaction executing the deployment of a new contract. This transaction contains the EVM bytecode of the new contract, and the initialization code executed once on contract creation.

The transactions in Ethereum have a cost. This cost is applied to prevent resource abuse. Every computational step in EVM is priced in units of GAS. In order to execute a transaction, the transaction sender specifies the **GAS Price** and the **GAS Limit**. The **GAS Limit** represents the limit of resources used by the nodes to compute the transaction. When this limit is not totally spent after the transaction execution, the remaining is sent back to the transaction sender. The GAS Price represents the price for which a sender will be able to pay a unit of

resource (GAS). Besides, there is also the **GAS cost** which represents the spent amount of resources for the transaction execution. Therefore, the transaction cost (in ether) will apply the equation below:

$$TxCost = GasLimit * GasPrice \quad (Equation 3.1)$$

EVM executes transactions atomically, therefore a failed transaction does not affect the Ethereum state, but consumes all provided gas. The Ethereum specification [27] defines gas costs of EVM opcodes which, developers occasionally change in protocol upgrades. Also, The price of the gas unit varies as this price is determined by the Market.

3.2.3 Mining and coin issuance

Blockchain mining represents distributed consensus mechanism used for validating transactions that are waiting to be added to the Blockchain ledger. This mechanism consists of particular Blockchain nodes known as miners to proceed to the execution of a consensus-based algorithm in order to verify, secure transactions and mint new coins. In Ethereum, like Bitcoin, the Proof of Work (PoW) is used to verify and securely add the transaction to the Blockchain ledger. To do so, Miners pick unconfirmed transactions from the Ethereum network, serialize them, and apply them to the current state. They then solve a mathematical puzzle using the Ethash hash function- proof-of-work mining algorithm. Solving this puzzle consist of Ethash, getting the right hash which serves as proof for the other nodes to verify and validate the transactions. Once the released hash from miners has been approved by the Ethereum network (some nodes), they are rewarded with transaction fees and block subsidies. The Block subsidy corresponds to an amount of ether per Block issued. The current Block subsidy is 2 ether.

In order to increase the number of transactions, Ethereum aims to average out for a series of Blocks one block every 14 seconds compared to 10 in Bitcoin. This allows Ethereum users to perform transactions within a short time compared to Bitcoin. However, at the same time, this short Block interval leads to a high orphan(or Uncle) Block rate. An orphan is a valid block that is not included in the main chain. Indeed, the Ethereum short delays lead to miners unwillingly generating multiple blocks on the same height. In this condition, only one of these Blocks is accepted arbitrary by the network nodes by reaching a validation consensus. Each block will have subsequent blocks created as shown in Figure 9, initiating a race to verify the most blocks. The fork with more verified blocks through POW gets accepted into the blockchain. Any verified blocks within the shorter chain are discarded, whereas the power spent by the miners for getting these discarded blocks is wasted.

To address the issue, Ethereum uses the GHOST protocol [37].GHOST is a chain selection cryptographic protocol that makes use of previously orphaned blocks and adds them to the main blockchain and partially rewards the miner. Therefore, in Ethereum, the miners include hashes of uncles in block headers to receive a higher reward. The GHOST protocol used in Ethereum rewards uncles no more than 6 blocks old. Miners of uncles whose headers get included in the main chain are also rewarded.

contracts logics are linked to Blockchain layers' features (ie, miner, Block timestamp) for the execution, but that linking the contract logic to the Blockchain layers' features may not guarantee running the expected transaction as these transactions may in some way be under the control of miners which might trick the transaction execution unless action is taken. For example, the authors show that a Solidity smart contract depending on BlockTimestamp from the Blockchain ledger may expose the contract to attacks since the miner who creates the new block can choose the timestamp with a certain degree of arbitrariness. This evidence provided by the authors supports our argument mentioned above. That is it seems the syntax similarities of Solidity with the other programming languages mislead the practitioners and lead them unwittingly introduce vulnerabilities because the Ethereum blockchain platform is different to traditional software environments.

Furthermore, beyond the similarity of the Solidity language with traditional programming languages, Atzei et al. [14] identify that Solidity features do not promote the development of secure smart contracts. For example, among the vulnerabilities caused by Solidity, the authors show that Solidity promotes Re-entrancy attacks which are relied on the "fallback function". The Re-entrancy vulnerability changes the normal execution of a smart contract function by recursively calling this function from another contract before the end of the original function execution. This vulnerability has been exploited on many smart contract attacks such as DAO [11], and DEFI [55] leading to the loss of millions of dollars. This result shows that practitioners are not enough experienced with Solidity language to avoid such kinds of vulnerabilities from the language. The full list of the vulnerabilities identified by Atzei et al. is available at [14]. These vulnerabilities were also described and discussed in [56].

On the other hand, the list of security vulnerabilities in the Ethereum smart contract is not exhaustive as new vulnerabilities are still being discovered. He et al.[57] extended the taxonomy provided by Atzei et al. [14] by updating and adding further vulnerabilities such as permission control, Integer overflow/underflow function visibility vulnerabilities. The authors conducted a survey of the Ethereum smart contract's various vulnerabilities, and defences mechanisms applied to tackle these vulnerabilities. The authors classified the Ethereum smart contract vulnerabilities into seven classes (*unchecked send/other Function call, re-entrancy Vulnerabilities, Permission control Vulnerabilities, Function Visibility Vulnerabilities, Timestamp dependency, random number Vulnerabilities, Integer Overflow/Underflow*) for which the authors provided brief descriptions. For example, the authors describe that since the Blockchain is public the permission control may not be effectively controlled as a malicious user may therefore call a higher-privilege function causing critical damage. The authors show that Solidity promotes by default an integer overflow and underflow. Indeed, the Solidity code is compiled in 256-bit EVM, therefore any value (such as uint256) over or under the limited (min and max) size will be resized resulting thus to another value. This vulnerability has been exploited in some attacks such as Beauty Ecosystem Coin (BEC)[56], and Smart Mesh (SMT)[58] causing a loss of millions of dollars.

Furthermore, collaborative projects such as the Decentralized Application Security Project (DASP) and Smart Contract Weakness Classification (SWC) provide a classification of Ethereum smart contract vulnerabilities which includes early identified vulnerabilities and new vulnerabilities such as Denial of Service. The Smart Contract Weakness Classification (SWC) registry was created to identify and map smart contract weaknesses according to the Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) typology [59], and to collect the corresponding test case. This project is currently maintained by the Ethereum community, and people under the supervision of an Ethereum community panel can publish new smart contract weaknesses attached with test cases. To this date, this project identified a list of 37 vulnerabilities including those early identified and new ones such as Incorrect Inheritance Order and Presence of unused variables vulnerabilities.

Recent research [60][61] based on systematic reviews provides a more comprehensive list of the smart contract vulnerabilities including security vulnerabilities and more specific vulnerabilities (privacy and GAS vulnerabilities). Kushuwaha et al.[61] conducted a systematic review on smart contract vulnerabilities from various research works from which they identified and provided a new classification of smart contract vulnerabilities. The authors in order to answer the question related to smart contract vulnerabilities, causes, and tools for detecting them, reviewed a list of 454 research articles from scientific research databases, from which they retained 119 articles related to smart contracts with respect to criteria that they predefined. These criteria include articles in Ethereum Blockchain, smart contracts, vulnerabilities, and smart contract detection tools, which fully text are accessible. As a result, the authors identified a list of 23 vulnerabilities grouped into 3 root causes including Solidity programming language, EVM and Ethereum blockchain design. This result show since the taxonomy earlier provided by Atzei et al.[14], more vulnerabilities have been discovered from these main root causes of smart contract vulnerabilities. Another more comprehensive research on smart contract vulnerabilities conducted by Rameder[60] supports this argument.

Rameder[60] conducted a systematic review aimed at collecting and classifying smart contract vulnerabilities, analysis methods and tools. The authors initially extracted through a primary search based on inclusion criteria (such as work on smart contract security bugs or vulnerabilities, smart contract vulnerabilities detection, verification methods) and exclusion criteria (such as work not written in English, work in which full text is not available), 303 publications. He then conducted a quality appraisal based on intrinsic and contextual data quality metrics to evaluate whether the collected publications are necessary and relevant. The intrinsic data quality metric defined by the authors is used by the author to measure the quality based on the accuracy, objectivity, credibility, and reputation of a publication. And the contextual data metric is used by the author to measure the data quality of a publication with respect to relevancy, value-added, timeliness, completeness and amount of data. As a result, the author was able to extract and then review 149 primary studies, 38 surveys and 8 systematic reviews. From these reviews, the author identified a list of 54 smart contract vulnerabilities which he classified within 10 classes. These 10 vulnerability classes also come from the 3 root causes of vulnerabilities mentioned above, showing thus the significant number of discovered vulnerabilities are from the Solidity programming language, EVM and Ethereum blockchain design since the vulnerabilities were identified during earlier research. Vulnerabilities such as “Callstack limit”, “Uninitialized storage pointer”, and “Erroneous constructor” have been eliminated by Ethereum and Solidity upgraded, however, the other vulnerabilities are still present in Ethereum.

In sum, there is a gap between smart contract development and the practitioner’s smart contract development experience with Solidity. The state-of-art regarding the smart contract vulnerabilities show the security issues in the smart contracts are caused by ineffective Solidity smart contract programming by practitioners which can be explained by the lack of experience from practitioners in smart contract execution mechanism in the Blockchain environment, which is different from that of the non-Blockchain software. Moreover, the number of vulnerabilities as shown in the state-of-art is still growing. Therefore, there is an urgency of solving this gap in order to avoid disaster given an Ethereum smart contract handles valuable assets, and its code is immutable.

3.4 Secure software development lifecycle & software security best practices

This section reviews the security practices used for the development of secure software in the non-Blockchain software environment. The goal of this section is to provide information on the security development

approaches used in this traditional computing environment and see how these practices can help of securing smart contracts. Given the vulnerabilities presented by the Ethereum application layer mentioned in the section above, exploring the security development of the non-blockchain software, may provide ideas and/or solutions to mitigate the vulnerabilities of the smart contract. Therefore, this section will cover the main security approaches used in software development including software practices and patterns, the software security metrics, and the software security analysis in traditional computing.

3.4.1 Secure software development Lifecycle

The software development life cycle is a conceptual model used in the management process of analyzing, developing and controlling and maintaining the software [62]. The SDLC include generally the following phases: requirement, design, implementation, testing, deployment and maintenance. The SDLC is used for releasing high-quality software at a low cost in the shortest period [63]. However, to prevent the software from this model to be vulnerable to security threats, research highlights[64]–[66] the need of incorporating security during all the phases of the SDLC. This process is known as the Secure Software development life cycle(SSDLC). the SSDLC is a software development process including practices that spread over all phases of the SDLC for strengthening security and compliance. The idea of considering security at all the phases of the SDLC emerged from the negligence of the business of considering security as a key priority which is the reason for the widespread of security vulnerabilities in non-blockchain systems[67]. Businesses value software feature over security[68], [69]. As a result of this late-in-the-game technique, bugs, flaws, and other vulnerabilities are hard to find until there is far more expensive and time-consuming to fix[70], [71]. Therefore, SSDLC will reduce the overall cost of development because it allows finding and eliminating vulnerabilities at the early stage in the software development life cycle [72].

Various security methodologies and practices applied to the SDLC phases have been developed over this decade to support SSDLC. To allow Security during the SDLC, Microsoft[73] developed Microsoft Trustworthy Computing Security Development Life Cycle framework that adds a set of security practices to each phase of the SDLC. These framework security practices involve in general: security features requirements defined based on the customer's need; activities such as threat modelling for security risk identification, security-critical component identification during the design phases; the use of static analysis tools and code reviews during the implementation phase; test of the whole system by focusing on the security-critical component during the testing phase. Essafi et al.[74] proposed a strategy-oriented process model S2D-ProM to support the developers during the software development process. This strategy-based model provides strategies and guidance at all levels of the software development life cycle to support secure software. A comprehensive software security process named CLASP was developed by Manico[75]. This process consists of security activities that can be integrated into all phases of the SDLC. For example, during the design and implementation phases of the software development, this process suggests the use of secure design guidelines and security programming practices; and static analysis tools, inspection and security testing can be used during the assurance phase[76], [77]. In order to build security concepts into the early stages of the software development life cycle, Mead[78] develop System Quality Requirement Engineering (SQUARE) model. SQUARE is a process model that provides a solution for eliciting, categorizing and prioritizing security considerations at the requirement phase. To address security software issues during the design phase, Al-Moutaq et al.[79] developed a Secure Software Design Maturity Model(SSDMM) framework. The authors conduct multi-vocal literature from which they identified 64 best practices such as 'Minimize and eliminate unnecessary functionality, Design exception handling features, Avoid timing, synchronization and sequencing issues' used to design the proposed framework. The evaluation

Figure 10 Example of software security best practices applied to various software artifacts (figure adapted from [80] - Reproduced with permission from the copyright owner)

of this framework through real-world case studies shows it can help to improve the process of designing secure software during the software development Life cycle. A recent systematic review conducted by Khan[67] allows for identifying 424 security best practices that help software development organisations to manage the security in each phase of the SDLC. This result suggests during the software coding phase, the developers should prioritize security code review whether manually or automatically. Also, the developers should refer to documentation and guidelines to create secure code during the software implementation.

Obviously, from what was mentioned above, most of the existing security methodologies and practices of SSDLC from the non-blockchain software intervene in each phase of the SDCL, including the pre-development and development phases. Moreover, most of the security activities presented from these different security methodologies include common security practices as shown the Figure 10([80] , Figure1-9). Given the immutability of the smart contract, applying the Secure Software development life cycle through some of its common security solutions to the smart contract may be useful for the development of smart contracts as it will help to prevent smart contract vulnerabilities by using these security solutions applied early in the software development life cycle. Nonetheless, it may not guarantee the smart contract without vulnerabilities, this development life cycle may mitigate the early-stage smart contract vulnerabilities before the contract deployment. We believe that using SSDLC and focusing on software security best practices in the early phases (before the deployment) of the software process, can help to mitigate the smart contract vulnerabilities.

In the following section, we are going to provide a review of some common security practices used for developing secure non-blockchain software. **The scope of this review is the security best practices at the code level of the SSDLC.** The choice of this scope is related to the fact that the security issue from the smart contract is mainly linked to the vulnerabilities injected by the contract developer during the contract development, and the immutability of the smart contract prssogram which does not promote the contract maintenance. Therefore, **we claim that to deal with this situation the effort should be oriented on the security practices at this level.**

3.4.2 Software security patterns and programming practices

One of the main focuses of this thesis is the application of security programming practices and patterns into smart contracts. We looked at this security approach for the smart contract from the literature and we found almost no evidence of this approach for the smart contract vulnerabilities mentioned above. This section aims to provide a comprehensive review of the security patterns and programming practices of traditional software (non-blockchain software).

Security patterns are structured solutions for recurring software security issues [81]. They are encapsulated solutions to software design issues that cover all the stages of the software life cycle[82]. The security patterns are described using templates which in addition to defining the security solution, provide information on the use, applicability, advantage and disadvantages.

Security pattern was first introduced around 1998 by Yoder and Barcalow[83], and to date has been regularly explored through research and use in software engineering. Yoder and Barcalow provided a list of the security pattern using Gang of Four (GoF) template to describe security aspects and to structure their patterns as a pattern language. They have been followed a year later by Braga et al.[84], and Neves et Garrido[85], who provided patterns for cryptography and access control. Several other patterns [72] [74] [86] [87] [88], appeared subsequently to reach today to an important number of security patterns. Given the growth of the security pattern[89], in order to ease the choice of appropriate security pattern, several pattern catalogues and classifications were provided [90]–[92].

As for Security programming practices, they are applicable at a lower abstraction. A security programming practice can be defined as an application or method for developing software by preventing vulnerabilities [93]. There are also several catalogues and classifications of security programming practices available the software engineering[94]–[96].

Regarding the usefulness of security patterns and programming practices, a recent survey [16] on the security pattern shows that most (67%) of the empirical evaluation-based research on the security pattern concluded the overall usefulness of security patterns. According to Abramov et al. [97], using a pattern-based method for secure development results in higher security and faster completion time. In the same vein, Smith and Williams[98] after conducting an evaluation of security patterns the author conclude that using security patterns is effective in disseminating expert knowledge among novice practitioners. Indeed, the authors in order to evaluate the ability of new novices to effectively generate black box security tests by accessing security expertise involve a number of student novices in using six security patterns to develop black box security test plans for requirements from publicly available electronic health records systems. The authors then compare the result produced by novices against that of an oracle for security test plans that was assigned to do completed the same task. As a result, the authors found that the novice results are similar to the oracle when using the six security patterns. Halkidis et al[99] conducted a qualitative evaluation of Thirteen security patterns based on criteria including ‘how well the security patterns follow the principle’, ‘how well they encounter possible problems in building secure software and ‘for which of the threat categories they do take care of. As a result, the authors concluded suitable security pattern can lead to higher reliability of the security. The usefulness of security programming practices is not excluded as well. Graff and Wyk [100], present the security programming practices as a must to address the software code vulnerability at its source. They highlight that security programming practices (secure code at the implementation level) are better used to mitigate vulnerability even if the program has been securely designed. Security programming practices refer to realistic and enforceable standards which address the most common software security issues.

3.4.3 Software security measurement and metrics

In software engineering, metrics have received multiple definitions [101], [102]. Thus, for this thesis, a metric will be defined as a quantitative measure of a given property of an attribute of an entity a standard of measure of a degree to which a software system possesses some property. Even while the measurement focuses on single-point-in-time data [103], a metric describes the data derived from the measurement that facilitates the decision-making from the businesses about the software aspect evaluated.

Software metrics are also used to evaluate the security of the software product [103]. These metrics span several stages of the software development lifecycle[104]. In the non-blockchain software literature, many research have been conducted to discuss metrics as an indicator of security. Although research recognized that a metric can be used as an indicator of security, other research stay sceptical about that. For example, Chowdhury et al. [105] investigated the use of existing complexity, coupling, and cohesion (CCC) metrics as an indicator of software security. In order to evaluate the existence of any correlation between CCC metrics and vulnerabilities, the authors conducted a case study on Mozilla Firefox involving five major releases of this system, from which they extracted the vulnerable files, computed the CCC metrics for each class, and then applied the Spearman rank correlation between these metrics and the number of vulnerabilities identified. As a result, the authors found a weak correlation between the measurements of the metrics within their studies. By conducting empirical research on complexity metrics in [105], Shin et al [17], [106] reveal that the complexity metrics can be used as an indicator of the security issue but with a low false-positive rate and a high false-negative rate. However, Epstein [107] argues several security metrics used in the industry have no relationship to security issues (vulnerabilities) and have regularly been based on false positive results.

Despite the divergence from the literature about the security metric, the metric-based researches show security metrics can be used as security indicators but some of them are not effective enough. Therefore, we argue that any possible adoption of the metrics for security in the context of smart contracts must pass through an appropriate metric definition, and evaluation to evaluate its suitability as a metric for smart contract security. For this purpose, Wang et al. [101] presented a criterion and guideline for the definition of a good security metric for an information system. After analyzing the CVSS (CVSS 2.0 SCIENCE OF COMPUTER PROGRAMMING Common Vulnerabilities Scoring System provided by NIST [108], [109]) system they raise the issue that the minor impact case of Confidentiality Integrity and Availability (CIA) element of the security in a system are treated by the CVSS as same as the cases where the impact of the CIA is significant and propose a new CIA impact equation on the CVSS base scores. To enable the developer to assess the security of the software during the development process Sultan et al [110] use the GQM (Goal Question Metric [111]) approach to provide security metrics at the level of requirement, design, coding, testing, maintenance and evolution phase. The security metrics from [110] were proposed as a framework from which other metrics can be derived.

On the other hand, empirical evaluation-based research shows that metrics are useful for software security development. For example, Shin et al. [17] investigate the prediction of the vulnerability in the software through the software metrics, particularly the software complexity metrics. By using three prediction models of each group and a model combining these metrics based on discriminant analysis and Bayesian network, they showed that these models were able to predict about 70% of vulnerable files from two open sources projects (Mozilla Firefox, and Linux Kernel) with accuracy lower than 5%. Similar to the Shin et al study, Moshtari et al [112] investigate the ability of the software metrics to predict vulnerabilities. In their study, they were considered more vulnerable unlike [17]. Their result showed complexity metrics could detect about 70% of vulnerable files with a tolerable false positive (FP) rate of 26% for cross-project vulnerability prediction on five open-source projects. In addition, 92% of the vulnerable files with a false positive (FP) of 0.12% were detected in the Mozilla

Firefox project used in their study. Besides, several metrics have also been developed for the Object-Oriented paradigm. Chidamber et al [113] via ground theories provided Object-oriented based metrics at the code level for the software structure which later has been claimed by research to measure the security of software. Some of these metrics for instance coupling (DIT, NOC, CBO) cohesion (LCOM) have been used to measure software security[105], [114].

3.4.4 Static code analysis tools

Static analysis is a method of software verification and validation (V&V), which consist of analysing the software source code for the identification of irregularities and potential defects[115]. Static analysis can be performed by a human through techniques such as code review, and inspection, however, the term “statistical analysis” is usually applied to analysis performed by an automated tool.

Static analysis tools help developers to understand the program's behaviour and to identify various defects in a program without executing the program. Various techniques are used by the static analysis tools to perform software V&V. These techniques include lexical analysis, type inference, theorem proving, data flow analysis, model checking, and symbolic execution described in Table 3. In these recent years, the static analysis tool was shown to be an efficient procedure for analysing software [116]. For example, Zhang et al. [117] analysed the effectiveness of static analysis tools and show that static analysis tools are effective at finding loopholes in software. Rahman et al.[118] ran a static analysis on 293 open source projects where they identified 21,201 code security smell such as weak encryption algorithms. Another example is from the research of Jin et al.[119], where statistical analysis tools have been successfully used to detect apps that potentially leak personal information.

On the other hand, static analysis tools present disadvantages which are related to the fact that they may produce a high rate of false positives and false negatives, whereas developers are interested in the real vulnerabilities corresponding to the ones that should be removed. Studies conclude through some empirical evaluation that applying static analysis tools are not effective for software security development [120], [121]. For example, Zitser and Misha [122] in their research, evaluated five static analysis tools from 14 code examples grouped into code without vulnerabilities and code with vulnerabilities and concluded that false positives rates need to be lowered substantially as some of the tools presented a high rate of false alarm. In the same vein, Wilander and Kamkar [123] empirically compare some public static analysis tools including Flawfinder, ITS4, RATS, Splint, and BOON on a testbed of 44 function invocations. From a testbed containing 20 vulnerable functions chosen from ITS4's vulnerability database, Secure Programming for Linux and UNIX HOWTO, and the whole [fvsn]printf family, they expose some weaknesses of the tested tools such as BOON cannot discriminate between a good and a bad strcpy even in its simplest form; High detection/false alarm rates are reported for the three purely lexical tools; and lower detection for the more sophisticated tool Splint and BOON. From this study's results, we argue that regarding the false positives and negatives that may present static code analysis tools, the use of static analysis tools in the smart contract context may not be effective for smart contract security.

Table 3 list of some static analysis techniques used in traditional software computing

Static analysis techniques	Description
Lexical analysis	Lexical analysis is based on grammar structure analysis, similar to the C compiler. This analysis method is to divide a program into several small fragments, and then compare these fragments with loopholes libraries to determine whether there are loopholes. Without considering the program's syntax, semantics and the interaction between subroutines, the false positive rate is high.
Type inference	Type inference refers to inferring the type of variables and functions by the compiler, and judging whether its access to variables and functions is in accordance with type rules. Programming language type system includes a mechanism for defining data types and a set of type rules.
Data flow analysis	Data flow analysis refers to collecting semantic information from the program code, and with an algebraic method to determine the definition and usage of the variables at compiling time. By using the control flow graph data flow analysis determines whether a value in the program is assigned to the possible vulnerability of the variables.
Rule checking	Rule checking is to check the security of the program using pre-established safety rules. There are some safety rules in program designing, such as in the 'root' privileges if the program calls the 'exec' function it will bring on security implications.
Constraint analysis	Constraint analysis is divided into constraint generation and constraint solving in the program analysis process. Constraint generation is to establish variable types or analyze restraint systems between different states using the rules of constraint generation; constraint solving is to solve the constraint system.
Patch comparison	Patch comparison includes source code patch comparison and binary code patch comparison and is mainly used to find "known" loopholes. After the software security vulnerabilities are found, the manufacturers usually release corresponding patches, so you can compare the code with patches to determine the location and causes of vulnerability.
Symbolic execution	Symbolic execution is to represent the program's input by using symbol values rather than actual data and produce algebraic expressions about the input symbols in the implementation process. By constraint solving method symbolic execution can detect the possibility of errors.
Abstract interpretation	Abstract interpretation is a formal description of program analysis. Because it only tracks program attributes users' concern, the interpretation of semantic analysis is similar to its actual semantic meaning.
Theorem proving	Theorem proving is based on semantic analysis of the program and can solve problems of infinite-state systems.
Model checking	Model-checking process first constructs formal model for the program such as state machine or directed graph, then traverses and compares the model to verify whether the system meets pre-defined characteristics.

3.5 The current state of Ethereum smart contract security development

The number of smart contracts in the Ethereum platform is over 1 million and is responsible for a huge number of data including valuable data of various businesses from different sectors. Studies and facts reveal that smart contracts are facing security problems stemming in the majority from the poor development manner of the developers. Given the immutability of the Blockchain, the security of the smart contract become crucial for business. Research has been conducted on the Ethereum Blockchain to tackle this security issue of the Ethereum smart contracts. In this section, we are going to review the research related to the development of the secure smart contract.

3.5.1 Contract analysis tools.

The research around smart contract security development is widely focused on static analysis tools using different analysis techniques such as symbolic execution, static code analysis technique fuzzy logic. Luu et al. [124] were the first to propose a static analyzer tool called Oyente to detect security vulnerabilities in smart contracts. Oyente uses the symbolic execution method and control flow graph from the EVM bytecode of the contract to detect a tool to detect certain vulnerabilities like transaction ordering dependence or re-entrancy.

From an analysis involving nearly 20,000 existing Ethereum contracts, Oyente was able to flag 8833 of them as vulnerable. However, the capability of OYENTE to detect vulnerability is weak as OYENTE present a high rate of false positive. To improve the capability of OYENTE, static analysis tools using symbolic execution methods such as MAIAN[125], TEETHER[126], Securify[127] have been introduced. MAIAN, based on specific properties of traces, leverages interprocedural symbolic analysis and concrete validator to exhibit real exploits. From the analysis of nearly one million Ethereum smart MAIAN was able to flag 34,200 vulnerable contracts. Like OYENTE and MAIAN, TEETHER uses symbolic execution to detect vulnerabilities. However, unlike OYENTE, the analysis is performed on general vulnerabilities that can be exploited by an attacker. It also automatically generates an exploit for the contract given its binary bytecode. An analysis of 38,757 unique Ethereum contracts with TEETHER, allowed us to find 815 vulnerable contracts. Based on symbolic execution, Security performs the contract analysis by symbolically analyzing the dependency graph of the code and checking compliance and violation patterns that capture sufficient conditions for proving if a property holds or not. It analyzed 18,000 smart contracts and was able to demonstrate the correctness of smart contracts and discovers violations.

Observation

Although these tools can be useful for the development of secure smart contracts, we argue these tools may not be efficient for contract vulnerability detection. Indeed, the Symbolic execution suffers from the path explosion issue, which makes it unsound and unable to explore all possible sequences due to complex constraints. For example, the symbolic execution tool may fail to scale on some programs as their code generate queries that blow up the symbolic execution solver. This problem presented by symbolism may lead to high-rate false positives and even vulnerability detection failure. By way of illustration, Ghaleb and Pattabiraman [128] show in their study that smart contract analysis tools using symbolic execution fail to detect vulnerabilities and also present false positives.

Unlike tools using symbolic execution for analyzing smart contracts, SmartCheck [15], and Slither [129] focus their analysis directly on the contract code (static code analysis). SmartCheck is an extensible analysis tool that an extensible static analysis tool is SmartCheck runs lexical and syntactical analysis on Solidity source code to translate the contract source code into an intermediate XML-based representation and then compares it with XPath models to detect vulnerability patterns. It has been tested on 4600 Ethereum smart contracts and its analysis result shows that 99.9% of contracts have issues, and 63.2% of contracts have critical vulnerabilities. Similarly, Slither which is one of the recent static analysis tools for smart contracts uses static code analysis to detect vulnerability. It performs the vulnerability detection by parsing the Solidity contract code into an intermediate representation. The Slither process consists of preserving the semantics of contract code when transforming into the EVM Bytecode. Then, this representation with the use of a static single assessment (SSA) is assessed via a set of pre-defined analyses. As a result, Slither was able to provide more effective results through experimentation involving 1000 contracts compared to the other static analysis tools such as Securify, and SmartCheck.

Similarly, tools using static code analysis such as ContractFuzzer[130] and EVMFuzzer[131] have been proposed to test smart contracts for security vulnerability. These tools combine static code analysis and fuzzy techniques to detect vulnerability. ContractFuzzer generated input fuzzing during contract execution according to ABI specifications of smart contracts and then they are defined as test oracles to detect security vulnerabilities. The identified vulnerabilities are later exposed in a log. A test running on 6991 smart contracts with ContractFuzzer was able to discover more than 459 vulnerabilities with high accuracy. The idea behind EVMFuzz consists in continuously generating seed contracts for several EVM executions to find inconsistencies between possible

results, even with cross-references. EVM fuzz testing is defined with two metrics (gasUsed and opcode sequence), implemented in different programming languages including Solidity to evaluate the differences between the different EVM platforms. EVMFuzz performed a test on 36,295 smart contracts in the real world which generated 253,153 new smart contracts after mutation. The result of the test shows that 66.2% showed differential performance, including 1596 variant contracts that showed inconsistent output.

Observation

The aforementioned tools are using different static analysis methods other than symbolic execution including a single static code analysis method (lexical analysis), a combination of static analysis methods and fuzzy logic to enhance the smart contract vulnerability detection. However, although these approaches seem more efficient for detecting vulnerabilities in smart contracts as SmartCheck and Slither present better performance than the other tools, it does not prevent the static tools to report false positives and even failing to detect vulnerability. The same study conducted by Ghaleb and Pattabiraman[128] shows the aforementioned tools using other static analysis approach report false positives and tool such as SMARTCHECK fails to detect some vulnerability. This evidence has been supported by Hegedus[132]. We argue that there is an urgent need of looking at another security approach other than smart contract analysis to tackle the smart contract vulnerability given the ineffectiveness of tool analysis for smart contracts.

While static analysis tools are focused on detecting several smart contract vulnerabilities, tools such as RA[133], and MadMax [134] focus on the detection of specific vulnerabilities. RA is a static analysis tool using symbolic execution and equivalence control to analyze only smart contracts vulnerable to re-entrancy attacks. Another tool analysing also this vulnerability was proposed by Xue et al.[135]. Unlike RA, the analysis from Madmax is focused on gas-based vulnerabilities. Gas-based vulnerabilities permit an attacker to force key contract functionality to run out of gas. This vulnerability can be exploited by an attacker to perform a denial-of-service attack on the contract. MadMAX analyses different higher-programming concepts such as "dynamic data structure storage" and "safely resumable loops to automatically detect gas-based vulnerabilities in smart contracts. The evaluation test running with MadMax show that 81% of sample contract involved in the test present vulnerabilities.

In the same vein as MadMax, static analysis tools such as Gasper, GasChecker[136] have been proposed to expose the gas-based code pattern in smart contract programs. Indeed, unlike traditional software, the Ethereum smart contracts are gas-driven programs. The choices of developers for the program implementation are crucial as intrinsically, developers will aim to optimize the levels of gas consumption under acceptable thresholds. Therefore, these tools can help the developers with this task. Withsper and GasCheker use symbolic execution to identify inefficient code patterns for gas consumption in smart contracts. The result of the test running with these tools shows most real contracts have inefficient gas-code patterns. We argue that there is a real need of adopting new practices to optimize smart contract gas consumption.

Observation

The usefulness of these tools is limited as their application scope is only for individual smart contract vulnerability types compared to other tools whose analysis includes various smart contract vulnerability types.

Furthermore, formal verification methods, which have also been evaluated to verify the correctness of the system in the traditional software environment, have been explored in the smart contract context through research. Formal verification is a process based on the formal methods of mathematics checking the correctness of the program with respect to a certain form specification. Bhargavan et al [137] proposed a framework that embodied Solidity subset and EVM bytecode in F*-a functional programming languages that allow verification of smart contract vulnerabilities. NPChecker proposed by Wang et al. [138] translates the smart contract EVM bytecode into LLVM- intermediate representation of R to check smart contract vulnerabilities. Nehaib and bobot[139] suggest Why3-a new formal language for deductive contract verification after translating the Solidity smart contract into the Why3 contract and show Why3 facilitates the evaluation of a smart contract more realistically.

Observation

The formal verification may considerably help to improve the smart contract analysis, however, the current tools for smart contract verification are not able to provide a complete formal semantics of EVM / Solidity language, thereby compromising the soundness/completeness of the verification. This has been supported by Grishchenko et al.[140] Schneider et al.[141] who show the limitations of these tools.

3.5.2 Security programming practices and patterns for smart contract security development.

As mentioned in section 1.1 security programming practices can help developers with preventing from injecting vulnerabilities into their source code. Secure programming practices to complement static analysis tools. However, few researchers have explored the application of security programming practices mitigating smart contract security vulnerabilities. To the best of our knowledge, only two sources applied secure programming practices for security smart contract development[142], [143]. Whorer and Zdun [142] were the first to propose a catalogue of security programming patterns for smart contract security. Based on the grounded theory techniques, they proposed six security design patterns supported with examples for Solidity smart contract development. In the same vein, Mavridou et al.[143] proposed two security patterns that can be implemented as plugins to facilitate their application.s

3.5.3 A review of development frameworks for supporting contract development.

To support the developer in the smart contract development various development frameworks have been released. These frameworks include Truffle[144] which is the most common development framework for smart contracts. It allows developers to write both unit and integration tests. Another development framework is Hardhat [145] which also facilitates running tests, automatically checking code for mistakes, and runs on a development network. It also provides plugins for code coverage, automatically verifying contracts on Etherscan. Etherscan [146] is a smart contract repository that can be used by the developers to analyze all deployed Ethereum smart contract data (ie code, transaction data). A similar platform to Etherscan is Bloxy [147]. The developers can also benefit from local blockchains such as Ganache [148] which is one of the most popular standalone implementations of the EVM built for development purposes. There is also a go-to suite of tools for developers called Remix[149]. It is known for its convenient browser IDE which supports the development, testing, and deploying of smart contracts. The developer can also benefit from various metric-based frameworks such as PASO [150], and Hegedus' metrics[132] to support the measurement of various smart

contract artefacts such as gas consumption, and contract structure. However, there is no evidence showing these metrics measure the contract security (we discuss that in Chapter 6).

3.6 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, we presented the state of the smart security development to alert the exposure of the Ethereum smart contract to vulnerabilities. The state-of-art of the smart contract domain showed that smart contracts are exposed to vulnerabilities. The vast majority of security incidents are attributed to the lack of experience in smart contract development by the practitioners. To support the development of the secure smart contract, the majority of research focuses on vulnerability analysis tools. However, these solution approaches are not effective enough as they present false negatives and false positives. Looking at the non-blockchain software domain, alternative solutions such as security patterns, and practices are used to support a secure software development life cycle. Research reveal through some empirical evidence the effectiveness of the security practices for mitigating vulnerability in non-blockchain software. This solution approach may therefore help to support the practitioners in the development of secure smart contracts to overcome its vulnerabilities. However, the literature review shows that only little interest has been given to this security approach for smart contract development. To the best of our knowledge, only 2 research have proposed security patterns and practices to support smart cosntract security development.

Chapter 4. Methodology

This chapter justifies and describes the main research methodology used for the contributions in this thesis. Case study research is a research methodology that combines both qualitative and quantitative approaches. We begin this chapter by presenting philosophies on the research context with the purpose of explaining the selection of the methodology used for this thesis. We proceed by providing the rationale for the selection of the methodology, and also provide information about the research methods adopted to achieve our research goal.

4.1 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy refers to the belief about the development and the understanding of the knowledge linked to a phenomenon. This belief involves the way data regarding a phenomenon are collected, analysed, and further processed [151]. The positivist research philosophy claims that the social world can be understood objectively. In this research paradigm, the researcher is an objective analyst and therefore, dissociates himself from personal values and works independently. Opposite to the positivist philosophy, the interpretivism research philosophy considers the world can be interpreted subjectively. This research paradigm is based on the principle, which mentioned that the researcher performs a specific role in observing the world. Although in principle opposite, studies that consider both positivist and interpretivism philosophy has the same importance in the world of scientific research [152] as they complement each other. The quantitative research methodologies, which have the foundation in the positivist philosophy, can be combined with qualitative methodologies, which have their foundation in the interpretivism philosophy to understand the world [153]. Sieber [154] articulated that as both quantitative and qualitative research approaches present strengths and weaknesses, researchers should utilize the strength of both approaches to better understand a phenomenon.

4.2 Considerations for choosing Case Study Research

Research methodology encompasses how the researcher intends to conduct research. It is a combination of assumptions, methods, and techniques that constitutes the procedure for collecting, analyzing data, and assessing the research's success to solve a research problem. The choice of the research methodology for research depends on many factors such as existing conducted research, theories about the field, research goals and questions, time, resource availability, and the known and unknown variables [155]. However, the choice of the research methodology is also or mainly influenced by the validity of research findings as to the goal of the researcher although is to provide insights, it is also to ensure the veracity of the insight about the phenomena studied. In software engineering, there are several research methodologies used for supporting research, and most of them are ranged into two main categories, which are qualitative and quantitative research.

Qualitative research- is an intrinsic approach aiming to understand concepts, opinions, or experiences through the collection and analysis of non-numerical data[151]. Qualitative researchers use techniques like individual experience, case studies, focus groups, and interviews to capture data about the values and emotions of participants for investigation observation. Quantitative research can be used to gather in-depth insight into a

problem or generate a new idea for research. In particular, it is beneficial in the cases where the researcher needs interaction with participants to seek in-depth answers or research that requires group interactions (e.g., interactions between both respondents and researchers). However, typically qualitative studies result in many cases that are not generalizable as the studies are carried out in a limited number of groups of participants. Unlike qualitative research, **Quantitative research** used methods and techniques to empirically investigate phenomena by collecting and analyzing numerical data. The goal of this research approach is to quantify the relationship between different types of variables (independent and dependent) involved in the studied phenomena using statistical techniques [156]. Generally, this research approach is based on a conventional and systematic process to collect data (describing cause and effect relation information) rigorously so that a number of facts and analysis results can be released.

Considering the pragmatism view, the integration of different qualitative and quantitative methods as research methodology can improve the validity of research findings [157]. This mixed-method strategy involving qualitative and quantitative methods is known as triangulation[155]. Triangulation relies on the fact that it is vital to view research from more than one standpoint in order to minimize bias. This method strategy (approach) advocates that multiple types of data and methods can support hypotheses or events to deal successfully with the naturalistic bias of a single method. Tashakkori and Teddlie[158] emphasize three reasons for conducting mixed-method research:

- (1) it allows both confirmatory and exploratory research questions to be answered by tailoring the suitable features of each method,
- (2) it enables the researcher to investigate more complex phenomena in the field because of its rich input of resources,
- (3) it represents different philosophies in a single study which allows us to conduct a more comprehensive empirical study.

Related to software engineering, Seaman [159] provides an in-depth analysis of qualitative research showing its relevance to our research domain, the author claims that nearly any software engineering issue is best investigated using a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods.

Therefore, according to the aforementioned information, to avoid bias issues related to a single data source or researcher, and to increase the reliability (validity) of our research insight, we use both qualitative and quantitative methods as a research strategy to conduct our research. Our study aims to provide a framework-based solution to optimize the security and cost problematics of software development and maintenance in the Blockchain context. Our approach is based on the investigation of transferability/applicability of the solutions and artefacts (such as security patterns, security metrics, and laws of software evolution) from the traditional computer into the Blockchain context. This outlook allows us to be pragmatic rather than ideological as we are carrying out research to deal with complex technical issues of a new software development paradigm (Blockchain) using traditional computing artefacts. Therefore, it is important to follow a stepwise method:

- Understand (Judgement) the transferability of traditional computing artefacts into the Blockchain context through supports (documents, guidelines, and theory) built by software practitioners (software developer, engineer, researcher).
- Gain the benefits (by measuring security level, cost, and other artefacts) of the findings of the applicability of traditional computing artefacts (law, security practices, security metric) from the Blockchain domain (real smart contract projects) to build this framework based solution

Consequently, using both qualitative and quantitative approaches is suitable for this research.

In the following sections, we present the rationale for selecting research methods for this thesis.

4.3 The rationale for selecting case study strategy

A case study is a multi-dimensional activity used for seeing something in its completeness and looking at it from many angles. This research method consists of analyzing events, persons, groups, projects, or other phenomena which are studied **holistically** through single or multiple methods to illuminate and explicate some analytical theme [24]. It is frequently used for seeking an answer to scientific inquiries. Although the quality of results and the combination of its elements vary, a case study is found to be a suitable methodology for carrying out empirical research studies in software engineering [160]. To conduct a successful case study, the researcher should study the case in-depth to collect information data from the case subject (project, person). Consequently, the environment where the case study is conducted should be accessible and the required resources need to be available. A case study may take a different form depending on how and why the case is selected and what the researcher intends to achieve. A case study form can be from a single case or from multiple cases both of which can be based on a holistic unit or multiple units of analysis.

Among this perception variety of case studies [161]–[163] according to Yin [164], a case study should be an empirical inquiry, which examines a state-of-the-art phenomenon in real-life situations based on multiple information resources with unclear boundaries in the given context. The case study, therefore, does not require the researcher to get control over the studied phenomena as it is in other research methodologies such as experiments or surveys. Compared to the other research methodologies Case study presents many advantages. The case study allows the collection of details about the studied phenomena that would not normally be easily collected by other research methodologies. In addition, it allows being carried out in rare cases where large samples of similar participants are not available. According to Kitcheman et al.[165], (1) cases studies can be combined with software engineering activities, (2) cases studies involving real projects do not require to increase in the size of the projects as they are already on the actual industrial scale, and (3) they enable the researcher to evaluate the actualized and expected benefits the progress.

The choice of case studies is perfectly justified by the aforementioned advantages emphasised by Kitcheman et al. [165]. Indeed, our research goal, which consists of the build a solution-based framework, will result from the investigation of the applicability of existing security development artefacts from traditional computing to the Blockchain context requires studying this phenomenon (applicability) in its completeness to avoid missing variables or bias introduction. This may affect the solution-based framework supposed to be used to support practitioners in their smart contract development. Studying this phenomenon by involving real smart contract projects will provide more accurate details on the current state.. Using real smart contract projects we will provide the actualized situation of smart contract project artefacts, from which the studied phenomena will provide actualised insights into the Blockchain context. Finally from these insights, we will be able to build a suitable framework for the security-cost effective smart contract development answering to the current needs of smart contract development.

For the whole research study, we selected a case study as a research methodology. Defined as triangulated research strategy [155], through the case study strategy we used both qualitative and quantitative approaches to collect and analysed data (see Chapter 5, Chapter 6 and Chapter 7). To implement and report the case study we followed the guidelines of Runeson et al.[160], which implementation consists of the following main activities (1) design and plan, (2) conduct (data collection), (3) analyze and (4) evaluate validity and (5) draw a conclusion

4.4 Sampling strategy and criteria

In order to address the research questions, We selected the smart contracts based on the Ethereum platform and developed with Solidity. The concerned contracts were selected from the Ethereum mainnet platform and also from a research laboratory. Some of the selected smart contracts were chosen by convenience, while others were selected based on some specific criteria allowing us to address our research questions. In-depth, for addressing (RQ1) and (RQ2), related to the investigation of the implementation of secure programming practices and patterns (RQ1), and security metrics (RQ2), we primarily relied on smart contracts representing most existing Ethereum contracts. The criteria for this were 1) a smart contract with a simple structure as advised by Ethereum when building the smart contracts. 2) smart contract with a more complex structure (contract with integrated sub-contracts) as there are also several contracts in Ethereum with complex structures. Therefore following these criteria, for the simple structure-based contracts, we selected a sample Ethereum smart contract provided by Ethereum itself, while for a complex structure-based contract, we selected one contract developed by University Blockchain researchers independently to us. Furthermore, for validation purposes of these research questions, we relied on smart contracts living in Ethereum having at least security vulnerabilities as criteria (the other criteria can be seen in Chapter 5 and Chapter 6). For addressing, the (RQ3), we only relied on contracts living on the Ethereum platform. The selection of these contracts was based on smart contracts using the Ethereum upgradability standards studied in this thesis.

4.5 The mixed data source for data collection

Yin[164] highlights different sources of data such as documentation, survey, observation, and physical artefacts that are suitable for case studies. Additionally, to data sources mentioned by Yin[164], many other sources of data (data collection techniques) such as Conceptual Modelling, Think-Aloud Protocols, Instrumenting Systems, Fly on the Wall, and Static and Dynamic Analysis of a System has been employed in Software engineering research[166]–[168]. Although these data collection techniques help to collect information, individually, the data they produce may typically present an incomplete picture. For example, for the research where the goal is to assess to assess which programming language features are most error-prone. By using the interview/questionnaire technique, a developer can give you general opinions and anecdotal evidence about this, which may be far from the accurate information that this research required.

When conducting a research study it is important to get accurate and reliable information about the phenomena under the study. For this purpose, Yin[164] suggests using multiple data collection methods as a triangulation method that relies on the fact that is vital to view research from more than one standpoint to minimize bias.

For our research, the goal is to improve the security–the cost of smart contract development through existing solutions used in traditional computing. To do so effectively requires “**understanding/judging**” the solution existing in the traditional computing applicable to the Blockchain context, and then “**evaluating**” this applicability. Therefore, from our research questions specified in the Chapter 1, which require both understating (judging) the applicability and evaluating applicability through some smart contract attributes (cost, security, size, complexity), we used mixed methods involving documentation analysis and static and dynamic analysis as data collection technique for this research.

Documentation Analysis focuses on the documentation generated by software engineers, including comments in the program code, as well as separate documents describing a software system. Data collected from these

sources can also be used in re-engineering efforts, such as subsystem identification. Other sources of documentation that can be analysed include local newsgroups, group e-mail lists, memos, and documents that define the development process. In this thesis, for the research question RQ1 and RQ2, documentation analyses were applied. Indeed, in order to judge the applicability of the security programming practices, patterns, and metrics in the smart contract context, we should need to get more information on how and when these security artefacts are implemented in traditional computing. Therefore, we conducted literature reviews, and the security programming practices, patterns and metrics guideline-based document reviews from which we could collect security programming practices, patterns, and metrics for this research. These reviewed documents consist of academics (articles, journals) and industry experts' documents (mainly from CERT[95]) related to the security artefacts involved in these research questions.

Static and Dynamic Analysis of a System analyses the code (static analysis) by traces generated or running the code (dynamic analysis) to learn about how software. For example, it can be used to compare the programming or architectural styles of several software by analysing their use of various constructs, or the values of various complexity metrics. In our thesis, we also used these data collection methods (as specified in Table 4) as the research questions RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3 quantitative data derived from software programs (smart contracts) and corresponding program artefacts including program cost, program size and other software constructs. In-depth, For the research question (RQ1), (RQ2) in order to evaluate the applicability of the security programming practices, patterns and metrics deemed applicable we applied static analysis. Indeed, we decided to not only just base the applicability of the security patterns, practices and metrics on our judgement derived from document reviews, but also by being able to implement those you judged applicable. Therefore, by using the static code analysis approach, we analysed the selected smart contract source codes and then evaluated the implementation of security programming practices, patterns and metrics into these source codes. Furthermore, in order to evaluate the metric reliability in (RQ2), we relied on static code analysis tools (including SolMet[169], and Slither[129]) to collect the value of the applicable metrics and security level for comparison. These static analysis tools were also used to collect data related to size, complexity and security in the (RQ3).

On the other hand, for collecting data related to the cost in (RQ1), and (RQ3) for upgradability standards we applied a dynamic analysis approach. Indeed, for (RQ1), we set a sandbox environment serving as the Ethereum mainnet replication. This sandbox consists of Ethereum remix [46], and Ganache[148] both connecting together and allowing to perform Ethereum's main actions(sending transactions, accessing transaction information, Ethereum account accessibility and management) and also Developer features(tracing execution, debugging). From this environment, the security programming practices and patterns were implemented and their costs (transaction costs) were **collected** from Ethereum Remix log after their source code execution as shown in the Figure. For (RQ3), the implementation costs of the upgradability standards were directly collected from the Ethereum mainnet using smart contract repositories sssfrom which data(i.e transaction cost) related to contract execution can be obtained. More details about how we implemented these data collection techniques can be seen in Chapter 5, Chapter 6 and Chapter 7)

Table 4 Data collection techniques used to collect data for research question

Contribution	Research question	Data collection technique
Chapter 5	RQ1-1: Can security programming practices from programming languages used in the non-blockchain computing be implemented in Ethereum smart contract?	Documentation analysis Static code analysis
	RQ1-2: What is the impact on the Ethereum transaction cost of implementing security programming practices?	Dynamic code analysis(Metric)
Chapter 6	RQ2-1: (Applicability of construct) Is it possible to identify and interpret the constructs embedded in the security metrics and interpret them in the Smart contract domain?	Documentation analysis Static code analysis
	RQ2-2: (Capability of measurement) Is it possible to perform the measurement (defined in the metric) in the smart contract domain?	Documentation analysis Dynamic code analysis
	RQ2-3: Usability based on automation) Is it possible to automate the metric measurement?	Dynamic code analysis(Metric)
	RQ2-4: (reliability) How do the measures of the selected metrics (From RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3) relate with each other and with security?	Dynamic code analysis(Metric)
Chapter 7	RQ3-1:What is the transaction cost of implementing upgradability methods in a smart contract?	Dynamic code analysis
	RQ3-2: Does the size of smart contracts grow as new versions are deployed?	Dynamic code analysis
	RQ3-3: Does the complexity of smart contracts grow as new versions are deployed?	Dynamic code analysis
	RQ3-4: Does the security of smart contracts decline as new versions are deployed?	Dynamic code analysis

4.6 Data Analysis through statistical methods

Schensul et al.[170] defined data analysis as a process used by researchers for reducing data to a story and interpreting it to draw findings. The data analysis process helps in reducing a large amount of data into smaller fragments, which makes sense. Marshall et al. [171], on the other hand, describe data analysis as, ambiguous, and time-consuming, but a creative and fascinating process through which a mass of collected data is being brought to structure and meaning. Researchers explore, their mission, and audiences' vision guides them to find the patterns to shape the story they want to tell. One of the important elements expected from researchers while analysing data is to stay open and remain unbiased towards unexpected patterns, expressions, and results.

Therefore, to make this, the researchers should employ effective data analysis methods that fit their research study. This concerns how the researcher should analyse the data.

In the case study-based research, the selection of the analysis method is more flexible compared to other research strategies such as surveys or experiments. In fact, for an empirical research-using case study, the choice of the analysis strategy concerns which method the researcher will adopt as a dominant one. Generally, this choice is between deductive approaches and inductive approaches. The deductive approach starts with developing a hypothesis (or hypotheses) based on existing theory and then designing a research strategy to test the hypothesis. While In an inductive approach, the process starts by collecting data, analysing patterns in the data, and then theorizing from the data to research. In research for data analysis, the quantitative approach is more preferred for the deductive approach while the qualitative approach is preferred for the inductive approach.

For our research, we followed a deductive approach. We developed a list of hypotheses based on existing theory and information related to traditional computing and employ case studies (involving smart contract projects) as a research strategy to test the defined hypothesis. As aforementioned, the research question of our research is related to the applicability of existing security solutions and artefacts from the traditional computer into the smart contract context. For this purpose, the test of our hypothesis mainly consist to evaluate the applicability through metrics (numerical obtain from Static and Dynamic Analysis of a System data collection technique) data (smart contract attributes) of existing solutions and artefacts from the traditional computer into smart contract context. Therefore, our data analysis will be mainly quantitative rather than qualitative.

In research, particularly in software engineering research, statistical techniques are, the most favoured to analyze numerical data. Statistical analysis injects objectivity into decision-making. With good statistics, instinctive decisions are not necessary. The statistical technique is usually grouped into Descriptive Statistics and inferential Statistics. Descriptive Statistics is used to describe the basic features of versatile types of data in research. It presents the data in such a meaningful way that the pattern in the data starts making sense. Nevertheless, the descriptive analysis does not go beyond making conclusions. The conclusions are based on the hypothesis researchers have formulated. Inferential statistics are used to make predictions about a larger population after research and data analysis of the representing population have been collected sample. Therefore, regarding the aforementioned information about the statistical analysis, we employed both statistics types (Descriptive and inference) to support our quantitative analysis to present accurate and reliable information for this research. More details about the data analysis implementation, and statistic techniques can be seen in the Chapter 5, Chapter 6, and Chapter 7

4.7 Threats to validity

In scientific research, the potential factors that may affect the accuracy and reliability of results are threats to validity [172]. However, these threats should be addressed in order to minimize their effects on the research results. For case study strategy, these threats should be addressed in every step of a case study where they can be classified in four dimensions of validity with the criteria to judge the design quality of a case study based on (1) construct validity: correct operational measures and constructs should represent the subject matter, which should also be interpreted similarly both by the researcher and the participant; (2) internal validity: the conceptual definitions should match operationalization as it was predicted where there may be other invisible factors affecting the validity, (3) external validity: the study should provide an extrapolation of the results beyond the initial study, in which researcher investigates the relevance of the findings for similar settings and other people, (4) reliability: is the stability of the measuring instrument with which the study should be repeatable with the actual results. For our research, we addressed all the threat classes. More details about how the threats were addressed can be seen in Chapter 5, Chapter 6, Chapter 7

Chapter 5. Characterizing the transaction cost of implementing security programming practices in Ethereum Smart Contracts

This chapter presents an investigation of general security programming practices from traditional software computing and their cost characterization in smart contract computing. This chapter aims to convey the application of existing security programming practices from traditional software to smart contracts. We also characterise the transaction cost of the security programming practices. This chapter is organized as follows: Section 5.1 provides an introduction and background to the chapter. Section 5.2 presents the research method used in this chapter. Section 5.3 provides the result of our investigation. Section 5.4 discusses the thread that can affect the validation of this study. Section 5.5 discusses the consequences of the research results, and finally, Section 5.6 provides a summary and concluding remarks on this investigation.

5.1 Introduction

Since smart contracts are immutable, they cannot be maintained like traditional software. Most research aiming to address smart contract vulnerability focus on smart contract analysis. In contrast, this research looks at adapting security programming practices from non-blockchain software development into Solidity source code. To achieve this, this research will try to adapt security programming practices from modern languages like Java, and C++ into Solidity, considering the difference in the syntax and computing platforms. Furthermore, this research intends to provide a quantification of the cost of implementing these practices in the Blockchain environment. In short, our research aims to characterize the transaction cost of introducing security programming practices in Ethereum smart contracts.

To achieve this goal, we designed a case study method. We performed a characterization of the Ethereum transaction cost (defined as the cost of deployment and cost of executing methods of the smart contracts) of implementing these security programming practices. From the literature, we identified 30 security programming practices from C++ and Java which can be applied to Solidity. To implement these security programming practices, we selected two testimonial smart contract examples. The E-Voting smart contract is offered as an example in Remix and a set of two smart contracts that implement a supply chain governance model as a distributed application in Ethereum. These selected examples provided the opportunity to implement 17 of the 30 identified security programming practices and deploy them in Ethereum. The 13 other practices could not be implemented because the vulnerabilities that they address are not exposed in these example smart contracts.

Furthermore, given the importance of this study subject, to validate the results of the case study, we investigated real-world examples of smart contracts currently deployed in Ethereum. Since the smart contracts deployed in Ethereum are immutable and transparent, it is possible to obtain the source code of deployed smart contracts. Corpus is a search tool designed to achieve this [173]. We used it to identify smart contracts that have been deployed in Ethereum and that would be suitable as validation subjects. By analysing these smart contracts, we were able to implement one of the security programming practices that cannot be implemented in the testimonial smart contracts that we had selected for the case study. Regarding the transaction cost, the results show that the application of security programming practices identified increases the cost of the baseline smart contract. Nonetheless, this difference in cost is not significant when considering the overall development cost and the potential losses resulting from malicious attackers exploiting the vulnerabilities in smart contract code. This is worsened by the fact that smart contracts are immutable, so vulnerabilities injected during deployment will remain in the smart contract as corrective maintenance is not possible. As a result, we argue

that practitioners should introduce security programming practices from traditional computing into the development process of Ethereum smart contracts.

5.2 Methodology

The research method used to achieve the goals of this chapter can be classified as a multiple-case study involving two sample cases and another real-world case for validation purposes. [149]

5.2.1 Case study design and planning

Research goal - To characterize the transaction cost of introducing secure programming practices in Ethereum smart contracts. To achieve this goal, we break down this goal by answering the following research questions:

RQ1-1: Can security programming practices from programming languages used in traditional computing be implemented in Ethereum smart contract?

Figure 11 Class diagram E-voting contract

Figure 12 Class diagram of the Supply chain smart contracts

RQ1-2: What is the impact on the Ethereum transaction cost of implementing the security programming practices?

Case definition and units of analysis- In this study, we measured the transaction cost of implementing secure programming practices in Ethereum. We selected two pertinent implementations of smart contracts for the Ethereum platform.

The first testimonial example is the E-voting smart contract which consists of a single smart contract (see Figure 11). The E-voting smart contract is provided by Ethereum and is available on the Remix-Ethereum development online platform and can be used to deploy secure distributed and anonymous elections. This smart contract has five methods (constructor, three payable methods, and one non-payable). The second testimonial example is composed of two smart contracts (see Figure 12), which interact to implement a Blockchain-based-governance-model for a supply chain [7]. These contracts from the supply chain model have 12 methods and were developed in another research project within our research group. We selected these two cases because they complement each other. The E-voting that the development is independent of this research is a single smart contract sample having a simple structure design as required by Ethereum (compared to traditional software), representing then most of the smart contracts that are in Ethereum. The supply chain smart contract has been validated and (compared to the E-voting contract) provides attack surfaces that stem from the interaction between contracts.

The unit of analysis in this study is the security programming practice, from which we measured its transaction cost when a smart contract is deployed to the Ethereum network. Transaction cost can be measured in ether (Wei) and can be equated to the dollar through a cryptocurrency exchange marketplace. For this study, we referred to the exchange rate from ether to USD fixed in March 2021 at 1,840.6224 (from <https://www.cryps.info/>). To measure the transaction cost, we rely on the measurement reported by the Remix platform when performing a transaction into an Ethereum Blockchain.

5.2.2 Experimentation and analysis procedure

Instrumentation-To answer the RQ1-1 (Can security programming practices from programming languages used in traditional computing be implemented in Ethereum smart contract?), the security programming practices guidelines were collected from SEI CERT [95] and the review of the literature. We were able to identify in the literature, security programming patterns that could be applied in Solidity other than those proposed by Whorer and Zhun [142]. Regarding these, we claim that the findings of Whorer and Zhun[142] are better classified as “Security programming practices” rather than, “Security patterns”. Some of the patterns from Whorer and Zhun [142] have been identified in the SEI-CERT list of security programming practices (albeit with a different name; these have been highlighted in Table 5). There are three others (speed bump, rate limit, check-effect-interaction), which are specific to the Blockchain platform, and have been included in this study (serving for the RQ1-2) as security programming practices. Finally, our judgment of their application in Solidity was based on our interpretation of guidelines and our knowledge of Ethereum. Likewise, our judgment was applied to determine which of the candidate practices were applicable to our testimonial examples. With these considerations, if they were deemed applicable, we implemented them.

To answer RQ1-2 (What is the impact on the Ethereum transaction cost of implementing the security programming practices?) we measured the transaction cost after deploying a smart contract in Ethereum (see section 5.3.2). To assure consistent measurement, we created a sandboxed Ethereum environment. The sandbox consists of a local Ethereum for the deployment supported by Ganache (<https://www.trufflesuite.com/ganache>). This local Ethereum is managed via Remix. Finally, for the security

programming practices implemented in the testimonial smart contract examples, we measure the transaction costs of deployment before and after implementing the security programming practice. Thereby instantiating a repeated measure ($O_{\text{before}} - X_{\text{intervention}} - O_{\text{after}}$) experimental design.

Table 5 Baseline measurement for E-Voting (EV) smart contract transaction cost

Method ID	Voting method	Baseline Transaction Cost (ether)
EV1	Constructor	1.26E-02
EV2	Delegate	1.10E-03
EV3	Vote	1.37E-03
EV4	giveRightToVote	8.74E-04
EV5	Winning Proposal	pure function, no transaction cost

Table 6 Baseline measurement for Supply chain (SC) smart contract transaction cost

Method ID	Supply chain (Bidding-Tracking) method	Baseline Transaction Cost (ether)
SC.B.1	Bidding::constructor	8.33E-02
SC.B.2	Bidding::bidding	2.95E-03
SC.B.3	Bidding::bid	1.53E-03
SC.B.4	Bidding::biddingclose	3.720E-02
SC.B.5	Bidding::withdraw	4.00E-04
SC.B.6	Bidding::authorize	1.28E-03
SC.T.7	Tracking::setContractParameter	2.93E-03
SC.T.8	Tracking::initialWholeSellerToken	9.32E-04
SC.T.9	Tracking::deliverProduct	3.56E-03
SC.T.10	Tracking::receiveProduct	6.49E-04
SC.T.11	Tracking::deleteProduct	5.94E-04

Figure 13 Flowchart of the evaluation process of security programming practices and patterns application in Solidity

Analysis procedure-Our analysis strategy is based on the measurement of the difference in transaction costs before and after the implementation of the security programming practices. Hence, for each testimonial example, we measured the baseline cost (the transaction cost without any modification on our part). This baseline transaction cost is reported in Table 5 and Table 6. Then a transaction cost was measured after

implementing each security practice. To analyse the difference, we applied pertinent statistical tests (see section 5.3.2).

5.3 Results: characterising the transaction cost of implementing security programming practices from traditional software to Ethereum smart contract

This section presents the results of our case study implementation.

5.3.1 RQ1-1 -Can security programming practices from programming languages used in traditional computing be implemented in Ethereum smart contract?

To answer the research question RQ1-1, we performed a two-step evaluation process (see Figure 13). The first step concerns the applicability analysis of the practices based on the guidelines of the security programming practices and the Ethereum environment context. If a practice was deemed not to apply to Solidity, it was not included in our study. For instance, we judged that *the Prevent SQL injection practice*, identified in our review is not applicable. We claim that this security practice cannot be applied to the Ethereum platform because this platform does not have features that make SQL injection a vulnerability. The list in Table 7 is the result of our review of security programming practices from both languages Java and C++ from SEI and those from the literature. This list represents the security programming practices that were deemed applicable to Solidity.

With this list of potentially applicable practices, we turned to our testimonial example for implementation. For each security practice in Table 7, we evaluated the testimonial example to determine if a vulnerability existed and that could be mitigated by the practice. The practice *“Ensure conversions of numeric types to narrower types do not result in lost or misinterpreted data”* was deemed to be applicable. We claim that this practice is applicable because Solidity has a type casting feature that exposes this vulnerability. However, we were not able to evaluate this practice, because none of the selected sets of smart contracts provided an implementation where this practice would be applicable.

As a result, we applied from this list 10 security programming practices to the E-voting smart contract and 13 to the supply-chain smart contract. Both testimonial smart contract examples of our study have 6 common security programming practices⁴. In total, we implemented 17 out of 30 identified security programming practices in these two testimonial smart contract examples.

To sum up and answer RQ1-1, although the testimonials contracts in this case study do not allow to verify the application of all identified security programming practices security, the programming practices from other languages can be implemented in Solidity as shown in Table 7 and those we could implement in the E-voting and supply chain smart contracts are included in this study to answer RQ1-2.

⁴ Source code available at: <https://github.com/ndaangekevin/SupplyChainSmartContractCase>; <https://github.com/smatalonga/BallotContractAndSecurityPractices>

Table 7: List of security programming practices applicable in Solidity

SP ID	Security programming practices applicable to Solidity
SP1	Conditionally executed blocks should be reachable
SP2	Defensively copy mutable input and mutable internal component
SP3	Emergency stop
SP4	Guard-check
SP5	Prevent data races when accessing bit field from multiple threads (equivalent mutex in [174])
SP6	Detect prevent integer overflow
SP7	Ensure actively held locks are released on exceptional conditions
SP8	Speed bump
SP9	Ensure that unsigned integer operations do not wrap
SP10	Ensure that compound operation on shared are atomic
SP11	Prevent initialization cycle
SP12	Public identifier from the Standard library of language
SP13	Ensure conversion of numeric types to narrower types do not result in lost or misinterpreted data
SP14	Limit accessibility of fields
SP15	Use integer types that can fully represent the possible range of unsigned data
SP16	Never use assertion or validate method arguments
SP17	Methods that perform a security check must be declared private or final
SP18	Ensure that constructors do not call overridable methods
SP19	Synchronize access to static fields that can be modified by untrusted code
SP20	Do not override thread-safe methods with methods that are not thread-safe
SP21	Do not let this reference escape during object construction
SP22	Do not publish partially initialized objects
SP23	Do not leak memory
SP24	Do not declare variables inside a switch statement before the first case label
SP25	Do not depend on the order of evaluation for side effects
SP26	Do not access a volatile object through a non-volatile reference
SP27	Do not read uninitialized memory
SP28	Checks-Effects-Interaction
SP29	Rate Limit
SP30	Enforce limits on integer values originating from tainted sources(equivalent balance limit in [174])

Table 8: Transaction cost in ether (Eth) of practices applicable in the E-voting smart contract (✗ security practices not applied)

Method SP ID	Transaction cost from E-voting contract methods (ether)			
	EV.1	EV.2	EV.3	EV.4
SP1	1.27E-02	1.10E-03	1.37E-03	✗
SP2	1.59E-02	1.34E-03	1.61E-03	✗
SP3	1.41E-02	1.12E-03	1.38E-03	8.80E-04
SP4	1.29E-02	✗	1.38E-03	✗
SP5	1.39E-02	1.62E-03	1.51E-03	1.39E-03
SP6	1.30E-02	✗	1.38E-03	✗
SP7	1.35E-02	1.32E-03	1.59E-03	✗
SP8	1.34E-02	1.13E-03	✗	✗
SP9	1.38E-02	✗	1.39E-03	1.12E-03
SP10	1.60E-02	1.64E-03	2.13E-03	✗

Figure 14 Transaction cost in ether of security programming practices applicable in the E-voting smart contract

5.3.2 RQ1-2- What is the impact on the Ethereum transaction cost of implementing the security programming practices?

To answer research question RQ1-2 we measured the transaction cost of all the methods exposed by the smart contract before and after the implementation of security programming practices.

Analysis of the E-Voting smart contract

Table 8 and Figure 14 present the transaction cost after implementing the applicable security programming practices for the E-voting. The data in Table 8 and are grouped by methods. We observed the transaction costs from the modified E-voting source code are greater than those from the baseline code. This empirical result was expected and consistent with the literature and Ethereum design [27] [34].

Nonetheless, we will analyse these results by drilling down into each method. As shown in Figure 14, EV.1 transaction cost is greater than the transaction costs from the other methods. This is because EV1 involves the deployment of the smart contract into the Blockchain, which is an expensive operation by the design of the Ethereum platform, unlike the method invocation [175]. A contract constructor is used to deploy all the contract source code, while a contract method is used for execution a part of a contract code. Therefore, for the correct analysis of the results we have divided the analysis into two groups (Group 1, for method EV1, that concern the deployment of contract, and Group 2, for methods EV2-EV4 which concerns simple method invocation).

To evaluate if there is a significant difference in Transaction Costs after the implementation of the secure programming practices, we applied paired sample T-test. Consequently, we evaluated the preconditions of the paired T-tests as follows:

- The dependent variable is measured on a continuous scale. Transaction’s cost is measured in Wei which is quantitative (in number)
- The independent variable consists of two categorical groups, in which subjects are present. In our study, groups are “before” and “after” implementation on the same baseline source code (subjects).

- There are no significant outliers as observed in Table 8.
- The distribution of the difference in the dependent variable should approximate a normal distribution. This precondition is analysed in every case. In the groups where this precondition fails, we substitute the paired T-test with a nonparametric Wilcoxon rank test.

Analysis of Group 1: As mentioned, we have observed that the transaction cost is higher after the implementation of secure programming practices. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS)-test rejects the null hypothesis of the non-normality ($D=0.253$, $p\text{-value}=0.4251$). Therefore, to evaluate our hypothesis, the paired one-tailed T-test was applied. Thus, the T-test indicates that the transaction cost after implementing the security programming practices ($M=1.4E-02$, $SD=1.114E-03$) is higher than the baseline transaction cost ($M=1.26E-02$, $SD=0.00$), resulting to statistically significant increase of $1.13E-03$ ($T(10)=-3.60$, $p\text{-value}=0.003$).

Analysis of Group 2: As observed from Figure 14, the transaction cost is higher after the implementation of the security programming practices. For Group 2, the KS-test rejects the null hypothesis of the non-normality ($D=0.2504$, $p\text{-value}=0.15498$). We applied the paired one-tailed T-test to evaluate our hypothesis. Thus, the test indicates that the transaction cost after implementing the security programming practices ($M=1.4E-03$, $SD=2.73E-04$) is higher than the baseline transaction cost ($M=1.2E-03$, $SD=2E-04$), resulting to a significant increase of $2E-04$ ($T(19)=-3.67$, $p\text{-value}=0.001$).

In summary, the empirical results show that the transaction cost after implementing the security programming practices increases.

Analysis of the Supply Chain smart contracts

For the Supply chain case, we observed the transaction cost from the modified Supply chain source code are (with a few exceptions, see section 5.3-Analysis of the outlier cases) higher than those from baseline as expected as shown in Figure 15. To evaluate the significance of those considered exceptions we applied a Grubb's test. Grubb's test consisted to identify outliers from sets of data grouped by methods ("group" explained below). The test indicates from each group that there is no significant outlier with group1 ($Mean=0.084, SD=0.0008, p>0.05$); group2 ($Mean=0.002, SD=0.001, p>0.05$); group3 ($Mean=0.037, SD=0.0004, p>0.05$). Similar to the analysis procedure with the E-voting case, the analysis procedure must separate between constructors and called methods. However, observing the data, a third category can be observed in method SC.B4. The call to SC.B4 involves the deployment of the second smart contract in the Supply chain smart contract solution. While SC.B1 and SC.B4 both involve contract deployment into the blockchain, they deploy different contracts so they must be analysed separately. Therefore, the analysis is broken down into the following three groups:

- Group 1. Involves SC.B1, which concerns the deployment of the main smart Contract which is the Supply chain smart contract constructor, which is responsible for the whole supply chain smart contract.
- Group 2. Includes SC.B2, SC.B3, and SC.B5 to SC.T11, which do not involve smart contract deployment.
- Group 3. Includes SC.B4. is the "biddingClose" method that triggers the deployment of the sub-contract Tracking which is a part of the supply chain smart contract.

To evaluate if there is a significant difference in Transaction Costs after the implementation of the secure programming practices, we applied a paired sample T-test. Consequently, we evaluated the preconditions of the paired T-test:

Table 9 Transaction cost in ether(Eth) of security programming practices applicable in the Supply Chain smart contract(security practices not applied)

Transaction cost from Supply chain contract methods (ether)											
Method SP ID	SC.B.1	SC.B.2	SC.B.3	SC.B.4	SC.B.5	SC.B.6	SC.T.7	SC.T. 8	SC.T. 9	SC.T.10	SC.T. 10
SP3	8.43E-02	×	1.53E-03	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×
SP5	8.37E-02	×	×	3.74E-02	×	×	×	×	×	×	×
SP6	8.39E-02	×	×	3.77E-02	×	×	2.93E-03	×	×	1.04E-03	×
SP7	8.40E-02	3.36E-03	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×
SP8	8.53E-02	3.36E-03	×	×	7.54E-04	×	×	×	×	×	×
SP9	8.46E-02	×	×	3.82E-02	×	×	2.98E-03	×	×	1.05E-03	×
SP14	8.42E-02	2.66E-03	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×
SP17	8.35E-02	×	1.53E-03	3.71E-02	7.01E-04	1.28E-03	2.93E-03	9.32E-04	3.56E-03	1.04E-03	5.94E-04
SP19	8.58E-02	3.36E-03	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	8.88E-04	×
SP22	8.36E-02	×	×	3.74E-02	×	×	2.93E-03	×	×	×	×
SP27	8.37E-02	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×
SP28	8.28E-02	×	×	×	4.00E-04	×	×	×	×	×	×
SP30	8.48E-02	2.96E-03	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×

Figure 15 Transaction cost in ether(Eth) of security programming practices applicable in the Supply Chain smart contract

- The dependent variable is measured on a continuous scale. Transaction cost is measured in Wei.
- The independent variable consists of two categorical groups, in which subjects are present. In our study groups are “before” and “after” implementation on the same baseline source code (subjects)
- There are no significant outliers. Outliers have been identified and discussed above. We have removed them from this analysis.
- The distribution of the difference in the dependent variable should approximate a normal distribution. This precondition is analyzed in every case. In the groups where this precondition fails, we substitute the paired T-test with a nonparametric Wilcoxon rank test.

Analysis of Group 1: We observed from this group that the transaction after implementing the security programming practices is higher than the baseline. The KS test rejects the null hypothesis of the non-normality ($D=0.12$, $p\text{-value}=0.981$). We, therefore, applied the paired one-tailed to evaluate our hypotheses. Thus, the test indicates that the transaction after implementing the security programming practices ($M= 8.42E-02$, $SD= 0.0008$) is higher than the baseline transaction cost ($M=8.33E-02$, $SD=0.00$), resulting in a statistically significant increase of $9E-04$ ($T(13) = -4.2$, $p\text{-value}=0.0006$).

Analysis of Group 2: For this group, we observed that the transaction after implementing the security programming practices is higher than the baseline.

Unlike group 1, the KS-test does not reject the null hypothesis of the non-normality ($D=0.295$, $p\text{-value}=0.387$).

Therefore, to evaluate the hypothesis defined for RQ1-2 we substitute paired one-tailed T-test with the Wilcoxon rank test. We, therefore, applied the Wilcoxon rank test. The test indicates the transaction cost after implementing the security programming practices ($Me= 1.529E-03$) is statistically different from the baseline cost ($Me=1.527E-03$).

Analysis of Group 3: As shown in Table 9, the transaction after implementing the security programming practices is also higher than the baseline. For this group, The KS-test rejects the null hypothesis of the non-normality. ($D=0.242$, $p\text{-value}=0.869$). Therefore, to evaluate Hyp-1 we applied the paired one-tailed T-test. The result from this test indicates that the transaction cost after implementing the security programming practices ($M=3.75E-02$ $SD=0.0004$) is higher than the baseline transaction cost ($M=3.72E-02$, $SD=0.00$), resulting in the statistically significant increase of $3.895E-04$ ($T(5)=$, $p\text{-value}= 0.047$). Therefore, this empirical result shows that the implementation of security programming practices increases the transaction cost.

To summarize and answer RQ1-2, security programming practices application affects the transaction cost by generally increasing the cost.

Analysis of the outlier cases

This section will try to explain the results from the three cases where the hypothesis for RQ1-2 did not hold. In Table 9 we can also observe a few data exceptions (5 of 40 implementations) in which the transaction costs from the modified Supply chain source code are (with a few exceptions) lower than those from baseline. These exceptions are resumed in Table 10.

Table 10 List of outliers

Practices	Method	Baseline cost(in ether)	Transaction cost(in ether)
SP14	SC.B2	2.951E-03	2.656E-03
SP17	SC.B4	3.720E-02	3.7176E-02
	SC.T7	2.9321E-03	2.9315E-03
	SC.T8	9.3206E-04	9.3176E-04
SP28	SC.B1	8.33E-02	8.2819E-02

Concerning SP14. Limit accessibility of fields/method practice

This practice consists of restricting the access of method and field which contains mutable objects to avoid an attacker to manipulate them. In our case, the implementation of this practice is to limit the access to “bidding” method to only the owner (user in charge of contract deployment). For that, we added to the baseline code (see Figure 16) a defined constructor to initialize the owner state with the address of the user who deployed the contract as shown in Figure 17. Then we added to the bidding method “ownerOnly” modifier to allow only the address that deployed the contract to call this method. We deployed first the contract applying this practice, then we collected from Remix log the transaction cost after calling the modified Bidding method by the address(owner) that deployed the contract. As a result, the transaction cost is lower than that of the baseline.

```
function Bidding(uint _initialTokenSupply,uint _biddingTime, address _beneficiary,
string memory _city, uint _distance,address _wholeseller) public ownerOnly {
    owner = _beneficiary;
    biddingclosetime = now + _biddingTime;
    distance = _distance;
    city = _city;
    wholeseller=_wholeseller;
    initialTokenSupply=_initialTokenSupply;
}
```

Figure 16 Baseline source code for the bidding function

```
constructor () public{
    owner=msg.sender;
}
//Bidding method
function Bidding(uint _initialTokenSupply,uint _biddingTime, address _beneficiary, string
memory _city, uint _distance,address _wholeseller) public ownerOnly {
    owner = _beneficiary;
    biddingclosetime = now + _biddingTime;
    distance = _distance;
    city = _city;
    wholeseller=_wholeseller;
    initialTokenSupply=_initialTokenSupply;
}
//adding modifier
modifier ownerOnly() {
    require(msg.sender == owner);
}
```

Figure 17 Modified source code for the bidding function

As shown the Figure 17 the bidding function uses a non-zero-value (beneficiary) to assign to a non-zero-variable

(owner) which was initialized to a non-zero-value in the constructor that we defined. In Solidity this type of operation saves the gas cost by using only 2000 gas compared to when the non-zero-value is assigned to a zero-variable (variable assigned with zero-value) that required 5000 gas which is the case of the baseline code. In the baseline code, the owner variable is assigned to a zero-value given the use of the default constructor.

Concerning SP17 “Methods that perform a security check must be declared private or final”

This practice consists to block the access of methods that manipulate sensible data. The implementation in our case is to define as private the methods that involve crucial data about the supply chain process and call these methods through defined public methods.

Understanding why this practice leads to deviations from the hypothesis was a little more complex as not all the implementations rejected the hypothesis (see Table 9)

To understand this, we devised a series of modified versions of the baseline until we were able to reproduce the behaviour with the minimum possible source code summarised in Table 11.

The experiments conducted show that SP17 does not influence this deviation of our hypothesis mentioned in the main manuscript (justified by Experiments 1, 2, 3, and 4). However, this deviation of cost has been influenced by the contract instantiation and the method visibility when SP17 is implemented. As shown the experiments 5 and 6 t seems that when the visibility of methods changes and the new contract is instantiated, there are savings in how the Solidity compiler generates opcodes.

By Analysing the opcodes from original and modified SC.T8 execution from the experiment as shown in Table 12 we observe:

- As expected, there are more opcodes in the modified SC.T8
- all opcode from modified SC.T8 are in the original one

however:

- The following five opcodes are only present in the original (and not in the modified) LOG4, BLOCKHASH, ADDMOD, NUMBER, PUSH 22.
- In particular, LOG4 consumes more gas than the rest of the other opcode units present in these executions (about more than 375 gas- its number of gas equal to $375 + 8 * (\text{number of bytes in log data}) + 4 * 375$)

In short, the presence of LOG4 is responsible for the lower cost recorded from SP17. The Solidity compiler decides to optimize the call of LOG4. Our source code is not intentionally calling Log. Therefore, we are safe to claim that our implementation of SP17 is not responsible for the lower cost. The context related to contract communication and visibility restriction leads the Solidity compiler to optimize bytecode output resulting in the lower transaction cost of certain methods after implementing SP17. This behaviour had already been identified in [176].

Concerning SP28. check-effect-interaction

This practice consists to guard function against re-entrancy attacks. The implementation of this practice consisted to prevent the re-entrancy attack to SC.B5 (withdraw method) by adding an external call code “msg.sender.transfer(bidAmount)” to the SC.B5 method.

Table 11 Experiments for tracking the lower transaction cost of SP17 on some methods

	Experiment 1	Experiment 2	Experiment 3	Experiment 4	Experiment 5	Experiment 6
Objective	Understand if instantiation of a Tracking Contract within SCB4 method has an influence. This experiment blocks everything out to rule out SP17 as the source.	Understand if instantiation of a Tracking contract within SC.B4 has an influence. This experiment introduces (minimal) instantiation.	Understand the effect of SP17 on the invoking side. This experiment extends the previous one	Understand the effect of SP17 on the instantiated side. Here we are interested in SC.B8 method transaction cost. This experiment draws from Experiment1 and Experiment2	Follow the tracking use case to understand where the decrease comes from. Here we interested in SC.T8 method transaction cost	Follow the tracking use case to understand where the decrease comes from. Here we interested in SC.T8 method transaction cost
Hypothesis	TC after the treatment is higher					
Subject	Original Unmodified Smart contracts					
Treatment	In BiddingClose of SC contract, implement SP17 Comment instantiation of Tracking	In Bidding: BiddingClose of SC contract, implement Sp17 To Tracking, implement only the constructor. Comment out all other codes.	In BiddingClose of the SC contract, implement Sp17 The tracking contract is commented in with its original all method.	Bidding contract as it is. Tracking contract with SP17 implemented to methods (including SC.T8).s	In Bidding SC contract, implement SP17 only to SC.B6(authorize) method ·Tracking contract with sp17 implemented to SC.T8 method.	In Bidding SC contract: implemented sp17 to authorize with a little modification which consisted to set visibility of SC.B6 public (knowing that Sp17 required that this method should be private)
Results	Baseline TC =53182 TC After Treatment =53228	Baseline TC = 218191 TC After Treatment =218259	Baseline TC =1832812 TC After Treatment =1839580	Baseline TC = 49070 TC After Treatment =49077	Baseline TC = 49077 TC After Treatment =48988	Baseline TC = 49077 TC After Treatment =48988
Lesson learned	The hypothesis holds, SP17 does not influence the result	The hypothesis holds, SP17 does not influence the result. Instantiation is not the issue. Therefore, there is something in the code of the Tracking SC.	The hypothesis holds, SP17 does not influence the result.	The hypothesis holds, SP17 does not influence the result. Therefore, SP17, as is, does not influence the results.	The hypothesis does not hold, Communication of both contracts implemented Sp17 might influence the result. But the communication cannot be the only or not the cause of this result given the prior experiments involving communication hold the hypotheses	Hypothesis holds. However, the visibility private that is required in the sp17 implementation influences the deviation of our hypothesis in this case including communication

Table 12 Opcodes comparison from original and modified initial-WholesellerToken for SP17

	Original initalWholeSellerToken opcodes	Modified initalWholeSellerToken opcodes
5392	SHA3	SWAP1
5393	PUSH21 726967676572656420617	PUSH2
5394	6f74206d6574a	1ff7
5395	INVALID	JUMP
5396	INVALID	JUMPDEST
5397	INVALID	JUMPDEST
5398	INVALID	POP
5399	BLOCKHASH	SWAP1
5400	INVALID	POP
5401	MOD	PUSH2
5402	NUMBER	2020
5403	ADDMOD	SWAP2
5404	INVALID	SWAP1
5405	SWAP4	PUSH2 2071
5406	LOG4	JUMP
5407	INVALID	JUMPDEST
5408	PUSH6 77f066ee4259	POP
5409	PUSH22 62878a101f0951b	SWAP1
5410		JUMP
5411		JUMPDEST
5412		DUP3
5413		DUP1

As a result, SC.B5 got higher than its baseline, however, the cost of the deployment of the modified contract after implementing SC.B5 had lower cost than the baseline.

To understand this deviation to the deployment cost side, we isolated the source code of the method SC.B5 and analysed Opcode at the deployment phase of this new contract with SC.B5 as follows:

1. Isolate the baseline SC.B5 by creating a new contract having only the SC.B5 method.
2. Deploy the contract
3. Record the opcode of the deployment
4. Modified SC.B5 by implementing Sp28 in this new contract
5. Deploy the modified contract 6. Record the deployment opcode
7. With both opcode set from baseline and modified new contract deployment we measured the gas cost from where the opcode list started to differ as shown in Table 13
8. Considering the gas used by each opcode as defined in <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1m89CVujrQe5LAFJ8-YAUCcNK950dUzMQPMJBxRtGCqs/edit#gid=0> for the measurement

As a result, the baseline contract gas cost for the deployment is 20656 against 20561 for that of the modified contract. Thus, the additional instruction code from the SC.B5 cost a minimum of 95 gas for the deployment of the baseline contract. Hence, this justified why the deployment cost of the baseline experimental contract is higher than that of the modified experimental contract. A behaviour that is described in [177].

Table 13 Comparison of the opcode list of the deployment before and after implementing SP28 to SC.B5

	original Withdraw opcodes	original Withdraw opcode
326 327	CALL	CALL
328 329	SWAP4	SWAP4
330 331	POP	POP
332 333	POP	POP
334 335	POP	POP
336 337	POP	POP
338 339	PUSH2 0309	ISZERO
340 341	JUMPI	DUP1
342	DUP1	ISZERO
	PUSH1 03	PUSH2 02c8
	PUSH1 00	JUMPI
	CALLER	RETURNDATASIZE
	PUSH20 ffffffff	PUSH1 00
	AND	DUP1
	PUSH20 ffffffff	RETURNDATACOPY RETURNDATASIZE
	AND	PUSH1 00
	DUP2	

Table 14: List of smart contracts obtained from our selection criterion

Solidity File	Type	Number of contracts	Number of high issues
0x14f56841bbe75b7f7765196b67ea3e8ad190c164.sol	contract	2	0
0x21ce844510d7fa31522d5d565f74e1c7cb950a96.sol	contract	2	0
0x3071a55a0f7916d796b54a2d095db85df693d956.sol	contract	2	0
0x733fa571c2db987dbdb7767fabf8392300f456d6.sol	contract	2	2
0xafb4785303b6dac4b6f125a271d9cf8b62f71e78.sol	contract	2	0
0xd4d21a4d3dc13730db343456fbc82ffd05c27e.sol	contract	2	0

Figure 18 Class diagram of the DEX helper

5.3.3 Validating the results with smart contracts from the Ethereum main Blockchain

In this section, we present our attempts at validating the results by using real-world contracts that have been deployed to the Ethereum main Blockchain. Our goal with this validation is to identify smart contracts where the secure programming practices that we identified as applicable can be implemented. The validation will be complemented with the same analysis of the transaction cost before and after the implementation of the security programming practices.

Validation Goal: With this validation exercise we intend to observe and provide answers to RQ1-1 and RQ1-2 using real-world smart contracts.

Contract selection: Smart contracts residing in Ethereum are immutable and transparent.

Table 15: Baseline transaction cost measurement for Dex Smart contract

Method ID	EthToDaiTradeHelperV4 method	Baseline cost(ether)
DX.1	deployment(constructor)	2.95E-02
DX.2	tradeEthForDai	7.30E-04
DX.3	tradeDaiForEth	1.06E-03
DX.4	tradeDDaiForDUSDC	1.26E-03
DX.5	tradeDUSDCForDDai	1.26E-03
DX.6	revertOnFailure	0

Table 16: Transaction cost for DEX after implementing SP4 and SP13

Security practice	Methods				
	DX.1	DX.2	DX.3	DX.4	DX.5
Sp13	2.90E-02		1.09E-03	1.29E-03	1.26E-03
Sp4	3.04E-02	7.31E-04			

Figure 19 Transaction cost in ether of security programming practices applicable in the DEX helper contract

Therefore, it is possible to identify them and explore their source code. Corpus is a Smart contract repository that captures the deployed smart contracts in the Ethereum Blockchain and makes their source codes available in a Git-like repository. When Corpus is used in conjunction with Slither [178], it is possible to filter smart contracts by several measurement criteria. As there are thousands of smart contracts deployed in Ethereum, we used the following criterion to select smart contracts for this validation⁵:

- The smart contract must invoke another smart contract. Because we know from our observations that smart contract invocations are likely spots in the source code where to apply the security programming practices. We used Corpus to filter smart contract projects with two contracts
- The smart contract must have at least one security issue of type **High**. Because we assumed that contracts with high-security issues will offer more possibilities to implement the security programming practices.

We used Slither to select smart contracts with at least one security issue of type **High**.

- Sorted the remaining smart contracts by the total number of security issues. We transverse the resulting list of smart contracts from top to bottom)

As a result, we obtained six smart contracts as shown the Table 14 and we were able to implement security programming practices in one of these contracts. This contract is DEX (Decentralise exchange) helper contract (0xafb4785303b6dac4b6f125a271d9cf8b62f71e78.sol) used to implement cryptocurrencies exchange on the top of the Ethereum. This contract is composed of a single Interface and a single contract, which interacts through the interface with three other contracts living in Ethereum as shown the Figure 18. The contract has six methods (deployment, tradeEthForDai, tradeDaiForEth, tradeDDaiForDUSDC, tradeDUSDCForDDai, _revertOnFailure). We were able to implement two security programming practices from Table 7 which are SP4 from the Security programming practices implemented in our case study, and SP13 from the security programming practices list that we were not able to implement in our case study⁶.

Analysis of the transaction cost of the implemented security programming practices: Table 16 presents the transaction cost after implementing SP4 and SP13 to the DEX helper contract. We collected the transaction cost of the baseline and modified the contract by using the same sandbox and transaction measure process used for our case study (see Instrumentation from section 5.2.2). As shown the Figure 19, the transaction costs from the modified contract after implementing the security programming practices are higher than the baseline costs of this contract (except for one transaction). As there are not enough data points to apply the statistical methods exploited in section 5.3.2, we evaluate the results of the validation using descriptive statistics. To evaluate this result, which is in line with the observations in our case study, we computed the difference between the baseline costs in Table 15 and the transaction costs measurements in Table 16. The results show that the minimum difference is 7.6E-07, the mean difference is 3.20E-05 and the maximum difference is 9.19E-04. Therefore, according to this evaluation, the implementation of security programming practices increases the transaction cost.

Analysis of the exception: As in our case study, there was one case (SP13) where the transaction cost after implementing the security programming practice was lower than the baseline measurement. Therefore, we tried to understand and provide an explanation. This case concerns the implementation of SP13 “Ensure conversion of numeric types to narrower types does not result in lost or misinterpreted data”. In this context,

⁵ Data was taken from Ethereum on 6th December 2020

⁶ Source code available: https://github.com/ndaangekevin/security_practices_application_on_real_ethereum_contract/blob/main/SP13
https://github.com/ndaangekevin/security_practices_application_on_real_ethereum_contract/blob/main/SP4

because of the structure of the program, our implementation of this practice consisted of replacing the call to the function `uint256(-1)` with an initialized `MAX_UINT`. To understand the reason behind the lower transaction cost, we isolated the source code of the contract to study the behaviour of the `uint256(-1)`. We systematically modified the contract for each call to `uint256(-1)`. Our finding shows that calling `uint256(-1)` increases the cost of deploying the contract (when compared to using `UINT_MAX`). Thus, in this smart contract, after just three uses of the constant `UINT_MAX`, is possible to observe savings in the transaction cost. This explains the initial result for SP13, as our implementation of the security practice replaced all instances of the call to `uint256(-1)`.

***Summary of the validation results.** Regarding RQ1-1, this validation exercise shows that it is possible to implement security programming practices in a case study in which the lead authors had no control of the source code. This means, the subjects within the validation sample had been developed by third parties and were all deployed to Ethereum. Regarding RQ1-2, this validation exercise shows that, with the exceptions identified, the expectation that transaction cost after implementing a practice is higher than before implementation is still a reasonable expectation.*

5.4 Validity threats

In this section, we present the possible threats, which might affect the validity of our findings and how we mitigated them.

Regarding Internal validity, we claim that the implementation of the security programming practices increases the transaction cost, however, the increase of the transaction cost might be due to the adding code and not the security practice effect. In Ethereum, adding any type of source code (opcodes) should lead to an increase in the cost. Though the main effect we are observing, is strongly related to this design decision of Ethereum, we claim that in the case of source code that is related to securing the software assets, this investigation is relevant. When arguing for the economics of secure source code (see section 5.3).

Regarding External validity, case study research is not prone to generalization. Indeed, smart contracts in our multiple case studies have been chosen by convenience. So, these might not be representative smart contracts in the Ethereum ecosystem. Nonetheless, we argue about the pertinence of the chosen examples. The E-voting provided by Ethereum is a sample of a smart contract for learning purposes. We considered it a good starting point to explore the security practice implementation. Its structure is simple. The main weakness of the Supply Chain smart contracts as a representative of the smart contract population is that they have been developed within our research group. Nonetheless, we argue towards its pertinence as (1) it has been validated by a peer-reviewed process, (2) it provides opportunities for observing the behaviour of interacting smart contracts. Moreover, to support the pertinence of our multiple case study, we investigated the transaction cost of implementing the security programming practices from this research with a contract living in Ethereum wild. As result, this contract holds the research hypothesis. Unlike our multiple case study chosen by convenience, this case has been chosen through a strong selection process (see section 5.3.2). The DEX helper contract provides opportunities for observing the behaviour of interacting contracts both leaving in the Ethereum main net which is in line with the structure of our Supply chain contract.

A possible source of **construct validity** might come from a misunderstanding of the security programming practices guideline may affect one of the findings which is the applicability of the security programming practices in solidity. In fact, our method for the decision on the applicability of the security programming practices was based on our interpretation of their guidelines. These interpretations may not be right. However,

we mitigate this through discussions and reviews of their applicability conducted by multiple researchers. Additionally, the case studies allow us to prove the applicability of security programming practices by implementing some of them.

Regarding **Conclusion validity**, the identified outliers (see section 5.3.2) are meaningful as they speak to the difference in the computational platforms between traditional computing and Blockchain distributed computing. Those outliers showed that the implementation of the practices might optimize the cost. However, we have shown that the optimization in these cases is due to the confounding effects. Indeed, the Ethereum environment has optimization mechanisms that in some contexts can trigger the optimization when implementing security programming practices. Furthermore, as our research method is a case study, it is not suited to identify the real distribution of these types of practices in the population of possible “security programming practices applicable to solidity”. As a result, our main affirmation that “implementing security programming practices increases the transaction cost of smart contracts in the Ethereum platform”, should be observed in the light of future investigations regarding the pervasiveness of security programming practices that take advantage of platform-specific savings.

5.5 Discussion

In this section, we discuss some takeaways that directly stem from our findings.

Concerning the applicability of the security practice- Our results show that the security programming practices from other languages (JAVA and C++ in our study) can be applied to Solidity. However, this transfer is not applicable to all practices. Indeed, the applicability of practices requires criteria, suitability, and opportunity of application. Suitability requires the evaluation of the context before practice is deemed applicable. For example, SQL injection practice cannot be applied to the Solidity because the Ethereum environment does not contain any SQL Database feature. Regarding the opportunity for application, the E-voting and supply chain smart contracts provide opportunities to apply the practices, however not all practices are deemed suitable for the selected smart contracts. Smart contract developers looking to exploit our results should take an interest in the practices (and patterns) from the other languages to implement security in a smart contract. Indeed, many security programming practices exist that offer many possibilities to the developer to mitigate smart contract vulnerabilities.

Incentives and deterrents for implementing security in smart contracts- The findings of our study show that, in general, the implementation of security programming practices increases transaction costs. The mean transaction cost of the implemented security programming practices for E-voting and supply chain smart contracts was respectively $1.268E-04$ and $4.26E-04$ ether. By evaluating this amount in USD, they correspond to USD 0.23 and USD 0.79. These are not onerous costs for a business. When we include all security programming practices applied, the cost of the set of implemented practices is estimated between $3.81E-03$ and $7.017E-03$ ether for the E-voting, and between $4.89E-03$ and $7.54E-03$ ether for the supply chain. Those costs are equivalent to a cost between USD 7.02 to 12.93 for E-voting and a cost between USD 9.01 and USD 13.90. We claim that these are not deterrents to implementing security. Furthermore, we note that the Blockchain platform is also different from traditional computing platforms, and so are its incentives and deterrents for implementing security programming practices.

In traditional computing, we can divide the cost of secure programming into two: the cost of implementing it, and the cost of executing the hardened software system. These two costs are paid by the business, the first in the development effort, and the second in increased platform requirements.

In a blockchain platform, the same two sources of cost can be identified. However, only the first is paid by the business. Once deployed, transactions interacting with the contract, are paid by the users of the smart contract. Therefore, increased security, which shields higher transaction costs, does not become a cost to the business.

Cost optimization and the impact of identified outliers-Finally, we turn to the identified outliers where the transaction cost in the baseline is higher than in the modified code which implemented the security practice. For practitioners, we must make two observations in this regard. First, the cost is not significant in terms of USD. Secondly, the potential for cost savings becomes an incentive for implementing security. From our research perspective, it was important to understand the nature of these cost reductions. But from a practitioner's perspective, the important takeaway should be that implementing security programming practices, is not expensive in Ethereum.

5.6 Chapter summary

This chapter presented the results of characterizing the transaction implementing security programming practices in Ethereum smart contracts. To achieve this characterization, we designed multiple case study research, where the security programming practices were evaluated against indicative smart contracts. The results were then validated with real-world smart contracts that had been deployed to Ethereum.

Our results show that the security programming practices from other languages can be applied to Solidity. Through the presented case study, we identified 30 security programming practices that can be applied to Solidity among which 17 practices have been implemented in representative smart contracts. Furthermore, during the validation step, we were able to observe one additional programming practices (which was not observed with the indicative smart contracts).

Finally, we discuss the implications of our results and produce a few claims. First, the application of security programming practices increases the transaction cost. We discussed the implications of these findings when considering Blockchain as the computing platform for smart contracts. We argue that, while our results suggest that the cost in USD of implementing these secure programming practices increases after the introduction of secure programming practices, the cost introduced is not significant. We claim that in blockchain smart contract development, where smart contracts deployed are immutable, there are increased incentives for developing secure smart contracts in the first attempt (as corrective maintenance is not readily possible in a Blockchain).

Chapter 6. Applicability of security code metrics for Solidity smart contracts

This chapter presents an investigation of software security code metrics in the smart contract field. This chapter aims to convey the application of security code metrics in smart contract programs. It is organized as follows: section 6.1 provides an introduction and brief background to the chapter. Section 6.2 provides the research method used to carry out this study addressed in this chapter. Section 6.3 presents the results derived from this study. Section 6.4 discusses the thread that can affect the validation of this study. Section 6.5 discusses the consequences of the results of this study, and finally, Section 6.6s provides a conclusion and remark on this study

6.1 Introduction

From our previous investigation on smart contract security in Chapter 5 emerged interesting conjectures regarding the application and the cost of the security programming practices and patterns on smart contracts. However, although practices and patterns may help to secure the smart contract, they do not provide an indication of the level of security of the smart contract applying them. We argue that in a computing environment like the Blockchain, practitioners should be able to measure the security level of the smart contract before their deployment, in particular, given the immutability of the smart contract. We could refer to the static analysis tool from smart contract literature to identify the security level of the metrics, but this approach presents limitations which therefore require the investigation of other means for measuring smart contract security.

Software development has a rich history outside smart contract development, and in addition to vulnerability verification tools and programming practices, software security metrics are also used to help to improve the security of a software system. Software security metrics can be used to evaluate the security of a software product during development and before deployment (as mentioned in section 3.4.3). In the smart contract domain, where deployed smart contracts remain immutable, assuring the quality and security of deployed contracts becomes, therefore, a crucial task. Thus, this study set out to investigate the applicability of the security code metrics from the non-blockchain (traditional) software domain in the Ethereum smart contracts domain.

6.2 Methodology

Similar to the methodology used in Chapter 5, a multiple case study and Goal Question Metric method are used to conduct the research presented in this chapter.

6.2.1 Case study design and planning

- Research questions

This research aims to characterize the applicability of the non-blockchain security code metrics to the smart contract. Table 17 below presents the goals of this research using the GQM template:

To achieve the goals described in Table 17, we will aim to answer the following research questions:

- **RQ2-1: (Applicability of construct)** Is it possible to identify and interpret the constructs embedded in the security metrics and interpret them in the Smart contract domain? To answer RQ2-1, we will evaluate the construct of each of the identified metrics and make a binary judgment regarding the application of the construct in a Blockchain environment.

Table 17 Research question design based on the GQM model

Purpose:	
Analyze	Source code metrics for measuring security in non-blockchain software development.
With the purpose of:	Characterizing their applicability
With respect to:	
	The applicability of Construct: Identification of built concepts around the metric and their potential interpretation in the Blockchain domain (RQ2-1) The capability of measurement: getting the metric measures based on the measurement process in the targeted domain (RQ2-2) The capacity to automate: Determine if the current blockchain development toolset enables the automation of the metric (RQ2-3) The reliability of security measurement: To evaluate the relationship between metrics measuring security in the Ethereum blockchain. (RQ2-4).
Point of view:	Researcher
In the context of:	The software coding process of smart contracts in Solidity for the Ethereum Blockchain platform. Subjects are smart contracts obtained from Ethereum and published peer-review papers

- **RQ2-2: (Capability of measurement)** Is it possible to perform the measurement (defined in the metric) in the smart contract domain? To answer this research question, we will try to follow the metric definition to obtain measurement in an indicative smart contract. The answer to this research question will result in a binary characterization of the metrics, dividing them into those for which we could achieve a measurement (yes) and those for which we could not achieve a measurement (no).

- **RQ2-3: (automation)** Is it possible to automate the metric measurement? This question builds on the previous one, by looking to provide automated support for the measurement of the metrics. This question is based on our assumption that for the Blockchain platform, automated support for source code metrics will not be as developed as in non-blockchain software environments. The answer to this research question will result in a binary characterization of the metrics, dividing them into those for which we could achieve an automatic measurement (yes) and those for which we could not achieve an automatic measurement.

- **RQ2-4: (reliability)** How do the measures of the selected metrics (From RQ2-1, RQ2-2, and RQ2-3) relate to each other and with security? This question looks at determining the relationship between the measurement results from RQ2-3. We would expect that if all the selected measurements to this point measure the same property of the same attribute from the same entity, then their resulting measures should be at least monotonic (or better yet, they should correlate). Furthermore, we also introduce the study against vulnerability detection with static analysis tools to evaluate the relationship between the selected metrics and the smart contract security vulnerability. As shown in section 3.4.3, there is conflicting evidence in the literature regarding that expectation in traditional computing (non-blockchain software).

- Case definition and units of analysis

To answer RQ2-1, RQ2-2, and RQ2-3 we selected two testimonial contracts to evaluate the identified security metrics regarding their construct and measurement. The first contract is E-voting which is a contract related to a voting agreement. Its structure is represented by a single contract using non-payable and payable methods and ownership elements which corresponds to the major single contract structure in the Ethereum platform. This contract has been provided by Ethereum as a sample for smart contract development purposes. The second set of smart contracts automates the provenance in a Blockchain-enabled supply chain. The structure of the supply chain smart contract is a

Figure 20 Abstract UML diagram of the smart contract of address:}xycfd458a064ba2f2e2a5fffa8fb13d45d07c9eb

multiple-contract structure involving communication between the contracts. This contract uses also non-payable and payable methods and ownership elements which represent the most complex structures in the Ethereum blockchain. The supply chain smart contract has been validated and (compared to E-voting) provides attack surfaces that stem from the interaction between contracts.

For RQ2-4, we rely on the real-world contracts deployed in the main Ethereum network and present a certain level of security issues. We selected smart contracts using the corpus tool. Corpus is a smart contract repository tool for obtaining contract information (source code, metadata of the contract) deployed in Ethereum [173]. For getting the most representative contracts of the contract in Ethereum, we applied the following criteria to the corpus repository:

Pragma version: any- This field represents the version of the Solidity compiler, it is not within the scope of this study to evaluate vulnerabilities through the evolution of Solidity, therefore we select 'any'

Number of source code lines: greater than 100 – we chose the arbitrary number of 100 LOC (line of code) to filter out the vast numbers of small smart contracts deployed in the Ethereum Blockchain.

Number of functions: greater than 1 and max 10- we chose this arbitrary range to obtain a reasonably sized sample of smart contracts.

Number of modifiers: any (for getting contracts with ownership permissions) - the modifier is an essential component of most of the contracts in Ethereum. Therefore, we imposed no restrictions on this filtering criterion.

Number of payable: any (for getting contracts with the payable method) - similar to the number of modifiers, most of the contracts in Ethereum include payable methods.

As the result, we were able to collect a list of 146 smart contract files, where each file can include several entities. These entities can be contract classes, libraries, and abstract classes. There is a total of 1298 entities in our sample of 146 smart contract files. Figure 20 provides an example of the smart contract file structure obtained from the collected list through Corpus, all entities in Figure 20 are included in the same deployment unit (the smart contract file). In this study, we will apply the metrics to these deployment units.

Therefore, the unit of analysis in this study is the security code metric from which we analyze its constructs, its measurement, its consistency based on automation, and its reliability in the smart contract domain.

Figure 21 Searching strategy for security code metric collection

- Instrumentation

To answer RQ2-1 (Applicability related to the construct): We firstly proceed to the collection of the security code metrics available in the non-Blockchain software environment. Figure 21 presents the search strategy used for identifying the relevant literature related to the security code metric. Our inclusion criteria comprise references that focus on code security metrics, publicly refereed, and which metrics presented are well defined and provide evidence that they measure the security. For each identified metric, we extracted the following data:

Metric name: given name of the metric

Subject: The type and the description of the entity being measure

Attribute property of the feature from the subject being measure

Measurement: process describing how the subject attribute is measured

Validation approach: validation process provides to evaluate the reliability of the metric base on the attribute being measure

As result, we were able to select among the plethora of security metrics in the literature, a list of 20 relevant security code metrics (see Table 18).

From this list of 20 security code metrics, we will provide a judgment by analyzing the metric construct against the Blockchain ecosystem and Solidity features. We will break down the information of each security construct and see if they can be interpreted in a Smart contract context. Thus, if the construct of each security metric can be interpreted in the Smart contract environment, it will be deemed applicable otherwise not applicable. Besides, based on our judgment we will assign the corresponding metric value of the applicability of the specific metric construct.

To answer RQ2-2 (measurement Capability): For the metrics deemed applicable in RQ2-1, we will evaluate if their measurement can be enacted. Firstly, we will analyze the artefacts involved in the measurement of each non-blockchain security code metric against the smart contract environment (solidity features and Ethereum ecosystem). The analysis consists of a discussion to see if the information related to the measurement of a specific security code metric can be enacted in the smart contract environment. Thus, we will deem the measurement of a specific metric applicable if its measurement can be enacted for the testimonial smart contracts. Finally, based on the potential implementation of the measure deemed applicable in the smart contract we will provide the measurement result

To answer RQ2-3 (automation): For the metrics deemed applicable (RQ2-1) and for which we showed the measurement capability (RQ2-2), to answer this research question we will study the automated measurement support. We will review from the literature, the existing automated measurement tools for Solidity in Ethereum. If there is tool support to extract the measurement artefacts for a selected metric, we will deem this metric to be usable on the basis that it can be automated.

Table 18 List of security code metrics from the traditional (non-blockchain) computing and their applicability result in the smart contract

Metric category	Metric name	Applicability of construct? (M1)	The capability of measurement (M2)	References
Weakness	SM/VBW (vulnerability-based weakness)	NO	NO	[101]
Object-oriented	WMC (Weighed Method Per Class)	YES	YES	[113]
	DIT (Depth of Inheritance)	YESs	YES	
	NOC (Number of Children)	YES	YES	
	CBO (Coupling between objects class)	YES	YES	
	RFC (Response for the Class)	YES	YES	
	LCOM (Lack of Cohesion in Method)	YES	YES	
Complexity	Stall Ratio	YES	YES	[179] [180] [181]
	CER	YES	YES	
	McCabe (CCM)	YES	YES	
	Halstead metrics	YES	YES	
	CCP	YES	YES	
Exception	Nerr	NO	NO	[110] [182]
	Nserr	NO	NO	
	Rserr	NO	NO	
	Nex	YES	YES	
	Noex	YES	YES	
	Roex	YES	YES	
	NCBC	YES	YES	
	EHF	NO	NO	

To answer RQ2-4 (reliability of the measurement): We will assess the statistical relationship between the identified security metrics and the result from the vulnerability analysis tool in the smart contract domain. For that, we will perform monotonicity and correlation analysis based on the Pearson correlation coefficient. In case they do not pass the Pearson precondition we will directly apply the Spearman correlation test. To answer this question, we focus on metrics in which the measurement can be automated (see results from RQ2-3). Solmet was used to extract these measures from the 146 contracts identified with CORPUS [173]. Furthermore, for the other verification tools existing in the literature, Slither’s vulnerability detection is more comprehensive as shown in section 3.5.3 [183].

6.3 Results

In this section, we present the results of the analysis deriving from the applicability of the security code metric from non-blockchain into the smart contract domain with solidity.

RQ2-1: Analysis of the applicability of the security metrics based on the metric construct:

To answer this research question, we proceed to the collection of the security code metric from the Literature review from which we have identified a list of 20 security code metrics. These metrics can be grouped by category as shown in Table 18(Weakness, Object-Oriented, Complexity, and Exception metrics). For each security code metric in Table 18, we identified and compared its construct against the Ethereum smart contract environment by considering the Solidity language and Blockchain computational platform.

As a result, we identified 15 of the 20 code metrics shown in Table 18 which the construct is applicable in the Ethereum smart contract domain.

Following we present our rationale for answering the applicability of construct for each of the metrics in Table 18.

Weakness metrics:

- **SM/VBW** [101]. The construct implies standard lists. The first one is CWE [59], which is a list of Common Weaknesses related to software. The second one is CVE [58], which is a list of Common Vulnerabilities related to software. These two lists are linked by the fact that weakness can imply vulnerability(ies). Therefore, for a specific weakness in CWE, the list of vulnerabilities from the CVE can be identified. However, in the smart contract context, currently, there is no standard common weaknesses list from which smart contract vulnerabilities are associated. There is a standard common weakness list implementation for smart contracts named SWC [184] (stand for Standard Weakness classification) similar to CWE, but unlike CWE, it does not associate vulnerabilities with weaknesses. Therefore, in absence of CWE and CVE lists in the smart contract context, we deemed these metrics as not applicable.

Object-oriented-metrics:

- Regarding the construct, **WMC, NOC, DIT, CBO, RFC, and LCOM** [113] constructs are originally based on Bungee's ontology. Bungee's ontology forms the basis of the concept of the objects. The constructs of these metrics are based on the complexity of the objects, some on the inheritance, the coupling between the objects, and the similarity among methods. In the smart contract domain, those concepts are well represented. By analogy, a smart contract in the Ethereum blockchain represents the class from which the deployed contract is an object. Solidity smart contract supports cohesion, coupling, and inheritance [185] (which is in line with the concepts within the scope of properties in Bungee's ontology). Furthermore, there is evidence in the literature of these metrics are used as a proxy for security[105]. Therefore, we deem these metrics applicable.

Complexity metrics:

- **Stall ratio** [179]: The construct is based on the issues that some statements may create for a program to progress toward its goal which might open the program to the attacks (like saturating the victim's machine). This construct is also observed in the smart contract context. In fact, there are statements in smart contract development that should be used carefully such as the use of "throw" in the loop, which can stall the smart contract execution. This type of statement in the contract can lead to "out of gas" situations. Therefore, we deem this metric **applicable**.
- **CER** [179]: The construct is based on the critical elements that software programs can contain. A security risk emerges if some essential data objects are changed, which may destabilize the process as a whole. In the smart contract context, contracts are also not free to critical elements. A single state variable (i.e: address private owner; uint balance) defined in a contract can be considered as a critical element of the contract given it maintains the state of the contract, which holds sometimes critical data (owner identity(address)y, financial amount). However, these states are not free to unexpected change during a transaction execution which might prevent the proper execution of a specific transaction. For instance, a contract may iterate through an array used as a data object to paying users. It is common to make sure that each payment succeeds. If not, the best practice is to revert the operation. The issue is that if a call fails, you are reverting the whole pay-out system, meaning the loop will never be complete. No one gets paid because one address is forcing an error. Therefore, we deem this metric **applicable**.
- **CCP** [179]: The construct is based on the coupling of a method that can lead to errors in method coupling with an erroneous method. In the smart contract context, Solidity allows the coupling of methods. So, as an erroneous method coupling with other methods, it will be easy for the other methods to also contain errors. Thus, Solidity through the coupling of the methods promotes the propagation of errors. Therefore, we deem this metric **applicable**.
- **McCabe complexity** [180]: The construct is based on the structure of the program code that can be complex. Furthermore, according to [106] McCabe's complexity metric can measure the security of the program. In a smart contract context, a program structure can also be complex due to the requirement of the contract. The

contract program might require more decision statements, loop statements, and so on. These combinations of statements can make a contract more complex. Therefore, we deem this metric **applicable**.

- **Halstead metrics**[181]: The construct is originally based on the evaluation of the operand and operators of each line of code of program complexity and not the span of the program. Furthermore, according to [186] this metric also measures security.

In the smart contract context, a smart contract is represented by a set of lines of code, which also has an operand and operator like the other program software. Therefore, we deem this metric as **applicable**.

Exception metrics:

- **Nex** [110], **Noex**[110] , **Roex** [110], **NCBC** [182]: Their constructs are commonly based on the exceptions in the program code, which when they are not handled can lead to program failure and also the presence of software vulnerabilities threatening the software security if the exception is not handled. In the smart contract context, a program can also contain exceptions. For example, overflow exception is a type of exception making the smart contract critical. Solidity deals with exceptions, with features (revert, throw, etc). Therefore, we deemed these metrics as **applicable**.
- **Nerr** [110], **Nserr** [110], **Rserr** [110]: The constructs of these metrics are in general based on “implementation errors”. Although the development of the smart contract can involve errors from the developer, the term “implementation errors” has not been clearly detailed by the authors in [110]. Thus, to avoid any misuse of the construct, we deemed these metrics as not applicable.
- **EHF** [182]: The construct is similar to Nex, Noex, Roex, NCBC, but this construct focuses on “the exception classes” used generally in the Object-Oriented paradigm. In Solidity, the Exception class features (by analogy Exception contracts) are not yet available. Therefore, we deemed the metric as not applicable.

Answer to RQ2-2: Analysis of the capability of the security code metric measurement in the smart contract domain:

To answer RQ2-2 we identify the metric measurement through the security metric definition. Through the comparative analysis of the metric measurement against the smart contract environment, we were able to obtain the measurement of 15 of 20 metrics from Table 18. We, therefore, claim that the measurements of those 15 metrics are applicable in the smart contract. Table 19 shows our rationale for obtaining a measurement from the metric. Table 20 supports the capability of the measurement answered in Table 18(second column) while presenting the value obtained from the measurement.

We provide the details of these 15 metrics measurements in the smart contract context in Table 20 for the E-voting and the Supply chain contracts. As shown in Table 19, the measurement approaches of these metrics are well represented in the smart contract domain. The measurement of these metrics is generally based on the number of methods related to the concept of Object-Oriented programming, the values stem from program structure based on statements (McCabe, Halstead), the complexity of the methods, the number of types of exceptions that can be determined in smart contract domain given the elements (constructs), which the measurement is related, exist in the smart contract environment. However, although some values from the measurement of certain metrics equal 0 in our contract example, this result does not challenge the answer of RQ2-2. The high-level explanation for these results is that the smart contracts used here do not provide the complexities (or vulnerabilities) that those metrics intend to count. We will discuss this further in the discussion section of this chapter.

Answer to RQ2-3: Analysis of the automation of the security code metric into smart contract domain

We identified the method of the implementation of the security code metric for which the measurement was applied (see RQ2-2) through our testimonial example. As a result, as shown in Table 21 the implementation of the measurement of WMC; DIT; CBO, and McCabe complexity were conducted automatically in the smart contract domain through an available tool called Solmet. However, for the other security code metrics, the measurement has been conducted manually. We were not able to find automated tools in the smart contract domain to collect the measures of this metric based on their measurement definition. Therefore, we claimed those metrics are currently not able to be collected automatically in the smart contract domain.

Table 19 The comparison analysis for the capability of the metric measurement into the smart contract domain

Metric	Measurement definition	Measurement interpretation in smart contract
WMC	Is the sum of the complexity for each method of a class	Like the class, contracts are also divided into methods for which complexity can be measured.
DIT	Is the depth of inheritance of the class. In cases involving multiple inheritances, the DIT will be the maximum length from the node to the root of the tree.	Based on multiple inheritance nodes and roots that represent contracts in inheritance structure, the tree involved in the measurement can be designed and the maximum length determined.
CBO	CBO for a class is a count of the number of other classes to which it is coupled.	The measurement of this metric can also be determined in a smart contract, this will consist of the identification of all the contracts coupled with it.
RFC	Is the absolute value of the set of all the methods in the class adding to all the methods called by the methods of the class	By analogy given method can call a method from another smart contract), then this cardinality can be determined in the smart contract context.
LCOM	Is a count of the number of methods pairs whose similarity is null minus the count of methods whose similarity is not null	The notion of similarity in the method refers to the use of instance variables of the class by the method. Therefore, the measurement of this metric can also be determined in the smart contract domain given instance variable (state variable) of the contract can also be used by the contract methods, the number of which can be determined.
Stall Ratio	Are the Lines of non-progressive statements in a loop/ Total lines in the loop	The metric measurement is applicable in the smart contract context given the Solidity language support loop statement.
CPP	Is the number of child methods invoked with the parameter(s) based on the parameter(s) of the original invocation	The measurement is also well applicable. Given the coupling in the smart contract and the possibility for a method to share data, the number of child methods invoked with the parameter(s) based on the parameter(s) of the original invocation of the contract can also be determined.
CER	Critical Elements Ratio= Critical Data Elements in an Object ÷ TotalNumber of Elements in the Object	In the smart contract context, critical data elements (method/state) also exist. This measurement in the smart contract consists of the determination of the number of the critical data element contract code and dividing by the total number of elements in the contract.
Nex	The number of exceptions that have been included in the code to handle possible failures	The number of exceptions used to handle errors in a smart contract can be determined by identifying exceptions provided by Solidity to handle errors in a program. Therefore, this measurement is applicable
Noex	Is the number of missing exceptions that have been omitted.	This measurement which consists of getting the number of missing exceptions can be applied in a smart contract. This will consist of the identification of the part where exceptions should have been applied in the code. Tools like OYENTE can also identify missing exceptions.
Roex	Is the ratio of the number of omitted exceptions (i.e., Noex) to the total number of exceptions that are related to security.	Given the Noex and Nex measurements are applicable in a smart contract context, $Roex = Noex \div (Noex + Nex)$ is also applicable to smart contract
McCabe (CCM)	The cyclomatic number $V(G)$ of a graph G with n vertices, e edges, and p connected components is $v(G) = e - v(G) = e - n + p$.	Smart contract structure with solidity (using decision statement, loop statement so on) allows determining e , n , and p -value of program code.
Halstead's volume	$V = N * \log_2(n)$, where $n = n_1 + n_2$, and $N = N_1 + N_2$ with N being The total number of operator occurrences and the total number of operand occurrences. ; and n is The total number of unique operators and unique operand occurrences.	Halstead's metrics measurements depend on n_1 =number of operands and n_2 =number of operators, which can be identified in solidity.

NCBC	Consider a class K1, with methods M1,.....Mn. Let each method have C1,.....Cm catch blocks. Then it is defined as the ratio of catch blocks in a class to the total number of possible catch blocks in a class	The measurement of this metric is based on the number of catch blocks in the program. Solidity does not support these statements. Solidity use features like revert, throw, and assert. In Solidity, the measurement will be based on the number of these features (functions). Therefore, this measurement is applicable but by using features provided by Solidity.
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Table 20 Measures of applicable security code metrics based on their measurement from E-voting and supply chain

Metric	E-voting	Supply chain (Bidding)	Supply chain value(Tracking)
WMC	12	11	11
DIT	0	0	0
CBO	0	1	1
McCabe Complexity	3	1.58	1.38
NOC	0	0	0
RFC (Response for the Class)	5	18	23
LCOM (Lack of Cohesion in Method)	0	0	0
Stall Ratio	0	0	0
CPP	0	0	6
CER	1	0.78	0.9
Nex	0	13	14
Noex	7	5	8
Roex	1	0.28	22

Table 21 Analysis of the automation of the non-blockchain security code metric into the smart contract domain

Metric name	Automation
WMC (Weighed Method Per Class)	YES
DIT (Depth of Inheritance)	YES
NOC (Number of Children)	NO
CBO (Coupling between objects class)	YES
RFC (Response for the Class)	NO
LCOM (Lack of Cohesion in Method)	NO
Stall Ratio	NO
CER	NO
Nex	NO
Noex	NO
Roex	NO
McCabe Complexity	YES
Halstead metrics	NO
CCP	NO
NCBC	NO
EHF	NO

Answer to RQ2-4 Analysis of the reliability of the security code metric measurement in the smart contract domain

To answer RQ2-4, we perform a correlation analysis. Our rationale for this analysis (which is similar to Chowdhury et al. [105]) is that if all the metrics included in the analysis are measuring security, then their measurements should ideally correlate (or at least show a monotonic relationship). Furthermore, we included the measurement of a static analyzer (Slither) to provide an independent – understood as not dependent on our research – measure of security in smart contracts.

The data for this analysis includes the measurement of security code metrics for which we were able to automate the measurement (see RQ2-2) and between the static analyzer measures resulting from Slither. The data for both security code metrics and Slither were collected from real-world smart contracts deployed in the main Ethereum network as explained in the instrumentation section of this chapter. A total of 146 unique smart contracts are involved

Figure 22 Plot of the relationship between security code metrics and vulnerabilities from Slither

Table 22 Descriptive statistics the data of security code metric and vulnerabilities from Slither

Variable	N	Average	Mean	Std Dev
WMC	146	57.23	57.23	61.36
DIT	146	6.26	6.26	11.61
CBO	146	2.48	2.48	4.42
McCabe Complexity	146	9.82	9.82	8.09
Slither data	146	56.68	56.68	75.46

in this analysis. Thus, to proceed to the correlation analysis we first evaluate the dataset involving security code metrics measurements and vulnerability data from Slither (Evidence provided in [187]) to the Pearson precondition:

- The pair of variables is measured continuously. The data values are numbers.
- There is the presence of a few outliers for the set of pair data apart from data involving WMC and McCabe Complexity (as shown in Figure 22).
- The relationship between variable values should be linear. As shown in Figure 22 the set of data involving all the security code metrics and the vulnerabilities from Slither do not present a linear relationship apart from the data involving WMC and McCabe complexity (the shape of values formed by the scatterplot is linear).

Thus given at least one of the preconditions of the Pearson correlation coefficient failed (presence of outlier/non-linearity) for some paired variable, we applied Spearman correlation and perform the Pearson correlation to data involving **WMC and McCabe complexity** which are in line with the precondition of Pearson correlation.

Table 23 Spearman's rank correlation between the non-blockchain security code metrics and between Slither

	WMC	DIT	CBO	McCabe Complexity	Slither
WMC	1/0				
DIT	0.577/2.4E-14	1/0			
CBO	0.71/9.01E-24	0.26/1.11E-03	1/0		
McCabe.Complexity	0.88/ 3.36E-49	0.73/3.22E-26	0.67/1.27E-20	1/0	
Slither	0.57/2.43E-14	0.25/1.19E-03	0.48/8.57E-10	0.54/1.59E-12	1/0

For our analysis we adapt the categorisation for correlation coefficients of Marcus and Poshyvanyk [21]: ([0 – 0.1] insignificant, [0.1 – 0.3] low, [0.3 – 0.5] moderate, [0.5 – 0.7] large, [0.7 – 0.9] very large, and [0.9 – 1] almost perfect; if p coefficient proves to be statistically significant at the 0.001 level.

Correlation analysis

- **Assessing the correlation of the metrics and the vulnerabilities from Slither:** Correlation measures the linear relationship between two variables. As shown the Figure 22, there is no linear relationship between the data involving the metric and vulnerabilities from Slither.

Monotonicity analysis

- **Assessing the monotonicity between security code metrics measurement:** Monotonicity measures the strength and the direction of the monotonic association between two variables. Unlike the correlation, there is no requirement for that relationship to be linear. This relationship can be observed through the Spearman correlation test. Table 23 presents the result obtained by performing this test on our data. As shown in Table 23, unlike the DIT and CBO pair presenting a low monotonic relationship ($0.1 < P < 0.3$), for the rest of the metric there is a statistical significance ($p\text{-value} < 0.001$), and in general a very large correlation ($0.7 < P < 0.9$) relationship between them (except DIT and WMC pair with ($0.5 < P < 0.7$)). Therefore, this result shows in general, there is a strong monotonic relationship between the metrics identified in this research for the data sample.
- **Assessing the monotonicity between each metric measurement data and security vulnerabilities data from Slither:** As shown in Table 23, there is a statistical significance ($p\text{-value} < 0.001$) and large correlation between WMC(0.57), the Average McCabe complexity(0.54), and vulnerabilities identified from Slither. There is also a statistical significance ($p < 0.001$) between CBO, and the vulnerabilities from Slither but with a moderate monotonic relationship ($0.3 < P < 0.5$). However, unlike the rest of the metrics, the relationship between the DIT and Slither results can be said to be less monotonic ($0.1 < P < 0.3$). Therefore, despite there is statistical significance from most of the metrics (McCabe complexity, WMC, and CBO), and the vulnerabilities data from Slither, this result shows there is not a strong monotonic relationship between the measurements of security from the metrics and from the static analyzer (we discuss the implication in section 6.5).

6.4 Validity threats

In this section, we present the possible threats that can affect the validity of our research results.

Regarding construct validity, the reliability result of the security code metrics might be threatened by the improper choice of the security analysis tool used in our research. In fact, the reliability of the security code metrics has been evaluated through correlative analysis between security code metrics and vulnerabilities identified by a static analysis tool. However, the result provided by this tool might not be appropriate regarding the other result from other tools given the detection tool environment suffers from a lack of consensus illustrated for instance by different result reports from the common measures [188]. Nonetheless, we could mitigate this by referring to the result provided by

the empirical study [189] showing that currently unlike the other analysis tools, Slither is more suitable (cover more vulnerability, high performance).

Regarding the conclusion validity, it is not the reliability (RQ2-4) of all security code metrics for which construct, and measurement are applicable that has been evaluated. Only the reliability of the metrics which measurement can be automated has been evaluated and show that they are in general reliable in terms of security in the smart contract. Therefore, the claim regarding the non-applicability of the security code metrics identified from traditional computing might require further investigation to cover the evaluation of the rest of identified security code metrics in this study.

6.5 Discussion

In this section, we provide a discussion of some points that stem from the results of our study.

Regarding the Applicability of security, code metric construct into Solidity smart contract

The main result from our study regarding the applicability of the security code metric constructs into smart contracts shows that the construct of 15 security code metrics from the non-blockchain software literature can be applied to Solidity smart contracts. These 15 metrics for which the construct is applicable in the smart contract domain are related to the categories of coupling, cohesion, inheritance complexity, and exception handling of the program code. These categories of metrics (coupling, cohesion, inheritance, exception, and complexity) have been empirically shown to be suitable to measure program code security [93], [106]. In the context of smart contracts, although there is little (up to this research work) evidence of the use of software security metrics, nonetheless, it can be assumed that the relationship between these metrics and security is maintained in smart contracts. For instance, a complex smart contracts program is generally a source of vulnerability [130]. Thus, the use of complexity metrics might help to raise awareness of the complexity of a smart contract program and therefore indirectly provide information on the security of a smart contract. We, therefore, encourage the developers to use the metric identified as applicable in this study to get more confident about the security of the smart contracts before their deployment.

Regarding the measuring capacity to automate metrics measurements in Blockchain

The result from answering RQ2-2 shows that the security code metrics measurements from the non-blockchain software domain apply to smart contracts, however not all the metric measurements can be currently automated. The applicability of the measurement into the smart contract domain is not surprising as although the smart contract environment (means the Blockchain) differs from the traditional software environment, the measurement descriptions of the set of the identified metrics seem to be not related to the program environment, but they relate to the programming paradigm and the language features used. In fact, the measurement description of the identified metrics is directly related to Object-Oriented programming features (cohesion, inheritance, coupling) and also to the basic programming language features (statement, data variable, exception). Both the Programming paradigm and language basis are well represented in the context of the smart contract for the fact that Solidity is based on Object (Contract) Oriented programming and also as a programming language, it is used all basic language features to build a smart contract.

On another hand, the lack of automation of the identified security metrics into the smart context may limit the adoption of the discovered security metrics. Indeed, from developer professional experience if the development environment does not support the automatic gathering of metrics, then it is unlikely that the metrics will be used. Therefore, from our point of view, the adoption of a metric stems from its automation. In this regard, only WMC, DIT, CBO, and McCabe complexity (considered like security metrics) can be collected automatically with the available tool at the moment of this research (see the measurement data of these metrics in [187]). The rest of the identified metric measurements, to the best of our knowledge, can only be collected manually. For some metrics measurements such

as Halstead, this task is laborious (our raw data is available on Github ⁷ ⁸). For instance, the Halstead volume measurement which is applied manually to an Ethereum smart contract requires identifying all operators and operands of the program code. Thus, the higher the program size will be, the harder the measure collection of the Halstead volume is going to be.

Regarding metrics measures at zero in Table 20

The measurement analysis for the security code metric involved the implementation of the security code metric for which measurement was deemed applicable in our two contract examples. As shown in Table 20, the measure of some metrics (DIT, NOC, stall ratio, and LCOM) are equal to 0 for both contracts. This result is reasonable given none of those smart contracts use inheritance. A similar point is also observed for the stall ratio metric measure applied on our testimonial contract where their value equals 0. For instance, the Stall ratio measurement looks at the number of statements in the loop that can delay the program execution. Yet the E-Voting smart contract and the Supply Chain smart contract do not present loop statements. Therefore, for a contract involving the loop and statement that might delay the program execution the measure of the stall ratio will likely not be a non-zero value. We make this explanation to highlight that the values with 0, are consistent with the construct of the metric and a valid result in the process of measuring the involved metrics.

Regarding consistency and reliability of the security code metric

In RQ2-4, we investigated the type of relationship among the metrics and between the metrics and a static code analyzer. The expectation was that since all the variables (metrics) are measures of the smart contract (entity) (regarding the result from RQ2-1 and RQ2-2), and the program security (attribute) (according to the non-blockchain software literature), then the results from the relationship should correlate (or at least show a monotonic behaviour).

We evaluated the assumption with a list of 146 real-world smart contracts deployed to Ethereum (For evidence, all the measures data can be seen in [187]). We first observed that there was no correlation among the measurements. Regarding possible monotonicity, the set of metrics shows a correlation among the rank of the measurements that can be classified as a “very large monotonic” relationship (see section 6.3). However, this classification relationship identified among the set of metrics does not exist between these metrics and the vulnerabilities from Slither. Only WMC and the Average McCabe complexity and Slither show a correlation with the vulnerabilities from Slither that can be classified as a “large monotonic” relationship. We claim that is an indication that “security” as a measurement concept is elusive and dependent on interpretation. Slither's interpretation of security issues seems different from what some applicable non-Blockchain security metrics identify as potential security issues. We do note that our results are consistent with other correlation studies of security metrics in non-blockchain domains (see [17],[107],[190],[191]).

In the case of smart contract development, where Blockchain immutability prevents maintenance, the risk-averse strategy is to use several measures of security. Accepting that, WMC, DIT, CBO, McCabe complexity, measure the smart contract security, and indicate potential threats; a developer should investigate all metrics or at least one from each category (including the results of static analyzers) whenever he builds smart contracts.

6.6 Chapter summary

In this chapter, we investigated the applicability of the security code metrics from traditional software into Solidity smart contracts. For achieving this study, we analyzed the applicability of security code metrics, collected from the literature. We analyzed their construct to validate that their definition applied in the Blockchain context, then

⁷ <https://github.com/ndaangekevin/security-code-metric-collection-for-smart-contract.-E-voting-casae-st>

⁸ <https://github.com/ndaangekevin/security-code-metric-collection-for-smart-contract.-Supply-chain-casae-study>

measured known smart contracts to validate the previous analysis by obtaining a concrete measurement. Then, we analyzed the capacity of the current blockchain development toolset to automate their measures. Finally, we analyzed all resulting measures to determine the reliability of these metrics to measure security.

As a result, we identified a list of 15 security code metrics from the non-blockchain software domain for which the construct and measurement are applicable in the smart contract domain. We provided evidence of the measurement of each of the applicable metrics. We, therefore, claim that security code metrics can be used by the developer and business in smart contract development. However, the use of those metrics is challenging. Most of those metrics must be collected manually and this manual collection task can be laborious. Therefore, we looked at the currently available tools to collect measurement of smart contracts and found that there are tools to automate the collection of only four (WMC, DIT, CBO, McCabe complexity) out of the 15 metrics.

Finally, we looked at the reliability of the aforementioned four metrics to measure security and compared them to the vulnerability measures of a static analyzer. Using a sample of 146 real-world smart contracts, we found that WMC, McCabe complexity and Slither show a largely monotonic relationship. This result is important for practitioners looking to use metrics to inform the security of their development process. While this result is consistent with the literature in non-blockchain domains, we argue that for developers of smart contracts, the result implies that a single metric would not be sufficient to inform the development process. The Immutability of the blockchain implies that once deployed smart contracts cannot be subjected to corrective maintenance, therefore, a single metric cannot provide enough assurance of the security level of the source code.

Chapter 7. Characteristics of the smart contract evolution-based standard upgradability method used in Blockchain

This chapter presents an investigation carried out on the upgradability standard methods used in Ethereum smart contracts. This chapter aims to characterise the impact of the upgradability standards on smart contract maintenance. This chapter is therefore organised as follows: Section 7.1 provided an introduction to the chapter. Section 7.2 provides background regarding the non Blockchain software and smart contract current maintenance. Section 7.3 presents the research method used to address this study. Section 7.4 presents the results of the investigation carried out in this chapter. Section 7.5 discusses the threats that can affect the validation of this study. Section 7.6 discusses the results obtained from this study, and finally, section 7.7 provides a conclusion to this chapter.

7.1 Introduction

Following the results of Chapter 6 and Chapter 7, interesting conjectures regarding the applicability of security solutions including software program practices, and metrics from traditional software to mitigate smart contract security vulnerability during the contract development. We observed how immutability guides decision-making in Smart contract development. To work around the immutability of the blockchain, the Ethereum community is developing upgradability methods to enable to update the smart contracts

As this thesis aims to provide a comprehensive solution to support smart contract security development, the adoption of the upgradability method in smart contract security development with the security solutions identified in Chapter 6 and Chapter 7 is of interest as it may allow maintaining the security of the smart contract.

There are currently four main upgradability standards in use by Ethereum developers (EIP-897 [19], EIP-1822 [20], EIP-1967 [21], and EIP-2535 [22]). These upgradability standards describe practices that can be used to modify and re-deploy a smart contract into the Ethereum Blockchain, thereby enabling the maintenance and evolution of smart contracts. In the software engineering context, while software maintenance focuses on activities to improve or adapt the software product in production, software evolution focuses on the activities linked to the evolutionary behaviour of the software product. The software evolution stipulates as the software product can be changed through maintenance activity, This behaviour presented by the software forms the basis of the Lehman laws. According to Lehman [192], a software system follows eight laws. Many studies have been conducted to evaluate these Lehman laws on different types of software systems such as proprietary, and open-source systems and they seem to show that many traditional software systems follow these laws.

To evaluate the impact of the upgradability methods in smart contract security development, this chapter intends to investigate the behaviour of Ethereum's standard upgradability methods, by characterizing the current Ethereum upgradability standard methods with respect to cost, size, complexity, and quality (security). As a result of this characterization, we will provide a view into the behaviour of Lehman's law in a Blockchain context. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to look at a software evolution for the smart contract in Blockchain. In short, this research aims to characterize the effects of Ethereum's standard upgradability methods on smart contract evolution.

7.2 Background

7.2.1 Concepts in software maintenance and evolution

Software maintenance and evolution are the areas that focus on extending the lifespan of a software system after it has been deployed to its operational environment. These areas have been thoroughly studied in software engineering

(for instance see [23], [193]–[196]), with their first roots usually assigned to Lehman as early as 1969. Software maintenance and software evolution are terms that are related, yet different. And this distinction will take special importance when looking at the current practices for evolving smart contracts.

According to ISO/IEC/IEEE 14764-2006 standard, software maintenance consists of the set of activities used to modify a software product after delivery to correct faults, improve performance, and adaptation to another environment [197]. It is part of the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC), is usually the most expensive phase. There are four types of maintenance for ISO/IEC/IEEE 14764:2016 standard: Perfective, Corrective, Adaptive, and Preventive. Perfective maintenance consists of improving the performance or maintainability of the software after delivery. Corrective maintenance consists of reactive changes to remove faults in the software after delivery. Adaptive maintenance is the modification of a software product performed after delivery to keep a computer program usable in a changed environment. Preventive maintenance refers to software modifications performed to prevent problems before they occur. All these maintenance types take place when there is a requirement for change. Furthermore, software maintenance is considered a costly and hard activity for the business [198]. The software maintenance cost can fluctuate between 50% and 90% of the total software production cost [199]. Businesses face several challenges during the maintenance in the life cycle phase of software development, such as the analysis of the impact of change, corrective change, and challenges based on program comprehension. Many research works were driven for this activity and led to the establishment of the approaches, management policies, theories, and guidelines to support software Maintenance [23][197] [200][201].

Software evolution was introduced by Lehman to describe how software behaves after it has been deployed to its production environment. A software system evolves as software maintenance activities are enacted to modify a software product after delivery. The behaviour of the software system as it evolves forms the basis for Lehman's laws on software evolution. [23]. These laws seek to consistently account for observed phenomena regarding the evolution of software, and can be stated as:

1. **Continuing Change:** The system must be continually adapted or it becomes progressively less satisfactory;
2. **Increasing Complexity.** As the system evolves, its complexity increases unless work is done to maintain or reduce it;
3. **Self-Regulation:** The system evolution processes are self-regulating with the distribution of product and process measures close to normal;
4. **Law of conservation of organizational Stability:** The work rate of an organization evolving a software system tends to be constant over the operational lifetime of that system or phases of that lifetime
5. **Conservation of Familiarity:** As a system evolves, all associated with it such as developers, sales personnel, and users, must maintain mastery of its content and behaviour to achieve satisfactory evolution,
6. **Continuing Growth:** The functional content of a system must be continually increased to maintain user satisfaction over its lifetime;
7. **Declining Quality:** The quality of a system will appear to be declining unless it is rigorously maintained and adapted to operational environment changes;
8. **Feedback System:** The evolution processes constitute multi-level, multi-loop, multi-agent feedback systems and must be treated as such to achieve significant improvement over any reasonable base.

These laws have been thoroughly studied, and evidence-based research has both supported and rejected the predictions of these laws in non-blockchain software systems. In this paragraph, we summarize a few of these research on proprietary systems and open-source systems. Among these empirical studies on proprietary systems, the study of Yuen [202] shows that only the first two laws were supported. Similarly, Cook and Roesch [193] conducted an empirical study involving 10 releases over 18 months of a telephone switch system from a Telecommunication company. They found that the system's behaviour satisfies Lehman's laws. On the other hand, Godfrey et al.[203] evaluate Lehman's laws on a system, but an open-source system. The idea behind their study was to see if the open-source system evolution narratives are significantly different from the proprietary developed system as they use different development approaches. They examined 96 Linux kernel versions from which they measure various aspects of the growth of Linux. Their result follows the 6th Lehman law but is not in line with the 2nd, 3rd, and 5th laws. A similar study

by Lee et al. [204] evaluates Lehman’s laws on an open-source system named JfreeChart. They measured 22 versions of JfreeChart, the size(number of classes), the coupling and cohesion metrics then analyze the relationship between them. Their result supports the 1st, 2nd, and 6th out of eight laws. We summarize in Table 24, some studies and their result regarding the Lehman laws. As shown in Table 24, from the best of our knowledge most of the studies driven for evaluating the Lehman laws were on proprietary and open-source systems. This relevance justifies the need to conduct the Lehman laws evaluation on Blockchain applications precisely on smart contracts as the Blockchain features differ from that of the traditional computing environment.

Closer to our area of study, the work by Cao et al.[213], looks at the validity of Lehman’s Laws in the evolution of open-source blockchain protocols. The difference in this work is clear, while we are focusing on the evolution (and maintenance practices) of smart contracts, Cao et al.[213] are looking at the evolution of the source code of protocols of different Blockchains. Their results show that most Blockchain protocols involved in this study behave in agreement with the 1st, 3rd, 5th, 6th, and 8th laws.

Table 24 Empirical studies based on the evaluation of the Lehman laws (✓ verified, ⊗ not verified, ✓ partially verified, ✗ (partially not verified)

Reference	System type	Lehman’s laws							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Lehman et al[23], [192], [205]	Proprietary	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Yuen[202]	Proprietary	✓	✓	⊗	⊗	⊗	N/A	N/A	N/A
Cook and Roesch[193]	Proprietary	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	N/A	N/A
Kitchenham[206]	Proprietary	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	N/A	N/A	N/A
Lawrence et al [207]	Proprietary	✓	✓	⊗	⊗	⊗	N/A	N/A	N/A
Godfrey et al[203]	Open source	✓	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	✓	⊗	⊗
Lee et al. [204]	Open source	✓	✓	⊗	⊗	⊗	✓	⊗	⊗
Robles et al[208]	Open source	✓	⊗	⊗	N/A	⊗	✓	N/A	N/A
Israeli and Feitelson[209]	Open source	✓	⊗	✓	✓	✓	⊗	✓	✓
Koch[210], [211]	Open source	✓	⊗	N/A	✗	N/A	✓	N/A	N/A
Herraiz et al.[212]	Open source	✓	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	✓	N/A	N/A
Cao et al[213]	Blockchain Protocols	✓	⊗	✓	⊗	✓	✓	⊗	✓

7.2.2 Current practices for Smart contract maintainability

From a bird's eye view, the immutability of the Blockchain would prevent a smart contract from being modified. As mentioned, Immutability is a key enabler of the applications of smart contracts as relentless enforcers of rules of engagement for a Distributed Application in a (potentially) untrustful environment. However, as with non-blockchain software, a smart contract will require modification after it has been deployed to the Blockchain network (for instance to adapt to the changes in the blockchain protocol, to adapt to the changes in the development language, or to correct security issues).

Maintenance of a smart contract system is therefore necessary. Given that a deployed smart contract cannot be modified, the general strategy to accomplish this is to deploy a new version into the network. As a result, there is a need to enforce the users to use the latest version contract and also perform data migration (if necessary). To facilitate this enforcement and or migration, a developer can refer to the registry and proxy-based upgradability methods to maintain the smart contract. The upgradability methods can be grouped into non-standard (registry and upgradable storage proxy methods) and standard methods ([203]EIP-897[19], EIP-1822[20], EIP-1967[21], and EIP-2535[22] methods). A standard upgradability method refers to the methods registered by the Ethereum Improvement Proposal(EIPs). EIPs describe standards for the Ethereum platform.

The registry method is a smart contract upgradability method that involves two types of smart contracts, a master and a slave. This method consists of creating a Master contract that stores the addresses of the other contract (known as slaves) and provides them (including the latest address) to the user or any other contract. This method seems to be simple, but it is difficult for a developer to migrate data from one contract to another contract [214].

A proxy-based upgradability method can be used as an alternative to facilitate data migration. The proxy-based upgradability method uses a proxy contract to separate the data storage from the business logic of the contract. This method involves the use of a delegate call mechanism. The delegate call is a low-level mechanism of the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) that allows any contract to execute a function in the context of another contract by using the caller contract state. Therefore, a smart contract system can be upgraded and executed with other contracts (holding business logic/storage) as long as they point to the proxy contract of the system. There are several proxy-based upgradability methods such as the upgradable storage proxy method, and the standard methods mentioned above (EIP-897 method, EIP-1822 method, EIP-1967 method, and EIP-2535 method). Each of these proxy-based methods results in addressing some of the limitations of the previous one.

The upgradable storage proxy proposed in [215], consists of separating the storage to the business logic by making the storage act as a proxy to the logic contract. As shown in Figure 23, the smart contract system based on this method consists of a proxy contract that uses to store the data, and a logic contract that holds the system's business logic, both inheriting the same storage contract so that their storage references are aligned in the EVM. Thus, through this method, the smart contract system can be upgraded by replacing the Logic contract (hold business logic) with another contract. In addition, this method offers the possibility to update the storage as by design the Logic contract can make a change in the storage. However, the data storage structure cannot be upgraded because inheriting another storage contract in this context can lead to data layout collision due to the EVM design [216].

Figure 23 Proxy-based upgradability strategy

The EIP-897 is an improved version of the previous proxy method. To overcome the storage layout collision, this method is to make the other contracts (logic and storage) aware of the additional storage for the proxy contract [217]. This method suggests creating a particular Storage (i.e. ProxyStorage) only for the proxy, which inherits the proxy storage as well as a storage contract. For this method to work, all other contracts interacting with the contract system must inherit the proxy storage or at least avoid the storage slot reserved for specific variables such as the contract logic address.

Another way to avoid, storage collision is by using EIP-1822 [20] known as Universal Upgradeable Proxy Standard (UUPS). This method uses a pseudo-random storage slot to store the address of the actual contract (holding the business logic). The contract logic is stored on a fixed storage slot generated by a hash function “Keccak256” seeded with constant string value “Proxiable”-“Keccak256 (‘Proxiable’)” unlike the contract logic storage in the upgradable storage proxy and the EIP-897 methods where the storage slot is not explicit. The developer can generate his storage slot in which the logic contract will be stored and loaded. This method prevents another variable defined in the Proxy from using the same storage slot defined randomly for the logic contract (Business logic). Moreover, unlike the EIP-1822, the EIP-1967 is also used to upgrade the smart contract. This method suggests a standardization of the storage slot for the contract logic in the Proxy contract to avoid any storage collision. This method consists of using a fixed hashcode for storing the contract logic variable in the proxy contract[21].

Finally, unlike all the previous EIPs, that proxies a whole contract (business logic), the EIP-2535, allows upgrading a smart contract system by mapping contract logic functionality with a single address [22]. Based on the Diamond-facet contract [22], the smart contract system can gradually be upgraded by adding/removing/replacing functionality to the system. The Diamond acts as a proxy contract with external functions that are supplied by contract call facets. A facet is an independent contract with internal functions, states, and libraries that share with other contracts. Smart contracts can be updated by adding any functionality encapsulated within a facet whose address is mapped to a function selector into the diamond contract. Thus, when an external function is called on the Diamond, as this called function does not exist in the Diamond, the Diamond fallback function is executed to find in the mapping of function selector to facet, which facets contain the called function and thus execute the called function in the context of the identified facet using delegate call mechanism. A fallback function by design belongs to the Solidity smart contract and it is called when a non-existent function is called on the contract.

7.3 Methodology

This section reports the research methodology and the results of this chapter.

7.3.1 Research design and plan

Research goal: This research aims to characterize the effects of Ethereum’s standard upgradability methods on smart contract evolution. We will focus on the standard upgradability methods (EIP-897, EIP-1822, EIP-1967, and EIP-2535) used by the Ethereum blockchain community, and empirically analyze the effects of applying these standard upgradability standards on smart contract evolution.

As a result, we will analyze our dataset to answer the aforementioned research questions for this research. For each of these research questions, we will evaluate if the upgradability practices affect each measurement attribute of the smart contract.

- **For RQ3-1:** We primarily look at this question to identify and understand the transaction cost of the upgradability methods. There is no prior evidence or research about the cost of applying these upgradability practices, so this is

a characterization question, where we will empirically observe the cost of each upgradability practice and compare the results among them.

- **For RQ2-2:** Here, we assume that the 6th Lehman law (“Continuous growth”) provides an expectation on how the size of a smart contract will behave after consecutive deployments. We expect that, in general, the overall size of the different smart contracts in our sample will increase. We will analyze the line of code(LOC) of each smart contract version as a measure of size, then we will evaluate if there is a statistical difference between the upgradability practices that can explain potential differences in size.

Figure 24 Process for building the dataset

- **For RQ3-3:** Like in RQ3-2, for this research question, the 2nd Lehman law provides an expectation of how complexity will behave. We expect that, in general, the overall complexity of the different smart contracts in our sample will increase, while allowing for variations as the law predicts that effort can be invested into reducing complexity. To answer this question we use the McCabe complexity metric [180] as a measurement for smart contract complexity, and then we evaluate if there is a statistical difference between the upgradability practices that can explain potential differences in complexity.
- **For RQ3-4:** Like in the previous two questions, we look into the 7th Lehman’s Law (“Declining quality”) to provide an expectation on how security behaves. We are using security as a proxy for quality. We expect that, in general, the number of security incidents will increase with successive deployment of the smart contract. We will use the issue data of smart contracts from a static analysis tool(Slither[178]) to analyze the security of smart contracts. Then we will evaluate if there are statistically significant differences between the upgradability practices explaining potential differences in contract quality.

7.3.2 Obtaining the dataset for this research (instrumentation)

The transparency of Blockchain results that all smart contracts that have been deployed to Ethereum being available to be observed. Nonetheless, building a dataset that can be used for this research is not straightforward. This section describes the process used to build the dataset. The resulting dataset has been made available on GitHub. Figure 24 presents the process we followed for building our dataset.

- a) Identify the upgradability standards

We reviewed the literature to identify and collect the list of the upgradability standards used by Ethereum developers. To identify these upgradability standards we look at the Ethereum Improvement proposals (EIPs) which describe standards for the Ethereum platform [218].

We identified the standards shown in Table 25. Among these standards, the EIP-1538 has been withdrawn. Hence, standards EIP-1897, EIP-1822, EIP1-1967, and EIP-2535 were used for this study.

b) Identify smart contracts that use these standards

We used the Etherscan [219] and Bloxy [147] platforms to look for smart contracts in the Ethereum network that would show evidence of applying the standard upgradability practices. On both smart contract explorers, we look at the smart contract by searching specific “keywords” and “function and event” names described in Table 26.

c) Extract all versions of the identified upgraded smart contract

Transactions in the blockchain can be used to identify the “upgrade” action of a smart contract. This action is different in each of the standard practices. We used the Bloxy.io platform to inspect each contract and identify the upgrade action (see function/ method/event name in Table 26), and as a result, obtain the address of the “upgraded” smart contract. By repeating this action with each new uncovered contract, it is possible to retrace the relationship between the addresses in the Blockchain. Then, these can be grouped into the concept of a “smart contract project” which consists of the versions of a contract system and **will represent the unit of analysis of this study.**

d) Extract the source code for each version

This activity was done in parallel to the previous one. As mentioned in section 2.1.2 it is not the source code of a smart contract that gets stored in the blockchain but the bytecode. As a result, we refer to Etherscan to extract the source code of each address collected.

For consistency, we decided to include in our study only the smart contract projects for which we were able to obtain the source code for all upgrade versions in the project.

For upgradability practices EIP-897, EIP-1822, and EIP-2535 we reviewed all smart contract projects with more than three versions and included all projects with source code for all the versions in the sample. For EIP-1967, we did the same review but decided to include the first five smart contract projects that had more than three versions and had source code for all the versions. This result is summarized in Table 27.

Table 25 The standard upgradability practices provided by EIPs

Standard Upgradability practice (EIP)	Status
EIP-897: DelegateProxy	This EIP is not recommended for general use or implementation as it is likely to change.
EIP-1822: Universal Upgradeable Proxy Standard (UUPS)	This EIP had no activity for at least 6 months.
EIP-1967: Standard Proxy Storage Slots	This EIP is in the review stage. It is subject to changes and feedback is appreciated.
EIP-1538: Transparent Contract Standard	This EIP has been withdrawn.
EIP-2535: Diamonds, Multi-Facet Proxy	This EIP is in the last stage (call for review)

Table 26 Search filter items

Search item group	Search item
EIP name	EIP-897, EIP-1822, EIP-1967, and EIP-2535
Specific contract name	Proxy, diamond, proxy storage, facet,
Function/method name	upgradeTo, updateTo, updateImplementation, update, set implementation, implementation upgradeTo, updateCode, diamondCut
event name	update, upgrade, update code, diamond cut,

Table 27 Summary of the list of contacts using the standard upgraded methods

Method	Identified	With more than 3 versions	Included in the study
EIP-897	1525	92	5
EIP-1822	242	14	4
EIP-1967	2777	663	5
EIP-2535	62	24	4

Table 28 List of smart contracts implemented the standard upgradability methods

Method	Smart contract project	Number of versions
EIP-897	ACOO	5
	MINTABLE	5
	POLYGONE(MATIC)	6
	ROOTCHAIN	3
	STAKEMANAGER	6
EIP-1822	CATNIPV2	15
	CONNECTORPROXY	22
	EASY BIRD	23
	NYANFINANCE	11
EIP-1967	AMORFI	6
	LIQUIDITY DIVIDENTS PROTOCOL	10
	RIBBON	3
	TRUEFI	11
	REBASING LIQUIDITY:DELTA RLP TOKEN	4
EIP-2535	DERIVADEX	5
	MAGIC	6
	PREMIA	11
	POLYMORPH	5

Table 29 Attributes measurement and unit

Attribute	Measurement Tool	Unit
Transaction Cost	Bloxy	ether
Size	Solmet	Line of Code (Loc)
Complexity	Solmet	McCabe Cyclomatic Complexity (cc)
Security	Slither	Issues

In summary (Table 28), the resulting dataset contains **18 smart contract** software projects, grouped by the upgradability practices. This includes **157 different versions** and over **1198 unique smart contract files**.

e) Measure the smart contract project's attributes

To measure the attributes of interest (transaction cost, size complexity, and security) for this study, we set up a measurement environment, which consists of smart contract repositories (explorers)-Bloxy and Etherscan, a metric tool SolMet and a static analysis tool Slither. Table 29 summarizes the elements of this measurement environment and how these tools contribute to the dataset.

We collect the transaction cost for the upgrade of the contracts through Bloxy.io. Thus, for each contract by identifying the method for upgrading a version, we were able to get the transaction cost for each upgrade. The transaction cost for upgrading a new version is the cost of deploying a new version on Ethereum (that is the contract creation cost) added to the cost of setting this deployed contract as the new version of the smart contract project (that is the cost of using the upgrade method).

To achieve the size and complexity measurement, we firstly flattened each version source code of the smart contracts into a single file(see Appendix), and then we used SolMet to get their measures. For each version file of the smart contract resulting from the flattening, a SolMet script is executed to obtain the size and complexity measure of the version concerned.

To measure the security of each contract version we use Slither by passing the address of each contract version into Slither script. This is only possible for smart contracts whose source code is available in Etherscan.

The measures of transaction cost, size, complexity, and security of all the contract projects involved are available in ⁹.

7.3.3 Unit of Analysis rationale

In short, the unit of analysis is the smart contract project, for which we have an expectation of how it behaves given Lehman’s Laws. Each project in the sample (Table 28) has had several versions deployed to the Ethereum main network. And, except for transaction cost, we can turn to Lehman’s laws to provide an expectation of how the other attributes should behave. The next paragraph conveys the concepts and rationale for the definition of the unit of analysis.

A smart contract project is composed of the set of related smart contracts identified in the Blockchain. These relationships can be identified through the transactions in Etherscan. The term upgradability is used to name the standard upgradability practices in the blockchain smart contract.

This is consistent with the concepts of evolution and maintenance (see section 7.2.1), as the upgrade signals the moment, in which a smart contract version is replaced by a newer version. In Blockchain, immutability means that the previous version is not deleted, but is left forever in the ledger. Maintenance is then the set of actions that the project teams executed in between the upgrade events. As our data draws from the Blockchain (not the teams building the smart contracts), smart contract maintenance is not in the scope of this study. Finally, evolution is the observation of the behaviour of the smart contract project as measured at each upgrade point in our dataset. Thus, the unit of analysis for this study is the smart contract project understood as a logical organization of individual smart contracts which are all deployed (and related) in the Ethereum mainnet. Figure 25 synthesizes this discussion.

Figure 25 Unit analysis construct (relationship between evolution, maintenance, and upgrade.)

⁹ 10.17632/mzmj52gk25.1

Figure 26 Analysis of Transaction cost by Upgradability practice

Figure 27 Transaction cost of upgradability practice normalized by the size

7.4 Experimentation Results

RQ3-1: What is the transaction cost of implementing upgradability methods in a smart contract?

To answer this question, we first looked at the absolute costs of each of the upgradability practices within the scope of this study (see Figure 26). Though a visual inspection does not convey the possibility of differences between the upgradability practices, we proceeded with an ANOVA test to confirm. There were no statistically significant differences between the upgradability practices means in terms of transaction cost (as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(3) = 0.9, p = 0.455$)).

Analysis of cost normalized by size (LOC). Since transaction cost is related to the LOC size¹⁰ we repeat the analysis above by normalizing the transaction cost by LOC. A visual inspection of Figure 27 seems to suggest that EIP-1822 is more expensive and that EIP-2535 is cheaper than any other upgrade method. Thus, we proceed to the ANOVA to evaluate this difference. This analysis revealed that there was a statistical difference between the upgradability

¹⁰ Transaction cost is a function of Bytecode LOC not Solidity LOC.

practices means in terms of transaction cost when normalized by size (as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(3) = 4.387$, $p = 0.02$))

Answer to RQ3-1 The analysis of the transaction cost of the upgradability practices shows these practices can be differentiated in terms of the transaction cost. This differentiation is well perceived when considering the relationship between size and transaction cost. In this regard, EIP-1822 is expensive, and EIP-2535 is cheaper than any other standard practice. It is also striking the small variation observed in the EIP-2535 normalized transaction cost ($2.82E-04 \pm 5.24E-05$). We interpret this observation as empirical confirmation of the design intention of EIP-2535. Namely, to enable method-level upgradability in smart contracts.

RQ3-2: Does the size of smart contracts grow as new versions are deployed?

The expectation according to the sixth Lehman's law is that size will grow with the newer versions. To evaluate this, we apply a regression test to the dataset. Table 30 presents the results of this analysis. For most of the smart contract projects in our sample (15 out of 18), the hypothesis holds and the size grows with the versions of the project. Of those 15 smart contract projects, 10 of them present a linear correlation model with significant goodness of fit ($R^2 > 0.5$ and $p < 0.05$).

On the other hand, the Connector project shows a model that decreases in size with significant goodness of fit model ($R^2 = 0.725$ and $p < 0.01$).

Project DELTA has a slight negative slope with a model without significant goodness of fit. Visually inspecting the trend of DELTA (see *Appendix*), it can be seen the last version of the contract exerts an influence on the descendant slope. Similarly, the CaptiveNiv2 project presents a slight negative slope with a model without significant goodness of fit. This can be inspected visually as well (see *Appendix*) where versions 4 and 5 exert an influence on the angle of the slope.

The effect of the upgradability standard on the evolution of size

Regarding the effect of the upgradability methods on the trend of size, we run an ANOVA analysis on which the standard upgradability method is used as a factor and the slope coefficient as a measurement. We note that, to the best of our knowledge, there is no theory to explain why the upgradability method would have an influence on the size. Therefore, we expected this analysis to not reject the null hypothesis. We executed this analysis with all projects in our data and repeated the analysis with a sub-sample that included only the project with significant models. In both cases, the null hypothesis was not rejected (see Table 31) and we can affirm that, in our dataset, the upgradability standard practice has no influence on the trend of the size of a smart contract project.

Answer to RQ3-2: Our analysis allows us to identify that most of the smart contract project in our sample present a significant model where the size increase with each version. For our analysis, we interpreted size as the number of lines of code and used Lehman's sixth law to predict the behaviour of smart contract projects. From this viewpoint, the results are mostly consistent with the predictions of the law. Upgradability standards do not have a noticeable effect on size.

Thus, it is expected that the size of the contract project increases when a new version is deployed regardless of the standard practices used for managing upgradability.

Table 30 Regression test result of the testimonial series data of the contract for Size evolution

Upgradability standard	Contract	Slope coefficient	R-Square	P-value
EIP-897	ACCO	51.8	0.23	0.41
	MINTABLE	42.8	0.9	0.01
	POLYGONE	32.8	0.66	0.04
	ROOTCHAIN	53.5	0.75	0.33
	STAKEMANAGER	224	0.79	0.01
EIP-1967	AMORFI	44.9	0.78	0.01
	TRUEFI	40.6	0.39	0.03
	LIQUIDITY	43.95	0.49	0.02
	RIBBON FINANCE	26.5	0.75	0.33
	DELTA_REBASING_LIQUIDITY_TOKEN	-0.4	0.02	0.85
EIP-1822	CONNECTOR	-51.3	0.72	9.70E-07
	EASYBIRD	5.82	0.55	4.26E-05
	NYANFIANCE	10.6	0.58	3.75E-03
	CAPTIVENIV2	-3.75	0.04	0.44
EIP-2535	DERIVADEX	390.2	0.97	8E-04
	MAGIC	119.1	0.97	9.68E-06
	PREMIA	1901.2	0.84	0.013
	POLYMORPH	316.2	0.83	2E-03

Table 31 one-way ANOVA results (Upgradability practice on size trend)

Analysis	N	df	F	p-value
All projects	18	3	2.98	0.06
Only significant model	10	3	0.91	0.48

Figure 28 Expected variation of complexity under 2nd Lehman law

RQ3-3 Does the complexity of smart contracts grow as new versions are deployed?

Following the second Lehman’s law on software complexity, we expect that the complexity of a smart contract project grows as newer versions are deployed in the Blockchain. However, the second law includes a clause (“unless work is done to maintain or reduce it”) that must be considered in the analysis. Figure 28 shows the coquis of what we consider as the valid behaviour of complexity. Regular dips in complexity can be the results of “work done to reduce it”, while oscillations and overall decrease might signal behaviour that is not predicted by the law. From a statistical regression analysis point of view, this is challenging, as the visual inspection of the complexity trends of the project examples(see *Appendix*) is meant to show positive slopes with non-statistically significant goodness of fit, and yet one follows the law and the other does not. As a result, there is a degree of judgment in this analysis that will be drawn from the observing dataset.

Table 32 presents the result of the regression test applied to our dataset. This shows that most of the smart contract projects (15 out of 18) in this sample hold the hypothesis and that the complexity of the contract grows as new versions are deployed. From those 15 projects that hold the hypothesis, eight present a linear correlation model with significant goodness of fit ($R^2 > 0.5$ and $p < 0.05$).

Outstandingly, the **Connector** project presents a model with a goodness fit ($R^2 = 0.77716$ and $p < 0.05$) that decreases in complexity with each version.

The project **Amorfi** and **CaptiveNiv2** present a negative slope with a model without significant goodness of fit. By visually inspecting the Amorfi project (see *Appendix*), we observe that the complexity of the project increases until version 3 before being disturbed by version 4 where the complexity considerably decreases. Then this complexity stays quite stable from version 4 to 5 before getting increased on version 6. After observing the data, we cannot affirm that the complexity of this project decreased, however, we can observe that the complexity has been reduced through some versions (4 and 5) while it was initially growing, which may justify this slight negative slope. This case may translate the complexity clause of the Lehman law.

For the **Captiveniv2** slight negative slope, after visually inspecting the project (see *Appendix*), this slope seems to be caused by versions 4 and 5 which exert an influence on the angle of the slope.

Table 32 Regression test result of the testimonial series data of the contract for complexity evolution

Upgradability standard	Contract	Slope coefficient	R-Square	P-value
EIP-897	ACCO	0.91	0.91	0.01
	MINTABLE	0.60	0.89	0.01
	POLYGONE	0.16	0.43	0.16
	ROOTCHAIN	0.51	0.75	0.33
	STAKEMANAGER	1.38	0.77	0.02
EIP-1967	AMORFI	-0.26	0.16	0.43
	TRUEFI	1.79	0.79	2E-04
	LIQUIDITY	0.15	0.31	0.09
	RIBBON FINANCE	0.07	0.75	0.33
	DELTA_REBASING_LIQUIDITY_TOKEN	0.05	0.01	0.90
EIP-1822	CONNECTOR	-0.82	0.78	1.2E-07
	EASYBIRD	0.01	0.03	0.43
	NYANFIANCE	0.04	0.46	0.01
	CAPTIVENIV2	-0.82	0.07	0.33
EIP-2535	DERIVADEX	5.01	0.87	1.0E-03
	MAGIC	4.24	0.99	2.6E-06
	PREMIA	41.9	0.96	0.01
	POLYMORPH	8.66	0.88	0.001

Table 33 one-way ANOVA results (Upgradability practice on complexity trend)

Analysis	N	Df	F	p-value
All projects	18	3	3.19	0.05
Only significant model	8	2	0.97	0.44

The effect of the upgradability on the complexity evolution

Similar to the analysis provided for the size evolution, we run an ANOVA test to analyze the effect of the upgradability practices on the complexity trends. The upgradability standard practice is used as a factor and the slope coefficient for each contract as the measurement. In addition, to the best of our knowledge, there is no theory explaining that the upgradability standards have an influence on the complexity evolution. We executed this analysis

with all projects in our data and repeated it to a sub-sample including the project with significant models. However, this sub-sample does not contain any project of EIP-1882 as none of the sample projects under the EIP-1822 present a significant model. Table 33 presents the result of this analysis. In both cases, the result does not reject the null hypothesis. We can affirm the upgradability practices do not influence the complexity evolution in our dataset.

Answer to RQ3-3: For most of the projects in the dataset, the complexity increase with each version. This is consistent with the expectation of the second Lehman's law. Upgradability standards influence complexity. As a result, the complexity of a smart contract project increases as the project is maintained and new versions are deployed, regardless of the standard practices used to maintain it.

RQ3-4: Does the Security of smart contracts decline as new versions are deployed?

According to the seventh Lehman's law is that quality decreases with each new version. In this analysis, we are interpreting security issues as an indication of quality. Therefore, we expect that the number of issues of each project increase with each version as stated by the Lehman law. We will evaluate this following the linear regression analysis used in the previous questions.

Table 34 presents the result of the regression test applied to our dataset. It can be observed that 12 out of 18 smart contract project holds the expectation, with five projects presenting linear correlation models with a positive slope and with significant goodness of fit ($R^2 > 0.5$ and $p < 0.05$).

Three projects Connector, EasyBird, and CaptiveNiv2 present a negative slope with non-significant goodness of fit. Inspecting the trend for Connector (see *Appendix*), it can be observed that there is a steep decrease in security issues in the initial versions. For the EasyBird project (see *Appendix*), we can observe two major positive trend patterns where the number of issues increases. The first trend is that involving versions 1 to 5 and the second the version 6 to 20. The negative slight slope can be explained by a considerable difference in the number of issues between these two trends caused by version 6 where the issues have been considerably reduced. For the project CaptiveNiv2, versions 4 and 5 exert an influence on the angle of the slope (see *Appendix*).

Projects Polygone, DerivaDex, and Magic, present interesting cases as there is no variation in the values of the issues (the slope is equal to zero). In particular, the count of security issues for Polygone (see *Appendix*) is equal to zero across all its versions. We can observe that in these three projects the value of the issues is in the single digits. Though we cannot be sure, a plausible explanation is that the development project is using SolMet as an indicator for quality, which would explain the low values in this measurement and the remarkable constant slope.

The effect of the upgradability on the number of security issues

To see if there is any effect of the upgradability on security, we apply a similar ANOVA analysis executed for the size and complexity, of all projects and a sub-sample of the significant models. For the sub-sample, we also include the projects with a constant number of issues with each version.

There is also no theory explaining that the upgradability standards have an influence on the issue of evolution, so we expect that in the analysis we do not reject the null hypothesis.

Table 35 presents the result of this analysis. The results from this analysis do not reject the null hypothesis. We can affirm in our dataset that the security is not influenced by the standard upgradability practices.

Answer to RQ3-4: Our analysis allows us to identify that most of the smart contract projects in our sample present a significant linear regression model where the quality decreases with each new version. As mentioned, our analysis interprets quality as the number of security issues measured by SolMet. Interestingly, we found three projects with no variation in the number of issues across all of their versions. We conjectured that these projects have integrated the same security measures from SolMet in their development process.

Table 34 Regression test result of the testimonial series data of the contract for issue evolution

Upgradability standard	Contract	Slope Coefficient	R-Square	P-value
EIP-897	ACCO	7.1	0.74	0.06
	MINTABLE	1.8	0.75	0.05
	POLYGONE	0.0	1.0	-
	ROOTCHAIN	0.5	0.75	0.33
	STAKEMANAGER	12	0.79	0.01
EIP-1967	AMORFI	1.5	0.43	0.16
	TRUEFI	1.3	0.19	0.18
	LIQUIDITY	1.4	0.55	0.01
	RIBBON FINANCE	28	0.76	0.32
	DELTA_REBASING_LIQUIDITY_TOKEN	0.8	0.36	0.40
EIP-1822	CONNECTOR	-0.54	0.35	5E-03
	EASYBIRD	-0.09	6E-03	0.72
	NYANFINANCE	0.20	0.52	8E-03
	CAPTIVENIV2	-0.82	0.11	0.22
EIP-2535	DERIVADEX	0.0	1.0	-
	MAGIC	0.0	1.0	-
	PREMIA	44	0.77	0.02
	POLYMORPH	5.8	0.88	1E-03

Table 35 one-way ANOVA results (Upgradability practice on issue trend)

Analysis	N	df	F	p-value
All projects	18	2	0.78	0.14
Only significant model	8	3	0.18	0.91

Thus, to answer RQ3-4, the number of issues of the smart contract grows with each version, that is, the security of the smart contract declines with each version. This is consistent with the 7th Lehman's law. We affirm that this statement is true unless the development team is explicitly looking at security issues prior to deploying a version to the projects.

7.5 Threats of validity

In this section, we present the threats that can affect the result analysis of this chapter.

External validity: We conducted a case study based on multiple smart contracts aiming to present an evidence-based result that could be considered for all Ethereum smart contracts. However, the number of smart contracts used in this study does not allow us to determine the representativeness of all Ethereum smart contracts. Also, smart contracts in our sample were not randomly selected from Ethereum but were a result of a carefully crafted extraction process. With this process, we favoured, by design, construct validity over external validity. We believe that while this decision limits the statistical external validity, it will favour the transferability of our results as the sample projects in our dataset provide the real-world implementation of the EIPs under study.

Furthermore, our study scope includes the upgradability methods considered as standard methods by Ethereum. However, it cannot be known if these methods are used by most smart contracts in Ethereum, i.e we are not aware at the moment of a study or report about the adoption of the standard upgradability practices. As a result, there is no way to evaluate if the same is representative of Ethereum smart contract projects.

Construct Validity: As we mentioned, we favoured a high validity of the construct. However, some issues still challenge the validity of our construct. On the one hand, we decided to include in our sample smart contract project at least three versions. As three points would enable the analysis presented in this paper. At the same time, we are aware of the limitations of analyzing trends with just three points. Nonetheless, our sample includes also projects with a high number of versions spread throughout a long period (1 year, 2 years). On the other hand, the processes for building

the dataset leads us to remove the projects that did not fit our criteria. In particular smart contracts projects where at least one version did not provide source code for analysis. We debated whether to include these and accept the missing data threat in the analysis, and again decided to have a consistent dataset where all variables under scope could be measured for all data points.

Internal validity: Regarding the sixth Lehman law, which we used to guide the analysis of RQ3-2, the law references functional growth, while we interpret it to relate to the size attribute as measured by lines of code. These two concepts are not the same and can introduce an internal validity threat if the answers to our research questions are taken out of the context of this study.

Conclusion validity: We took care with the application of the statistical methods (ANOVA and linear regression) and how they were used to support our conclusions. Our measurement procedures are reliable as they are guided by tools, so all data points are measured equally (i.e. there are no Type II errors). The one source of potential Type II error is during our classification/assignment of the smart contract project to a standard applicability method. This process is explained as part of the dataset-building process (section 7.3.1), nonetheless, we believe this is an unlikely event given the review and diligence put into identifying and classifying the smart contract projects to assure the internal reliability of the construct of our dataset.

7.6 Discussion

This section presents a few discussion points stemming from our results.

EIP-2535 is the most cost-effective of the upgradeability standards: As shown in our answer to RQ3-1, EIP-2535 is considerably cheaper than the other three standard upgradeability methods. This empirical result is consistent with the intention of the authors of the standard, as this standard enables the deployment of new versions of individual methods. While this standard adds complexity to the design of smart contracts, in terms of transaction cost, this is paid in that it provides the capacity for incremental development and deployment into a Blockchain.

This is an actionable result for practitioners looking to optimize the cost of maintaining the contract by selecting to implement this standard.

Lehman's laws also describe the behaviour of evolving smart contract software when applying the standard upgradeability practices: This study allowed us to investigate the characteristics of the standard upgradeability methods used for upgrading the smart contract, on the size, complexity, and security of smart contract projects. The result of this study shows that for most of the smart contract projects involved in this study, the 2nd (Increasing complexity), 6th (continuing growth), and 7th (declining quality) Lehman laws can still be used to predict the behaviour of evolving smart contracts

- **Considering the 6th Lehman law:**

The cost development life cycle of the smart contract project may be more expensive than that of a traditional software project. A study [48] shows that the size of a smart contract has an impact on the smart contract cost as the number of statements(NOS) that is a component of SLOC(Source line of code) and the gas consumption are significantly correlated. That is, the higher the smart contract size, the higher the smart contract cost will be. Although traditional software evolution presents also costs, the smart contract evolution may be more expensive, as this cost is based on the execution of the source of code of the contract.

From the practitioner's perspective, this insight is practical as it affects the decision-making of maintaining a smart contract. For example, this result may deter the practitioners to conduct perfective maintenance. Unlike traditional

Table 36 Evidence-based contributions of this work to the state of the art (Laws (✓ partially verified)

System Type	Lehman's laws							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Smart contract	N/A	✓	N/A	N/A	N/A	✓	✓	N/A

software where software versions are released with new functionalities based on new or changed customer requirements (functional requirements), this may be hardened to implement with the smart contracts given the smart contract cost will significantly increase by using upgradability practices requiring to fully redeploy the updated main contract. From this conjecture, we claim for appropriate maintenance of smart contracts, the practitioners should refer to the contracts based on suitable upgradability practices (i.e EIP-3222) instead of upgradability practices needing to deploy the whole main contract.

The practitioner should be aware that the maintenance of smart contracts by using the standard upgradability practices in the long term might be very expensive, and that they should make a real effort during smart contract development to minimize deployments to the Blockchain.

- Considering the 7th law:

We interpreted quality as a security issue, and our result has important financial implications. In general, smart contracts will manage assets. The implication of the declining quality law means that as smart contracts are upgraded their quality will decline and as a result, they will be more attractive to be the target of attacks [220]. Considering this, It is crucial for the Ethereum community to turn over more sophisticated security solutions to reinforce smart contract security as the current security solution (mostly related to security analysis tools) may not be effective to deal with this declining security evolution of the smart contract. Referring to the evidence provided in Chapter 6, we, therefore, invite practitioners to take a closer look at the metric of their source to guide the deployment decision.

In summary, we contribute with the following evidence-based knowledge to the state of the art in the studies related to Lehman's laws (see Table 36).

While the data in the Blockchain is transparent, converting the data into a research dataset is not trivial: The transparency of the Blockchain may suggest that information is available from it. The data is available for all network participants (including observers). Tools like Etherscan or Bloxy facilitate the navigation through the ledger and its transactions. However, from a research perspective, making sense of the data so that it can be questioned requires human intervention (as we tried to objectively convey in section 7.3.1-*Obtaining the dataset for this research (instrumentation)*). In particular, for our research objectives, the main challenge was the availability of the contract source code. In short, we believe that a public Blockchain like Ethereum can be an interesting source for research data and that tools must evolve to support research initiatives like the one presented in this chapter.

7.7 Chapter summary

The Ethereum upgradability practices provide a workaround for Blockchain immutability. These practices are key enablers for the smart contract ecosystem, as they allow for their maintenance and evolution. Software maintenance is a key activity for the deployment of software systems as it allows for the software to remain valuable with changing

requirements. And while immutability is a desired feature in smart contracts, the idea of developing software without a mechanism that allows for its modifications after it has been deployed is not an enticing idea for developers.

This study presented the characterization of Ethereum standard upgradability practices (EIP-897, EIP-1822, EIP-1967, and EIP-2535). We created a dataset for observing the effects of these practices by importing smart contracts that have been deployed to the main Ethereum Blockchain. As a result, we created a dataset that groups 1198 unique smart contracts into 18 smart contract projects (a total of 157 different versions) grouped into the aforementioned four standard upgradability practices.

Our results are of immediate transferability for the smart contract development community. First, we found that EIP-2535 is the cheapest alternative (when measuring transaction cost). EIP-2535 was designed to enable the upgrade of the individual method of a smart contract, and our results experimentally confirm this intention and show its effects on limiting the transaction cost of new versions.

On the other hand, from a theory perspective, we looked at Lehman's laws and studied if their statements were still valid in the context of smart contracts being developed and maintained using standard upgradability practices. Our results show that, in general, laws 2nd (Increasing complexity), 6th (continuing growth), and 7th (declining quality) are supported in the smart contract context. For the declining quality law, in the context of smart contracts, it is noteworthy to highlight that the effects of poor quality have a direct impact on the potential of financial loss, as smart contracts are software entities that are built to manage assets.

Chapter 8. : A framework for effective smart contract development life cycle

This chapter presents a framework for supporting smart contract contracts. It provides information on the development of a framework which aims to support the development of secure cost-effective smart contracts. This chapter is therefore organised as follows: Section 8.1 provides an introduction to the chapter. Section 8.2 presents the development of the framework mentioned above. Section 8.3 presents an example of the implementation of the developed framework for smart contract security development. Finally, section 8.4 provides a conclusion to this chapter

8.1 Introduction

In light of the result presented in the previous chapter regarding the smart contract security development issue from the literature and the alternative security solution investigations carried through the Chapter 5,Chapter 6, Chapter 7, this chapter aims to provide a comprehensive solution-based framework to support the smart contract security development.

Our intention in carrying out this research study is to help practitioners to strengthen the development of security as well as optimize the cost of the smart contract. Although many security-oriented solutions exist to support smart contract security, they are not enough effective to support secure smart contract development. Here, we are proposing a comprehensive Secure cost-effective smart contract development life cycle framework(SCESMDF) by following the process presented in Figure 29 to support the smart contract development. This framework is the result of 3 years of research (Chapter 5, Chapter 6,Chapter 7) where we looked at security programming practices and maintenance approaches to support the development of secure smart contracts while optimizing their cost. As shown in Figure 29, SCESMDF is based on 4 foundations(see Table 37) derived from factors of the security and cost-effectiveness of smart contracts identified through our empirical research studies(Chapter 5, Chapter 6, and Chapter 7). These studies (Chapter 5, Chapter 6, Chapter 7) allow us to identify the following facts which represent for us the factors of the development of a secure and cost-effective secure smart contract:

Figure 29:Process used for building the Framework SCESMDF

- The similarity presented by both smart contracts and traditional software at a certain level must be taken as an advantage for exploring more security programming practices from traditional computing into smart contracts as according to the result in the Chapter 5, most of the security code programming practices empirically identified are applicable to smart contracts, because their constructs are also represented in the smart context domain; better as shown the result in Chapter 5 their implementation cost seems to be not significant. [F1]
- Referring to the results of the Chapter 6 on the applicability and reliability of metrics, the advantage of the applicability and reliability of security code metrics in smart contracts must be taken to explore more security code metrics from traditional computing into smart contracts and combined them with other metrics and other security solutions to reinforce the development of the smart contract [F2].
- Practitioners who look to optimize the cost of contract maintenance should prioritize the EIP-2535 for smart contract upgradability because its implementation is less expansive as shown in the result of the Chapter 7. [F3]
- The result of the application of the 6th law in the smart contract is interesting as it provides information on how the smart contract development must be carried out before deployment. In fact, the results of the Chapter 7 show that smart contract is in line with 6th Lehman law. So Therefore let suggest the practitioner should optimize the size of their smart contract in order to reduce the cost which compared to traditional software may be more expensive if action to reduce code is considered [F4].
- The developer should take the advantage of the security programming practices, and security metrics associated with other existing solutions to rigorously and continuously implement and evaluate the security of smart contracts because as shown in the results of the Chapter 7 the smart contract is in line with the 7th law of Lehman[F5]

In the following section, we present this framework in more detail by describing its foundations, its implementation and an example supporting its application.

8.2 Secure cost-effective smart contract development life cycle framework(SCESMDF)

Building on top of the factors mentioned above, we elaborated 4 foundations that we consider following our previous research results, as the underlying basis of the development of the secure and cost-effective smart contract life cycle. Table 37 below shows these foundations, mapping with the factors identified in the above discussion.

Figure 30 presents the security cost-effective smart contract development framework. This framework is built upon the foundations described above. Our proposed framework consists of a list of activities spread along with the software development life cycle phases. These activities are focused on the improvement of the security and cost of smart contract development. We note that these activities are suggested to be adapted on top of the normal development activities in each phase of the SDLC.

8.2.1 Requirement phase

Guidelines

G1: Identify and analyse all the security requirements of the smart contract.

Table 37 The foundations of the secure and cost-effective smart contract development life cycle

Foundation number	Foundation	Factors	Factor details
Fo_1	Adoption of security programming practices and patterns	F1	Programming practices and patterns are largely available for smart contract security and their cost implementation is not significant
Fo_2	Adoption of security metrics	F2	Security code metrics are largely available and are reliable to the smart contract security
Fo_3	Prioritize cost-effective upgradability standards for maintenance	F3	Upgradability practices support smart contract maintenance and the cost of implementation of the upgradability practices is different
Fo_4	Adoption of continuous and rigorous security implementation during maintenance	F3, F4, F5	Security tends to decline over time, and size tends to increase over time

Figure 30 Secure cost-effective smart contract development life cycle framework(SCESMDF)

G2: Be aware of the contract transaction cost and prioritize the security requirements for which the transaction costs can be afforded.

Explanation

G1: In the context of developing a secure cost-effective smart contract, similarly to traditional software, this phase consists of analyzing the identified smart contract requirements, all the security considerations, and identifying all the requirements need to allow the smart contract to be reliable, resilient and recoverable.

G2:Practitioners should also be aware of the cost when defining the security requirements as the smart contract domain involves costs that rely upon the computation, which cost it shares between user and owner. The practitioners should always plan to prioritize the security requirement which security level and cost can be afforded by both owner and customer

8.2.2 Design phase

Guideline

G3: Identify the vulnerabilities issue from the security requirements and the possible security programming practices and patterns able to mitigate them.

G4: Be aware of the cost of the implementation of security programming practices and patterns identified.

G5: Integrate the upgradability standards to the smart contract design and be aware of the cost of this design by prioritizing the EIP-2535.

Explanation

G3: This stage is for the practitioners to identify the security vulnerabilities that match the security requirements defined in the requirement phase. For the security vulnerabilities, practitioners can rely on the existing standards and classifications of the vulnerabilities for the smart contracts to match all vulnerabilities associated with the security requirements determined in this phase. Then from the security vulnerabilities, the practitioners should apply the security means in order to tackle these vulnerabilities. The Framework suggests prioritizing as security means, the security programming practices and patterns. For each identified vulnerability, the practitioners should identify all the possible security patterns and practices that can be applied. Beyond the limited list of security practices and patterns existing for smart contracts, the practitioner may include security practices and patterns from traditional software after verifying that those are well applicable to the smart contract.

G4: Also, practitioners should be aware of the cost that these practices and patterns may imply, although the results of Chapter 5 reveal that their costs are not significant. That's, it is recommended at this stage to affect for each practice or pattern a cost which will be determined in the implementation phase and later use for decision making during the deployment.

G5: In addition to G3 and G4, in order to deal with the cost that smart contracts development can implied relatively to the Blockchain immutability that requires the development and deployment of a whole new smart contract, the framework suggests at this stage that the practitioners include/use upgradability standard practices instead of creating new contract whenever a new version needs to be deployed. This will reduce the cost of maintenance as these methods do not imply fully developing and deploying a new contract. Moreover, at this stage, the practitioner must be aware of the cost that the implementation of an upgradability method may involve and that the cost varies from the upgradability methods. The results of Chapter 7 prove that among these standards' upgradability practices, EIP 2535 is cheap than the rest. Although this EIP-2535 implementation can be complex compared to the other, here (framework) it is currently recommended to use EIP-2535 in order to reduce the cost of maintenance.

8.2.3 Implementation phase

Guideline

G6: Implement the selected EIP upgradability standard pattern from the design (preferably EIP-2535) to the smart contract program.

G7: Implement the security programming practices and patterns identified from the design phase.

Explanation

G6: In this phase, the framework suggests coding the smart contract architecture with respect to an EIP upgradability standard pattern preferably the EIP-2535. This will allow practitioners to efficiently maintain the developing smart contract.

G7: Beside **G6**, the security practices and patterns produced during the Design stage are also coded (implemented) here. This stage is crucial as the non-implementation, or the wrong implementation of the security patterns and practices may bias the decision-making of the smart contract deployment. Therefore, it is highly recommended to rigorously follow the description of the practices and patterns implementation when implementing them into the smart contracts.

8.2.4 Testing phase

Guidelines

G8: Apply both static analysis tools and automated security metrics to measure the security level of smart contracts by applying security patterns and practices. And also identify the costs associated with the security programming practices implemented.

Explanation

This phase aims to evaluate the security level of the security means applied to smart contracts. Here, the static analysis tools and security metrics must be used. Here (framework), the static analysis tool is used as a first layer to evaluate the security by identifying any security vulnerabilities of the developing smart contract. Given the static analysis tools may present weaknesses such as false negative/false-positive results, the framework suggests using the security metrics as a second layer to measure the security level to confront the static analysis tools' results, and therefore evaluate the security level of the developing smart contracts. The results from Chapter 6 reveal that security metrics from traditional computing can be applicable to the smart contract context. Therefore, here we highly recommended that the practitioners refer to those metrics and get the advantage offered by the similarity between smart contracts and traditional software domain, to explore and evaluate the applicability of the traditional software metrics and implement them into smart contracts. For efficiency, the framework suggests the practitioners automate or use automated security metrics when measuring the security level, because as shown in the result of Chapter 7 most of the existing metrics are not automated in the smart contract domain, involving thus more labour and time.

Besides, at this stage, the framework requires measuring all costs related to the implementation of the security programming practices and patterns selected. As the aim of this framework is to provide a suitable security-cost effective implementation for the developing contract, identifying the cost associated with implemented security practices and patterns will be used in the next phase (deployment) to analyse the tradeoff of the security and cost involved. This cost refers to the transaction cost when deploying and interacting with the smart contract methods. The practitioner should therefore set up a Blockchain platform testnet from which it will deploy the contract and identify the transaction cost of implemented security programming practices and patterns through the deployed contract's methods.

8.2.5 Deployment phase

Guidelines

G9: Compare tradeoff security-cost of the possible security programming practices/pattern applied for a specific security requirement and deploy one with optimal security and cost.

Explanation

This stage consists to evaluate the results of the security and cost activities performed from both Implementation, and testing phases. Here, the practitioners are required to compare the couple (security, cost) of security practices/patterns applied for a specific security requirement. It consists to decide whether refine the security practices/patterns selection for this specific requirement or move them to the deployment. Given the security-cost, trade-off decision may depend on each business, and practitioner, it is hard to provide a standard security-cost trade-off used as a threshold for contract deployment. However, inanimately the practitioners should deploy implementation instances where **security is higher, the cost is cheaper and the security is proportional to the security cost.**

8.2.6 Maintenance phase

Guideline

G10: Rigorously and continuously apply the guidelines from the design to the deployment of our framework for each new smart contract update.

Explanation

The results of our research study revealed, that the quality of the smart contract tends to deteriorate, and the cost through the contract size tends to increase over time if no serious action has been taken. Therefore, at this phase, the framework recommends to practitioners after implementing one of the upgradability practices(preferably EIP-2535) for the contract maintenance, to rigorously and continuously perform the activities of this framework for any new version of the smart contract(or part of the contract) that need to be deployed. Neglecting these activities for the versions of the contract will likely lead to the quality declining of the smart over time and therefore exposing easily the smart contracts to attacks. This stage suggests as well the user prioritize the versions with optimal size in order to avoid an exponential increase in the cost of the contract over time.

8.3 Example of the application of the proposed framework.

This section provides an example of the application of our proposed framework. In this example, we will use our framework to carry out the development of a smart contract project implemented by one of the honour students at the University of the West of Scotland. This project has already been implemented before releasing this framework. However, we try to show here how conducting this project with our framework may lead to a more secure-cost effective contract. In this example, we will just focus on one of the security requirements of the project.

The project is an escrow contract developed under the Ethereum Layer Optimistic, implemented in the Freelance domain where the freelancers provide service to clients in exchange for remuneration. This project also involves a third party the presence is to solve disputes between freelancers and clients. Some of the project requirements as shown in Table 38.

8.3.1 Requirement stage

Regarding the software requirement mentioned above (Table 38):

Table 38 List of software requirements of the smart contract escrow project

No	System Requirement
1	Make a payment for a freelance service
2	Approve service after completion
3	Raise dispute to a third-party arbiter
4	Handling a dispute
5	Manage to list

Figure 31 Mapping of the software requirement with software security requirement in SCESMDF

G1- The framework suggests at this stage identifying the possible security requirement associated with these requirements. Considering the two first requirements of the smart contract project, a possible security requirement is to limit the ether amount as here the software deal with the ether transfers. Figure 31 below shows what has been described above by matching the software requirement and the software security requirement.

G2-The Practitioner also is required to be aware of the cost that dealing with this identified security requirement may involve.

8.3.2 Design Stage

At this stage, the framework suggests that the practitioners identify all possible vulnerabilities deriving from the security requirement identified in the requirement stage.

G3- Considering the security requirement for this project which required limiting the amount of ether, a possible vulnerability can be that the presence of a bug may lock the ether transfer to the escrow contract. Another vulnerability that is required to limit the amount of the transfer may be reentrancy attacks caused by the wrong implementation of code by the developer. Therefore, as suggested by the Framework, the Practitioners should match the security requirements with their security vulnerabilities as shown in Figure 32 below.

After identifying the security vulnerabilities, the framework suggests the user identity for each security vulnerability, and the possible security programming practices which can be used to tackle the vulnerabilities. Considering the vulnerability mentioning that Platform can present a bug that locks the amount in the contract, this can be tackled by Rate Limit or balance limit programming practices as shown in Figure 32 below. The Rate limit regulates the frequency at which a task can be executed within a period, to limit the number of transactions performed by a smart contract. Applying this to the escrow contract may avoid the contract user from sending more ether to the escrow contract and therefore provide the time for the developer to take proactive actions. The balance limit limits the amount of ether held by the smart contract. This practice can therefore prevent the client/ freelancer to have important amounts

locked in the escrow contract. For each selected Security practice/pattern a security variable should be defined which value will be determined during the testing phase to assign the security level of security implementation instances.

Figure 32 Mapping of software requirements with software security vulnerabilities in SCESMDF

G4- At this stage, the practitioners should also be aware of the cost that the security programming practices and patterns may involve. The goal of this framework although it consists to improve the security of the contract this goal also includes the reduction of the cost. Therefore, in this project, the practitioner should define the cost variable for each security programming practice identified here(see Figure 33), which value will be determined during the testing stage.

Figure 33 Mapping of security vulnerabilities to the security programming practices and patterns in SCESMDF

8.3.3 Implementation stage

In the implementation stage, the security programming practices and patterns associated with the security requirement will be implemented. An example of the implementation of the security practices associated with the ‘platform can have a bug that may lock the amount of ether in the contract’ is provided here.

G6-Here, the practitioner should implement the EIP-2535 for the smart contract architecture.

G7-For this project, the practitioners should implement the Rate limit and balance limit following rigorously their implementation description to avoid biases during the decision-making in the Deployment stage. A possible combination of the implementation of both practices can also be applied by the practitioners as we did in this project. The following Figures present an implementation of these security practices.

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: UNLICENSED  
pragma solidity ^0.8.0;  
contract Escrow {  
    address payable public client;  
    address payable public freelancer;  
    address payable public arbiter;  
    function deposit(uint256 amount) public payable{  
        require(msg.value == amount);  
        // nothing else to do!  
    }  
    .....  
}
```

Figure 34: Original source code of the Freelance escrow(Partial code-full source code is available in *Thesis_Implementation_Rate_Limit_to_Contract/original_freelance_escrow* at *main · ndaangekevin/Thesis_Implementation_Rate_Limit_to_Contract (github.com)*)

```

// SPDX-License-Identifier: UNLICENSED

pragma solidity ^0.8.0;

contract Escrow {

    address payable public client;

    address payable public freelancer;

    address payable public arbiter;

    //Implementation of the balance limit to the function deposit

    function deposit(uint256 amount) public payable limitedPayable {

        require(msg.value == amount);

        // nothing else to do!

    }

    //balance limit code

    modifier limitedPayable() {

        require(address(this).balance <=50 ether);

        _;

    }

    .....

```

Figure 35 Source code of the implementation of the balance limit to the freelance escrow (full source code is available in [Thesis_Implementation_Rate_Limit_to_Contract/Balance_Limit_Escrow_Contract](#) at [main · ndaangekevin/Thesis_Implementation_Rate_Limit](#))

```

// SPDX-License-Identifier: UNLICENSED

pragma solidity ^0.8.0;

contract Escrow {

address payable public client;

address payable public freelancer;

address payable public arbiter;

//Implementation of the rate limit to the function deposit

function deposit(uint256 amount) public payable enableEvery(1 minutes){

require(msg.value == amount);

// nothing else to do!

}

//rate limit

uint enabledAt = block.timestamp;

modifier enabledEvery(uint t) {

    require (block.timestamp >= enabledAt);

    enabledAt = block.timestamp + t;

    _;

}

.....

}

```

Figure 36 Source code of the implementation of the Rate Limit to the Freelance escrow(full source code is available in Thesis_Implementation_Rate_Limit_to_Contract/Rate_limit_Frelance_escrow at main · ndaangekevin/Thesis_Implementation_Rate_Limit_to_Contract (github.com))

```

// SPDX-License-Identifier: UNLICENSED

pragma solidity ^0.8.0;

contract Escrow {

address payable public client;

address payable public freelancer;

address payable public arbiter;

//Implementation of the rate limit to the function deposit

function deposit(uint256 amount) public payable limitedPayable
enableEvery(1 minutes){

require(msg.value == amount);

// nothing else to do!

}

//balance limit code

modifier limitedPayable() {

require(address(this).balance <=50 ether);

┌;

}

//rate limit

uint enabledAt = block.timestamp;

modifier enabledEvery(uint t) {

require (block.timestamp >= enabledAt);

enabledAt = block.timestamp + t;

┌;

}

.....

}

```

Figure 37 Source code of the implementation of both Rate Limit and Balance limit to the Freelance escrow(full source code is available in . Thesis_Implementation_Rate_Limit_to_Contract/mix-pattern at main · ndaangevin/Thesis_Implementation_Rate_Limit_to_Contrat

8.3.1 Testing stage

At this stage, the framework suggests that the user identify the security level and the cost of the smart contract when implementing the security practices and patterns.

G8-Here, for the implemented code with the security pattern/practices from the implementation phase, we assess both security level and cost. The security level will be assessed firstly through a security code analysis, and then through security metrics to measure the security level. For the cost, we assess using Remix (Ethereum online testnet). Therefore the security level value and the cost value of the implementation of “balance limit”, “Rate limit” and “balance & limit” are measured and recorded as shown in Figure 38 and Table 39.

Figure 38 Mapping of security vulnerabilities to the security programming practices and patterns associated with their security level and their cost in SCESMDF

Table 39 Summary of the security level and deployment cost value of the possible security practices implementation for 'platform can have a bug that may lock the amount of ether in the contract' vulnerabilities

Solidity File	SECURITY					Security Value(Mean)	COST Cost value(WEI)
	WMC	DIT	CBO	Avg. McCC	Slither security value		
Rate_limit	0	0	0	0	(low:2, Med:0, High:0)	(0+0+0+0+2+0+0)=0.3	507554
Balance_limit	0	0	0	0	(low:2, Med:0, High:0)	(0+0+0+0+2+0+0)=0.3	458672
Rate_Limit &Balance_Limit	0	0	0	0	(low:2, Med:0, High:0)	(0+0+0+0+2+0+0)=0.3	517010

8.3.2 Deployment stage

After obtaining the cost, and security level of each security practice/pattern implementation for a specific security vulnerability, the developers should select the suitable security implementation.

G9-The form below summarises the result score of security and the cost of security practices or patterns implemented to respond to a security vulnerability. This form serves to evaluate and record the selected security programming practice or pattern for a given security vulnerability identified in a contract project. This form can be used as a standard for any project implementing our framework. In this testimonial project, we can observe that the security level value

for the 3 security implementation instances does not vary 'from **0.3**' and this value seems to be similar to the value of 0.3 of security of level the original code. However here it is not really the case. Unlike the original contract, the implemented security programming practices add constraints to the contract execution which is a benefit to the smart contract as it avoids more damage in case of attacks. Therefore the security level of these implementations is quite higher than the original code. In this case, to describe this difference we add '+' to the security value of the security implementation getting from both the security metric and static tool. (i.e 0.3 + for Rate Limit against 0.3 for original code as shown in Table 40).

As the security levels of 3 security programming practices have the same value (0.3+), therefore here the choice of the selection will be based on the cost. The business that aims to optimise the cost, can therefore refer to the security implementation instance with less cost, which is in this example the 'balance limit' implementation instance whose cost value is 458672 WEI against **507554 WEI for Rae limit and 517010 WEI for both security practice implementation.**

Table 40 A result score form for decision making in SCESMDF

Security vulnerability: The platform can have a bug which locks the amount in the contract		
Security practices or patterns:		
Rate Limit		
Balance Limit		
Original code without security implementation		
Implementation	Security	Cost
Original code	0.3	449234
Security practices implementation		
Implementation	Security	Cost
Rate Limit	0.3 +	507554
Balance Limit	0.3 +	458672
Rate limit & Balance Limit	0.3 +	517010
Security implementation decision		
Balance Limit		

In sum, by following the framework guidelines, unlike its original code from the student honour project, the escrow contract gains the benefit to limit the damage of the 'platform can have a bug that may lock the amount of ether in the contract' vulnerabilities' by implementing Balance limit instance which cost was cheaper compared to the other alternative providing the same level of security.

8.3.3 Maintenance stage

In this stage, the framework suggests to the developer to rigorously implement the activities from the requirement stage to the deployment stage for any new version of the contract that will be deployed. However, this project did not reach the maintenance stage.

8.4 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, we presented the framework used to build and maintain secure and cost-effective smart contracts. The proposed framework is based on 4 foundations derived from an investigation of existing security artefacts from the traditional software in the context of the smart contract. The framework activities are applied at each stage of the

software development life cycle and they are focused on security programming practices and patterns implementation from which security level and cost are identified, compared, and selected. The use of this framework has been provided through an example of smart contract project development to facilitate its implementation for any smart contract project.

Chapter 9. Conclusion

In this chapter, we outline the main contributions of this thesis and present future work.

9.1 Contribution to the current state of the art of Blockchain domain

In this thesis, we have presented a comprehensive framework to support the secure cost-effective smart contract development life cycle. Towards, achieving this goal, we have addressed the following:

Application of security programming practices and patterns from non-blockchain to securing smart contracts: We investigated from non-blockchain software environment, security programming practices and patterns for securing smart contracts. As a result, we extended the security practices and patterns from the literature [142][143] by identifying security programming practices and patterns from non-blockchain which are applicable to smart contracts. This has been empirically investigated through case studies and systematic judgment. This evidence of the applicability of the security programming practices and patterns from non-blockchain software constitutes a large resource of security solutions for practitioners to avoid adding vulnerabilities during smart contract development. Given the number of catalogues and guidelines existing for the security programming practices and patterns from the non-Blockchain software, we advise practitioners to explore them to enhance the security aspect of the smart contract

Characterisation of the transaction cost of the implementation of secure programming practices and patterns into smart contracts: We investigated the cost of implementing security programming practices and patterns into smart contracts. This investigation has been conducted using a case study and its result significance is supported by statistical methods. The results show that the implementation of security programming practices and patterns is not significant. The direct implication of this result is that the affordable cost of the security programming practices and patterns may not deter practitioners to implement the security programming practices and patterns.

Application of security metrics in smart contracts: We investigated from the non-blockchain software, the applicability of security metrics for the smart contract. We provided security metrics from non-blockchain software which can be used for measuring smart contracts security. We supported this evidence through a case study involving laboratory contracts and Ethereum real-world contracts, and statistical analyses. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first security metric for smart contract study with supporting empirical evidence. The application of existing security metrics from non-Blockchain into smart contracts should incentivise the use of security metrics from a practitioner who, after applying other security solutions (i.e security practices) looks to get confident in the security level of their smart contract de before deployment.

Characterisation of the cost of the upgradability standards implementation in smart contracts. We investigated and provided the characteristics of cost of the upgradability standards implementation for smart contracts. We demonstrated the characterisation using a case study involving a list of real-world contracts from Ethereum and supporting the result with statistical methods. This investigation revealed that among the four upgradability standards, the EIP-2535 cost is not significant. Therefore, from the business perspective, the implementation of the EIP-2535 should be used to maintain the smart contract as its cost is affordable compared to the other upgradability standards.

Empirical evaluation of the Lehman's laws for smart contracts: Lehman's laws have been used as a reference to explain the evolutionary behaviour of software development. However, to the best of my knowledge, this thesis is the first study evaluating Lehman's laws for a smart contract. This has been supported through a case study involving real-world contracts with all the contract versions and results supported with statistical analysis. From the 2nd, 6th, and 7th lehman's laws including the investigation revealed that smart a smart contract using upgradability standards is in line with Lehman's laws. The direct implication of this result is the practitioners have to be aware of constraints related to smart contract maintenance using the upgradability standards as according to Lehman's laws and our thesis results, the size of the smart contract grows, which can affect the smart contract cost. Smart contracts tend to become complex, and smart contract security tends to decline. We, therefore, recommend taking necessary action in order to tackle the behaviours linked to software evolution

A comprehensive framework for a secure and cost-effective smart contract life cycle.: From the insights derived from our previous contributions, we designed and implement a comprehensive guideline-based framework to support the development of secure cost-effective smart contracts. We, therefore, encourage developer, business, and practitioner who looks to empower their businesses with smart contracts, to use the proposed framework in this thesis as this framework solve both the problem of the security and cost budget for the smart contracts.

9.2 Future research lines

We now provide the future research lines that stem from the results of the research presented in this dissertation.

More Security programming practices and pattern applicability: The number of security programming practices and patterns investigated and applicable in this thesis is 30 from which 17 security has been implemented. Given the important number of security programming security practices and patterns from non-blockchain, an extended exploration of other security programming practices and patterns should be conducted in order to provide a more large security resource and significant evidence of the applicability of the security programming practices and patterns by implementing more of them.

More automated security metrics for smart contract: The number of security metrics identified applicable for the smart contract in this thesis is 15, which is less compared to the existing number of security metrics from the non-Blockchain. Moreover, only four of these metrics are currently automated for smart contracts. and just two automated metrics which are related to security. There is a need of investigating more security metrics to extend the existing ones mentioned in this thesis as currently only 2 metrics can be used as automated security metrics for smart contracts. A possible approach will be to lead a comprehensive literature review in order to identify more security metrics; develop a tool for automating the most identified security; increase the number of case studies from the previous case study in order to cover the implementation of most of the security metrics and so that the analysis the reliability of the metric with the security will better be conducted.

Full Lehman's laws evaluation: The framework proposed in this thesis is based on foundations derived from the evaluation of the smart contract evolution with respect to the Lehman's laws. However, this framework is based on the evaluation of three of the laws. As this framework intends to be comprehensive, all of Lehman's laws have to be evaluated to identify new insights which can be useful during smart contracts development.

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Appendix

Getting verified smart contracts in Etherscan

Etherscan is a repository used to resort all the data information about Ethereum activity including data related to the smart contracts. It is currently the main source of getting the source code of deployed smart contracts in Ethereum. However, we can access the source code of the smart contract if the latter are verified as not all the smart contracts in Etherscan are verified. A verified smart contract is a contract, which after being deployed in Ethereum, its source code is submitted to the Etherscan, and then validate following a comparison of the byte code in Ethereum and the submitted source code. For the smart contract in which the submitted source code does not match the byte code or smart contract in which the source code has not been submitted (non-verified smart contract), only the byte code will be accessible on Etherscan as shown the Fig 1 below. For those verified smart contracts, the source code will be available on Etherscan. For our study as mentioned in the manuscript, we focus on smart contracts whose sour code is available(verified smart contracts on Ethereum).

Fig 1 Example of non-verified smart contract in Etherscan

Flattened the smart contract source code

A Smart contract development can be carried out on a single file as well as on multiple files(.sol file for Solidity language). So, in order to achieve the measurement of the size and the complexity of the smart contract versions in our research study, each smart contract version(verified smart contract) collected from Etherscan must be flattened into a single file. The flattening step is to combine all dependencies (contract, libraries, and interfaces) of a contract with the main contract code into a single sol file. This step requires that all the dependencies (sol file) of the contract be resolved manually into a single file. Thus for each contract version, we manually flatten the source code as shown the Figure 6. For each file(representing a smart contract version) that stems from this step(flattening), a Solmet script will be executed to obtain the measures of the size and complexity attribute.

Fig 2 Example of a smart contract(RouterFacet) with multiple source files in Etherscan

Contract Name:	RouterFacet	Optimization Enabled:	Yes with 200 runs
Compiler Version	v0.7.6+commit.7338295f	Other Settings:	default evmVersion

Contract Source Code (Solidity Standard Json-Input format)

File 1 of 19 : RouterFacet.sol

```

9 import "../interfaces/IRouter.sol";
10 import "../libraries/LibFeeCalculator.sol";
11 import "../libraries/LibRouter.sol";
12 import "../libraries/LibGovernance.sol";
13
14 contract RouterFacet is IRouter {
15     using Counters for Counters.Counter;
16     using SafeERC20 for IERC20;
17
18     /**
19      * @notice Constructs the Router contract instance and deploys the wrapped ALBT token if not on the Ethereum network
20      * @param _chainId The chainId of the chain where this contract is deployed on
21      * @param _albtToken The address of the original ALBT token in the Ethereum chain
22      */
23     function initRouter(
24         uint8 _chainId,
25         address _albtToken
26     )
27     external override
28     {
29         LibRouter.Storage storage rs = LibRouter.routerStorage();
30         require(!rs.initialized, "Router: already initialized");
31         rs.initialized = true;
32         rs.chainId = _chainId;
33     }

```

File 2 of 19 : SafeERC20.sol

```

1 // SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
2
3 pragma solidity ^0.7.0;
4
5 import "./IERC20.sol";
6 import "../math/SafeMath.sol";
7 import "../utils/Address.sol";
8
9 /**
10  * @title SafeERC20

```

Figure

Fig 3 Flattening the smart contract(RouterFacet) into a single file

```

2066     /// @notice Pauses the contract
2067     function pause() public onlyOwner {
2068         super._pause();
2069     }
2070
2071     /// @notice Unpauses the contract
2072     function unpause() public onlyOwner {
2073         super._unpause();
2074     }
2075
2076     function _beforeTokenTransfer(address from, address to, uint256 _amount) internal virtual override {
2077         super._beforeTokenTransfer(from, to, _amount);
2078
2079         require(!paused(), "WrappedToken: token transfer while paused");
2080     }
2081 }
2082
2083
2084
2085 contract RouterFacet is IRouter {
2086     using Counters for Counters.Counter;
2087     using SafeERC20 for IERC20;
2088
2089     /**
2090      * @notice Constructs the Router contract instance and deploys the wrapped ALBT token if not on the Ethereum network
2091      * @param _chainId The chainId of the chain where this contract is deployed on
2092      * @param _albtToken The address of the original ALBT token in the Ethereum chain
2093      */
2094     function initRouter(
2095         uint8 _chainId,
2096         address _albtToken
2097     )
2098     external override

```

Graph-based evidence of the size, complexity, and quality evolution of all the smart contract projects involved in this research case study.

This section is used to support the Experimental result of smart contract evolution based on the standard upgradability methods used in Ethereum. It provides visual observation through the graph of the size, complexity, and quality trend of the smart contract project involved in this research. As a result, the visual observation of this evidence shows that most of the smart contract projects in this research are in agreement with the 2nd, 6th, and 7th Laws of Lehman. This result observation has been supported by a statistical result provided in the main manuscript.

Size evolution

Fig 4 Size evolution of ACCO

Fig 5 Size evolution of MINTABLE

Fig 6 Size evolution of POLYGONE

Fig 7 size evolution of ROOTCHAIN

Fig 8 Size evolution of STAKE MANAGER

Fig 9 Size evolution of AMORFI

Fig 10 Size evolution of TRUEFI

Fig 12 Size evolution of DELTA

Fig 11 Size evolution of RIBBON

Fig 13 Size evolution of LIQUIDITY

Fig 14 Size evolution of CONNECTOR

Fig 15 Size evolution of EASYBIRD

Fig 16 Size evolution of NYANFINANCE

Fig 17 Size evolution of CAPTIVENIV2

Fig 18 Size evolution of DERIVADEX

Fig 19 Size evolution MAGIC

Fig 20 Size evolution of PREMIA

Fig 21 Size evolution of POLYMORPH

Complexity evolution

Fig 22

Complexity evolution of ACCO

Fig

23 Complexity evolution of MINTABLE

Fig

24 Complexity evolution of POLYGONE

Fig 25 Complexity evolution of ROOTCHAIN

Fig 26 Complexity evolution of STAKEMANAGER

Fig 27 Complexity evolution of AMORFI

Fig 28 Complexity evolution of TRUEFI

Fig 29 Complexity evolution of LIQUIDITY

Fig

30 Complexity evolution of RIBBON

Fig

31 Complexity Evolution of DELTA

Fig

32 Complexity evolution of CONNECTOR

Fig

33 Complexity evolution of EASYBIRD

Fig

34 Complexity evolution of NYANFIANANCE

Fig

35 Complexity evolution of CAPTIVENIV2

Fig

36 Complexity evolution of DERIVADDEX

Fig

37 Complexity Evolution of MAGIC

Fig 38

Complexity evolution of PREMIA

Fig

39 Complexity Evolution of POLYMORPH

Quality evolution

Fig 40 Security issues trend of ACCO

Fig 41 Security issues trend of MINTABLE

Fig 42 Security issues trend of POLYGONE

Fig 43 Security issues trend of ROOTCHAIN

Fig 44 Security issues trend of STAKEMANAGER

Fig 45 Security issues trend of AMORFI

Fig 46 Security issues trend of TRUEFI

Fig 47 Security issues trend of LIQUIDITY

Fig 48 Security issues trend of RIBBON

Fig 49 Security issues trend of DELTA

50 Security issues trend of CONNECTOR

51 Security issues trend of NYANFINANCE

52 Security issues trend of EASYBIRD

53 Security issues trend of CAPTIVNIV2

54 Security issues trend of DERIVADEX

55 Security issues trend of MAGIC

56 Security issues trend of PREMIA

57 Security issues trend of POLYMORPH